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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Description		
<i>3GPP</i>	3rd Generation Partnership Project	<i>MPTCP</i>	Multipath Transmission Control Protocol
<i>4G</i>	Fourth Generation	<i>MQTT</i>	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
<i>5G</i>	Fifth Generation	<i>MS</i>	Model Swapping
<i>6G</i>	Sixth Generation	<i>mMTC</i>	massive Machine-Type Communications
<i>AGV</i>	Automated Guided Vehicle	<i>NEF</i>	Network Exposure Function
<i>AI</i>	Artificial Intelligence	<i>NGAP</i>	Next Generation Autonomous Positioning
<i>AIA</i>	Athens International Airport	<i>NPN</i>	Non-Public Network
<i>AMR</i>	Autonomous Mobile Robot	<i>NSA</i>	Non-Standalone
<i>AP</i>	Access Point	<i>ORO</i>	Orange Romania
<i>API</i>	Application Programming Interfaces	<i>P2PNet</i>	Point-to-Point Network
<i>APN</i>	Access Point Name	<i>PCAP</i>	Packet Capture app
<i>AR</i>	Augmented Reality	<i>PDU</i>	Protocol Data Unit
<i>ASI</i>	Adaptive Stream Inference	<i>PHY</i>	Physical layer
<i>B5G</i>	Beyond 5G	<i>PPE</i>	Personal Protective Equipment
<i>BSSID</i>	Basic Service Set Identifier	<i>PPDR</i>	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
<i>CNAP</i>	Charging Network Analytics Platform	<i>PTZ</i>	Pan-Tilt-Zoom
<i>CPU</i>	Central Processing Unit	<i>PU</i>	Public
<i>CR</i>	Control Room	<i>QoD</i>	Quality of Demand
<i>CPEs</i>	Customer Premise Equipment's	<i>QoS</i>	Quality of Service
<i>DEM</i>	Digital Elevation Models	<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network
<i>DL</i>	Downlink	<i>RAM</i>	Random Access Memory
<i>DNN</i>	Deep Neural Networks	<i>REST</i>	Representational State Transfer
<i>DT</i>	Digital Twin	<i>ROS2</i>	Robot Operating System
<i>E2E</i>	End to End	<i>RSSI</i>	Received Signal Strength Indicator
<i>eMBB</i>	enhanced Mobile Broadband	<i>RTK</i>	Real-Time Kinematic
<i>EV</i>	Electrical Vehicle	<i>RTT</i>	Round-Trip Latency
<i>FPS</i>	Frames per Second	<i>RTSP</i>	Real-Time Streaming Protocol
<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation	<i>SA</i>	Standalone
<i>GNSS</i>	Global Navigation Satellite Systems	<i>SIM</i>	Subscriber Identity Module
<i>GPU</i>	Graphics Processing Units	<i>SME</i>	Small Medium Enterprise
<i>GPS</i>	Global Positioning System	<i>SLAM</i>	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
<i>GUI</i>	Graphical User Interface	<i>SLV</i>	SkyLink Vision
<i>HMI</i>	Human-Machine Interface	<i>SSE</i>	Server-Sent Events
<i>HTPLS</i>	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Live Streaming	<i>STS</i>	Serviciul de Telecomunicații Speciale
<i>IIoT</i>	Industrial Internet of Things	<i>TAA</i>	Transformer Attention Layers
<i>IMEC</i>	Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre	<i>TCN</i>	Temporal Convolutional Network
<i>IMUs</i>	Inertial Measurement Units	<i>TDD</i>	Time Division Duplexing
<i>IPsec</i>	Internet Protocol Security	<i>TUIASI</i>	Technical University Gheorghe Asachi
<i>ITSS</i>	Infrastructure, Transportation, Security & Safety	<i>UAV</i>	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
<i>iSOC</i>	intelligence Security Operations Centre	<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>KPIs</i>	Key Performance Indicators	<i>UM</i>	User Management
<i>KVIs</i>	Key Value Indicators	<i>UL</i>	Uplink
<i>LiDAR</i>	Light Detection and Ranging	<i>UPF</i>	User Plane Functions
<i>MCX</i>	Mission Critical Communications	<i>URLLC</i>	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
<i>ML</i>	Machine Learning	<i>YOLO</i>	You Only Look Once
		<i>VPN</i>	Virtual Private Network

VR
VRUs
ZSM

Virtual Reality
Vulnerable Road Users
Zero-touch network and Service
Management

WebRTC
WP
WPA

Web Real-Time Communication
Work Package
Web Progressive Application

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Executive Summary

This document, D3.3, provides a detailed presentation of the outcomes from all the use cases developed and executed under Work Package 3 (WP3), including the additional ones introduced through the Open Call process. The document is the final public deliverable of WP3, following the deliverable D3.2 [1] which was finalized in March 2024 and provided an intermediate overview of the progress at that time.

The purpose of D3.3 is to report a summary of the final implementation steps, trials execution, and the results obtained, structured by use case. The document covers the final integration activities, system-level validations, and the collection of performance indicators based on real-world trials. All use cases have reached full trial deployment, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs) have been measured according to the methodology defined earlier in the project. Each use case was trialed in a relevant environment to validate its performance under realistic operational conditions. The trials confirmed the technical feasibility of the proposed solutions and provided detailed performance results.

A short summary of the implementation of each use case concluding with the final trial is given below. As UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” has been developed in two sites, Madrid and Iasi, it is detailed in different sections.

Use Case 1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” (Madrid): UC1 addressed the need for enhanced security and situational awareness in crowded public venues through the use of mobile surveillance technologies connected to the Fifth Generation (5G) network. The setup combined high-resolution cameras, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors, and autonomous ground robots equipped with Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based analytics. These systems were managed remotely from a centralized intelligence Security Operations Centre (iSOC) over a dedicated 5G network. The final implementation of the use case included the integration of a robotic platform, intended for user interaction and public assistance, complementing the surveillance roles of robots. System architecture was updated with two 5G Customer Premise Equipment’s (CPEs) to ensure reliable connectivity and data routing between sensors, robots, and the iSOC server, which was equipped with Genetec software for alarm handling and device control. After pre-trials and lab tests focused on validating communication stability, AI event detection, and system response, the final field trial took place during a live basketball event on March 16, 2025, at Movistar Arena in Madrid. The event, attended by approximately 2000 people, provided a realistic setting to test robot navigation, remote video monitoring, and alert verification under actual operating conditions. All components operated over a 5G Rel-17 standalone private network, enabling real-time control and responsiveness across the system.

Use Case 1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” (Iasi): This use case focused on real-time crowd monitoring during public events on Ștefan cel Mare Boulevard in Iași, Romania. It used fixed high-resolution cameras installed on lighting poles and connected via 5G to monitor the crowd size, movement, and potential anomalies such as unauthorized access. Video feeds are processed locally or remotely through edge computing resources provided by Technical University Gheorghe Asachi (TUIASI) and Orange Romania (ORO), ensuring fast, secure, and privacy-compliant analytics. The solution was initially deployed on a 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) setup using Nokia Fastmile routers, Cisco switches, WiFi Access Points and private Access Point Name (APN) Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) cards. Video analytics applications were developed and hosted on TUIASI servers and integrated with ORO’s 5G Lab via a secured Virtual Private Network (VPN). In 2024, the software stack was fully refactored using the Savant framework, with milestones including dashboard creation, people counting, heatmaps, and video anonymization. The first trial took place in December 2024 under NSA configuration, while the final trial occurred in May 2025 after upgrading to a full 5G Standalone (SA) setup with local edge and Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) slicing. Pre-trials activities included single-camera, multi-camera, and full deployment scenarios with up to 13 cameras streaming in parallel. The trials confirmed the system’s operational capability under real conditions and helped validate system performance in terms of scalability, latency, and processing efficiency.

Use Case 2 “Public Infrastructure Assets Management” (Athens): This use case demonstrated a 5G-enabled solution for infrastructure condition monitoring using mobile robots, drones, and fixed cameras in urban and airport environments. The system used AI for damage detection (e.g., cracks, potholes) and a visualization dashboard to assist operators in preventive maintenance decisions. The trial sites included Athens International Airport (AIA) and the Technopolis area within the Municipality of Athens. The WINGSPARK platform, supporting this use case, progressed from partial development to a functional state, with major components

finalized, including video analysis pipelines, data ingestion, device management, and the visualization dashboard. AI models for detecting surface damage were improved and integrated into a streaming pipeline that processes input from mobile robots and IP cameras. Trial preparations included both lab and field testing to validate detection accuracy, latency, and uplink performance. Two field trials were executed: one at AIA in January 2025 using a 5G-connected Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) equipped with depth cameras and streaming modules, and another in June 2025 at Technopolis with the same robotic setup and expanded sensor suite (LiDAR, Global Positioning System-GPS, Inertial Measurement Units- IMUs). Both trials validated real-time remote inspection capabilities via the wi.MOVE dashboard. The trials showed the benefits of 5G for high-bandwidth video processing and highlighted limitations of commercial 5G in supporting high-resolution, low-latency applications, reinforcing the need for future Sixth Generation (6G) or 5G SA enhancements.

Use Case 3 “Autonomous APRON” (Athens): UC3 showcased an Autonomous APRON operation for baggage transport using an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) at AIA. The system uses a Digital Twin (DT) for remote monitoring, AI-based navigation and obstacle detection, and Beyond 5G (B5G) communication for low-latency control and video streaming. The solution aims to improve efficiency, safety, and coordination in ground handling operations through real-time data and robotic automation. The system was developed around the WINGSChariot platform (Wi.SUPPLY), which enables real-time monitoring and remote control of the AGV, integrating a Unity-based DT and a visualization dashboard. Enhancements included video streaming from a 360° camera, LiDAR-based obstacle detection, and real-time AGV tracking. Communication between robotic components and the cloud was established via Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and Robot Operating System (ROS2). A field trial took place on 6 March 2025 in a secured apron area of the airport. The AGV autonomously navigated between predefined waypoints, transporting luggage under operator supervision via the DT and dashboard interface. The trial validated the solution’s performance in terms of autonomy, responsiveness, and integration of real-time data over a 5G network.

Use Case 4 “Smart Traffic Management” (Iasi): This use case focused on improving urban mobility and road safety at the Podu Roş intersection in Iaşi by deploying AI-based traffic monitoring over a B5G network. The system leveraged real-time video feeds from six high-resolution cameras to detect traffic flow, monitor vehicle and pedestrian behavior, and trigger alerts for hazardous situations involving Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs). Video analytics applications, hosted on TUIASI edge infrastructure, process incoming streams and publish insights to a Kafka-based backend, enabling live monitoring via a centralized dashboard. UC4 builds on the software architecture used in UC1, consisting of three core components: video processing (using You Only Look Once v7- YOLOv7), metadata handling, and a dashboard interface for visualization and alerts. The configuration was adapted to the Podu Roş intersection to address specific traffic scenarios such as vehicle counting, car flow estimation, and restricted zone violations. The solution integrates Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre (IMEC)-Ghent’s zero-touch orchestration and dual 5G connectivity (NSA and SA) via Multipath Transmission Control Protocol (MPTCP), ensuring higher reliability and throughput. Field trials were conducted in two phases. The first, in December 2024, was executed over a 5G NSA network and validated the application’s basic functionalities and inference pipeline. The second, in May 2025, used a 5G SA network and tested full system capabilities under realistic, high-traffic conditions with multi-camera inputs. Both trials assessed the system’s responsiveness, scalability, and support for real-time analytics.

Use Case 5 “Control Room in Metaverse” (Turin): UC5 focused on enhancing the coordination and operational efficiency of safety and security forces through a metaverse control room. Designed with the input of Turin's emergency services, the application supports real-time collaboration between police, fire brigades, ambulance teams, and civil protection units. It simulates large-scale emergencies enabling teams to interact via avatars, share media from the field, and access real-time video feeds and sensors’ data. A comprehensive trial scenario was prepared in close collaboration with local authorities. The trial, held in October 2024 in Turin’s Valentino Park, involved 18 agents from four emergency services, using Virtual Reality (VR) headsets, 5G-connected tablets and smartphones, and streaming equipment. The scenario simulated a multi-agency response to a staged car accident, testing real-time collaboration and information sharing across all teams. Agents navigated the virtual space, communicated within their units, and uploaded live video and photos from the scene in the metaverse. The application was well received by the users, although field use highlighted the need for ergonomic improvements, such as preferring bodycams over tablets and simplifying media uploading. Feedback from participants confirmed the potential of the tool for improving coordination during emergencies.

This deliverable presents also a comprehensive overview of the transition from controlled trial environments to full-scale commercial deployment for all WP3 use cases, evaluating current 5G capabilities against the demands of widespread implementation. It delves into critical aspects like performance requirements (e.g., throughput, latency, reliability), network functionalities (e.g., dynamic resource allocation, fault tolerance, slicing), infrastructure deployment considerations (e.g., coverage, edge computing, device compatibility), and other vital factors (e.g., security, AI accuracy, sustainability, stakeholder engagement), ultimately identifying how next-generation 6G technologies are essential to overcome existing limitations and enable seamless, city-wide service realization.

This document reports also on the 11 additional use cases related sub-projects of the Open Call that belong to the ITSS domain and which involve advanced 5G technologies in various contexts, including autonomous transport, surveillance systems, AI-driven emergency handling, and urban accessibility. The activities of each sub-project included rigorous testing phases designed to optimize performance and validate system functionalities under real-world conditions. In addition, the sub-projects introduced also new sites, infrastructures, and facilities - such as operational trams, airport areas, industrial plants, city camera networks, and EV charging stations - that significantly expanded the experimentation footprint and provided diverse real-world environments for validation. A short summary of the use case description and trial of each sub-project is given below.

Connected Rails (Florence): This sub-project focused on enhancing tramway operations through advanced onboard positioning and 5G communication technologies. It was demonstrated on Florence's operational tram system, using tram 1013 in normal service. The tram was equipped with an autonomous positioning system, Next Generation Autonomous Positioning System (SYS-NGAP) and a 5G signal collection unit, Software Defined Radio (SYS-SDR). These systems were tested in real conditions without disrupting daily service. SYS-NGAP used integrated sensors for high-accuracy positioning, while SYS-SDR collected 5G signal data for positioning validation and network quality analysis. Results confirmed that 5G can support real-time services, though network continuity still requires optimization.

5GS3 (Patra): The sub-project targeted enhancing surveillance and incident response in critical infrastructure settings, with airports as the primary scenario. It introduced autonomous robotic platforms equipped with AI-based analytics, operating over 5G/B5G networks to perform real-time patrolling, object detection, and remote control through a centralized dashboard. The system was validated through staged trials, ending with a live demonstration at AIA. Robots operated autonomously and responded to detected anomalies, showcasing smooth navigation and real-time communication. Technical KPIs such as latency, detection accuracy, and availability met the required thresholds, confirming system reliability. User feedback highlighted strong acceptance, ease of use, and confidence in the system's ability to improve security operations with minimal manual intervention.

Skylink Vision (Madrid): This sub-project demonstrated a real-time aerial surveillance system based on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), AI analytics, and 5G connectivity. It was designed to support traffic monitoring and public safety by transmitting high-resolution video from UAVs to ground-based AI systems for real-time analysis, bypassing the processing limitations of onboard hardware. The platform was tested using a UAV hardware setup with live video and telemetry streaming over 5G. The trials confirmed the system's ability to detect and track vehicles with high precision and to provide stable video feeds with minimal packet loss. While the strict latency target was only met with optimized configurations, communication performance was generally strong. Operator feedback confirmed trust in the system's reliability, ease of use, and suitability for fast deployment in field operations, supporting its potential for broader use in emergency response and urban surveillance.

CITY4ALL (Turin): This sub-project explored how VR, AI, and 5G connectivity can raise awareness about disabilities and promote inclusion. The project developed a VR game simulating motor, visual, and auditory impairments, using immersive storytelling to help players understand accessibility challenges. A cloud-rendered version enhanced by 5G was also implemented to showcase higher-quality experiences, alongside an integrated AI assistant for additional educational support. Trials were conducted in two educational environments, engaging both secondary school and university students. The simulations successfully increased understanding and empathy regarding disabilities, with strong user engagement reported across all groups. While some technical limitations were observed with commercial 5G networks, especially related to latency, performance improved under controlled 5G SA conditions. Overall, the project demonstrated the educational value of immersive VR and highlighted its potential as a tool for inclusive learning.

AI-PREMSET(Iasi): This sub-project focused on enhanced emergency response by optimizing 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)-compliant Mission Critical Communications (MCX) over 5G and future networks. It used AI and Machine Learning (ML) to monitor, analyze, and adapt communication services in real time, ensuring reliable performance even in challenging conditions. A live trial was held in Romania in April 2025, combining end-user training with real-time group communication tests involving emergency personnel and students. The trials confirmed system stability, especially when network coverage was good. AI-driven service adaptation proved effective in minimizing disruption and maintaining communication quality. User feedback was positive, highlighting the tool's potential for improving public safety operations. The results support the use of AI for smarter, more resilient MCX deployments in next-generation mobile networks.

MILESTONE (Athens): This sub-project aimed at improving worker safety in public infrastructure environments using 5G connectivity, AI-driven computer vision, and secure access control. It enables real-time detection of safety issues like missing Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) or unauthorized access through video analytics and immediate alerts to supervisors. The system streams video from edge devices to the cloud, where AI models process footage for hazards. A trial at Technopolis in Athens involved 32 participants. Workers were monitored by 5G-connected cameras, and safety violations were detected and reported in real time. Supervisors tested the interface and provided feedback. Performance metrics met the targets, with low latency, high AI accuracy, and strong user confidence in system reliability, security, and sustainability—confirming solution potential for safe, smart infrastructure management.

ATOS (Netherlands): The ATOS Driving sub-project demonstrated remote vehicle control over a B5G network to support future teleoperation in logistics. It involved deploying an experimental B5G infrastructure and testing a full teleoperation system on a truck operating within a controlled area in the Netherlands. The sub-project integrated a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to manage network resources, collect performance data, and monitor energy use. These features allowed for dynamic Quality of Service (QoS) adjustments, real-time metric tracking, and energy-efficient service orchestration. Trials were held over three phases between late 2024 and early 2025. Remote operation was conducted both on-site and from Roboauto's facility in the Czech Republic. The system showed strong performance in realistic conditions, with stable control, consistent feedback, and minimal data loss. Although reliability was slightly below target, overall functionality met requirements for real-world use.

i-CNC (Paiania): This sub-project brought AI and 5G into industrial connected machining to improve quality and efficiency by detecting and reacting to milling chatter in real time. It enabled centralized monitoring through Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) sensors, low-latency 5G connectivity, and an AI-based detection system that supports operators during production. The system architecture included sensor units mounted on machines in two locations, which send vibration data via 5G to a cloud database and an AI module. The AI algorithm analyzes the signals and provides real-time alerts to operators through a local interface. A trial held in March 2025 involved 30 participants and showcased the system in a real industrial setting. Attendees observed live chatter detection and interacted with connected machines while receiving instant feedback from the AI system. Results confirmed that both network and application latencies remained within acceptable limits for manufacturing use. The system reduced downtime and material waste, improving efficiency and operator workflows.

AdaptoFlow (Iasi): The sub-project aimed at enhancing real-time video analytics in 5G edge environments by improving performance, scalability, and energy efficiency. The provided solution processes IP camera streams using deep learning models for object detection on edge servers connected through a 5G network. Trials in Romania tested solution with multiple city cameras streaming to an edge server. The results showed significant improvements in latency, network traffic, and computational load, enabling more camera streams without overloading the system and maintaining stable 5G performance. Validated against the TrialsNet value model, AdaptoFlow demonstrated strong economic, environmental, and social benefits. It reduces infrastructure demands and carbon footprint while supporting open-source research and promoting social value, making it a strong candidate for future B5G edge analytics.

AI4RTC (Athens): This sub-project focused on deploying a Charging Network Analytics Platform (CNAP) that balances power loads across Electrical Vehicle (EV) charging stations to prevent power peaks affecting local infrastructure or grid stability. Leveraging 5G connectivity and AI-driven forecasting, the platform enabled rapid, real-time responses to power fluctuations for efficient and reliable charging operations. The trial was conducted across multiple EV stations in Athens, Greece. Trials involved everyday users at five sites with

upgraded charging outlets. Performance monitoring showed significant improvements in throughput, latency, and reliability, with facility managers reporting high satisfaction and trust in the system. Overall, the trial demonstrated that combining 5G connectivity with AI analytics provides a scalable, responsive, and trustworthy solution for managing EV charging loads, supporting grid stability and improving operational efficiency.

Cities w/o Barriers (Turin): This sub-project aimed to improve urban accessibility for people with mobility challenges by using 5G-connected mobile devices and AI analytics to identify architectural barriers. Devices like smartphones and edge-processing modules collect data on obstacles such as uneven surfaces and narrow pathways. This data is processed locally for efficiency, then sent to the cloud where AI performs detailed analysis to generate dynamic accessibility maps with real-time information and scores. Trials took place in Turin in two phases - mapping and navigation - over 10 months. Operators collected data on over 500 km of routes despite challenges like weather and engagement issues. Network KPIs were measured, showing stable latency and performance, though some variability and stability issues arose due to 5G-Fourth Generation (4G) transitions in NSA architecture. Overall, the project demonstrated strong potential for enhancing urban accessibility and scalability to other cities.

Together with the core use case and trials, these sub-projects contributed to further strengthen the results and outcomes related to the ITSS domain, as the document will detail.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides a consolidated overview of the final implementation and trials of all use cases, including the ones of the sub-projects onboarded through the Open Call, developed within WP3. It builds upon the previous deliverable D3.2, offering a comprehensive update on the implementation progress, trial execution activities, and performance outcomes. The scope of the deliverable is to present the results from the final integration steps, describe how trials were conducted in operational environments, and summarize the performance indicators collected through real-world trials. All the use cases of the ITSS domain reached the final deployment phase and were evaluated using both technical and user-centric metrics based on the related processes defined in the context of the project. The document also reflects on the applicability of various solutions for future deployments and identifies relevant considerations for their scalability and operational integration. This document is structured as follows.

Section 2, describes the final implementation status of the WP3 core use cases. It covers the integration of all components required for deployment, the design of the system architecture, and the implementation of the applications and back-end services. Progress since the last reporting phase is detailed, showing how each use case evolved from early prototypes to finalized systems ready for trial. The development activities addressed both software and hardware aspects, ensuring that the solutions function reliably in the targeted environments. Changes to the system components, interface designs, and data processing workflows are included as part of the final implementation package.

Section 3 presents how the trials were organized, carried out, and evaluated. It outlines the planning efforts, including logistics, stakeholder coordination, and preparatory testing required before trial execution. The trials took place in environments aligned with the intended operational contexts and followed predefined scenarios that allowed for structured data collection and evaluation. Performance were assessed by measuring KPIs and KVIs, based on the methodology defined earlier in the project. Results were obtained through a mix of live data collection, system monitoring, and post-trial analysis. Network conditions and application behavior were observed under realistic usage, enabling validation of both technical feasibility and user interaction and perceived quality. Differences between the intermediate tests and final trials are also captured, showing the evolution in system reliability and responsiveness.

Section 4 reflects on the deployment phase of each use case, summarizing challenges encountered, decisions made, and lessons learned. The process of deploying each solution into a real-world setting required attention to integration timelines, system configuration, and compatibility with network and device requirements. The section also considers how the solutions could be adapted or scaled for wider adoption, noting infrastructure dependencies and resource requirements. Overall, it emphasizes the practical aspects of bringing complex systems from development to deployment and provides guidance for similar future implementations.

Section 5 includes the additional use cases and trials introduced through the project's Open Call, which expanded the range and diversity of the core use cases of WP3. These use cases followed the same development and trial process as the core use cases and have reached the final stage of implementation. Furthermore, the integration of some of the sub-project's use cases in the TrialsNet infrastructures, further validated the flexibility of the project platform and network solutions and the potential for applying its components in other operational scenarios.

Finally, Section 6 summarizes the key results and conclusions of the use case implementation and validation activities. The trials confirmed the readiness of the developed solutions to function in realistic environments and provided valuable insight into system behavior, user interaction, and network performance identifying which aspects could be relevant in the design of the next generation of mobile networks

Due to the extended data measurements available from both pre-trial activities and the final trials, the pre-trial results of some use cases have been reported in Annex A to Annex D of this deliverable to streamline the main body of the document. In addition, Annex E, reports the questionnaire used for the KVIs assessment activity.

2 Use Cases final implementation

2.1 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Madrid)

UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” in Madrid aims to enhance security in crowded sports venues using advanced telecommunication technology to support the implementation of a security system. The use case involves deploying surveillance cameras (Pan-Tilt-Zoom-PTZ and fixed), a LiDAR sensor and robots using AI algorithms to detect abnormal situations such as crowding in access areas, violence, vandalism, and suspicious activities. Three ground robots equipped with cameras and AI conducted autonomous and remote-controlled security rounds and video assistance to attendees. All security devices are controlled from a remote iSOC position which receives the alerts and allows security personnel to take control of different devices to verify them. A 5G/B5G Ericsson Non-Public Network (NPN) was used during the trial, and network performance during video streaming and robot control were measured.

2.1.1 Update on development activities

Activities related to UC1 – Madrid have been focused on determining the final infrastructure of the application, as well as the integration and configuration of each of the different devices involved in the trial so that they were able to connect to ERC’s CPEs. This was carried out via several joint test in 5Tonic premises, reported in Annex A.

There have been several updates from the application overview in deliverable D3.2 [1] to the final application. In particular, for the final implementation of the UC, a third robotic platform (Amarelo) was added to the already included robotic platforms Yellow (SPOT) and Kiir0 (SummitXL). The robot Amarelo (Temi) has been used as a service robot, interacting with attendees and guiding them to key areas of the venue. Moreover, the setup related to the previous application version have been updated based on the infrastructure deployed for the trial (as in D3.2 [1]). The new setup is described in the following section.

2.1.2 Final application overview

In terms of architecture and connectivity, the transmission of information among the different setups is made through a private 5G network, both locally and to the internet (see Figure 1). A private APN has been set up to secure communication between the devices and the iSOC. The device was connected via ethernet switch to CPE 2, which transmit the information via 5G high-band to CPE 1 in the Control Room (CR) and to the remote iSOC server. The 5G high-band connection was ensured by the 5Tonic Radio Access Network (RAN) equipment and set-up and the 5G antenna located in Movistar Arena (formerly known as Wizink Center) by Ericsson.

Figure 1. Deployment Architecture Diagram for UC1.

The application (see Figure 2) involved two different groups of devices and software. The first were located on the upper floor of the entrance, in the control room, and related to the iSOC. The second were control located on the ground floor and composed the security equipment.

Figure 2. Application overview for UC1. Flow of data and alerts.

The setup of the iSOC consists of the following equipment:

- **iSOC Server:** A DELL Precision 3930 Rack XCTO Base server with an Intel Xeon E-2136 CPU makes up the hardware component of the iSOC. Genetec Security Center [2] is the primary software. Through Genetec Industrial IoT, it may receive signals from sensors and Information Architecture (IA) alerts using the MQTT protocol. Genetec also permits the direct connection of cameras. The server's MQTT broker makes it easier to control the signals and permits future direct integration with other services, if necessary. Simultaneously, the KiIRO's technical alarms can be received through Genetec's Representational State Transfer (REST) API. It has to be clarified that the Human–Machine Interface (HMI) (KiIRO's internal platform) is accessed locally while the Nimbus is a Cloud-based platform accessed via Internet.
- **MQTT Broker:** An MQTT Broker was in charge of centralizing all processed signals and alerts.
- **iSentry Server:** the AI server received all video streams from the cameras, processed the videos, and launched alerts to the MQTT Broker to be received in Genetec.
- **Yellow Controller:** The Android control device with the Yellow control software received and sent commands to the robot.

The setup of the control system consists of the following devices and robots:

- **Devices:** Security devices include one LiDAR Ouster Operating System 0 (OS0), one fixed camera (HIKVISION DS-2CD2686G2T-IZS), and one PTZ camera (HIKVISION DS-2DE3A400BW-DE). The LiDAR information is transmitted to Gemini [3], a perception platform that is installed on a Personal Computer (PC) and allows for the configuration of several detection zones (pre-alert and alert). The alerts are sent to Genetec via the MQTT Broker.
- **Yellow:** Yellow robotic platform is also managed and programmed using its own application. It has the capacity to go up and downstairs and is equipped with cameras.
- **KiIRO:** missions and routes are programmed through HMI (KiIRO's local application) and Nimbus, a cloud-based software that enables the management of ROS/ROS2-based robotic platforms. KiIRO is also equipped with cameras, sensors and has AI processing capabilities thanks to the NVIDIA Graphics Processing Units (GPU) card contained in the AI Appliance that has been integrated in KiIRO's payload. Alerts for AI models are sent to the MQTT broker and forwarded as Genetec alerts.

- **Amarelo:** Amarelo robotic platform is also managed with its own cloud and management platform. It is equipped with cameras, sensors, a screen and microphone that allows it to capture and recognize voice commands. It is controlled from the iSOC position using Temi's own cloud control software [4].

Different software platforms were used to manage the devices involved in the solution. Genetec was the main software used to receive and manage all alerts from robots, cameras and AI; as well as LiDAR alerts, though the LiDAR's point-cloud was processed via OUSTER's software Gemini. Genetec provides a simple UI where the iSOC operator is able to collect and receive notifications from alerts coming from different devices in real time. Robot tasks were managed via Kiirro HMI and Nimbus cloud platform, as well as Yellow's controller. Nimbus is a robotic fleet management software, which is able to integrate mission planning, area maps, and camera streamings from multiple robotic platforms. Kiirro HMI is able to manage the robot's movements, mission planning, maps and integrated sensors (e.g cameras and LiDAR). In the Figure 3 below, the GUI of the different platforms are showcased.

Figure 3. GUIs for UC1 Madrid. From left to right: Gemini, Kiirro's HMI, Nimbus, Genetec.

2.2 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Iasi)

UC1 focuses on smart crowd monitoring on Ștefan cel Mare Boulevard, a busy pedestrian area in Iași, Romania. The goal is to monitor public events (cultural or religious), estimate crowd sizes, analyse movement dynamics, and detect anomalies like unauthorized vehicles. High-resolution panoramic cameras connected via Nokia Fast-mile 5G routers and CISCO switches are installed on lighting poles and linked to ORO's private 5G network. Video feeds are processed in real time on TUIASI servers through a secure Internet Protocol Security Virtual Private Network (IPsec VPN) tunnel with ORO's 5G Lab in Bucharest. The system integrates data into a unified operational platform for enhanced situational awareness. It supports public safety monitoring using B5G/6G and Wi-Fi technologies.

2.2.1 Update on development activities

The technical implementation of UC 1 Iasi has progressed significantly during 2024 and 2025. Initially, the solution was built on ORO commercial 5G NSA deployment, as was already showcased in D3.2 [1], leveraging hardware such as surveillance cameras and Nokia Fastmile 5G routers equipped with private APN SIM cards. These devices provided secure connectivity to ORO's 5G Lab in Bucharest, where edge computing resources processed video feeds for crowd monitoring and public safety applications. Data transmission utilized an IPsec VPN tunnel linking ORO's 5G Lab and the, whose servers hosted video analytics applications. This setup enabled efficient video inference and visualization.

By the end of 2024, critical infrastructure preparations for upgrades were completed, including the installation of edge-computer servers at the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter and the preparation for the deployment of a local 5G SA, User Plane Functions (UPF) unit, as presented in Figure 4. The SA capabilities have been activated in April 2025. This enhanced architecture enabled low-latency transmission (8 ms end-to-end) through a dedicated URLLC slice.

Figure 4. UC1 5G and Edge-Compute final architecture.

Since the last report, the application software underwent extensive and significant development. The whole application was refactored to use the Savant computer vision framework [5], for easier managing of the video analytics pipeline. Several milestones have been achieved, including the finalization of the visualization dashboard, which delivers real-time insights such as people counting, density heatmaps, and alarm notifications, as well as the implementation of the video privacy-preserving measures following the software development steps, as summarized in Table 1, covering both UC1 and UC4 use cases.

Table 1. Status for software development activities UC1 and UC4.

Software development activity / feature	Current implementation status
Main video analysis pipeline	Done in Q1 2024
Containerized application services	Done in Q2 2024
Visualization dashboard	Done in Q3 2024
Privacy protection methods on video	Done in Q3 2024
Parallel display for multiple cameras	Done in Q1 2024
Establish a deployment procedure	Done in Q4 2024
Extrinsic calibration of video cameras	Done in Q2 2025
User interface for application control	Done in Q2 2025
Density analytics application	Done in Q2 2025
Multi-model inference and display	Done in Q2 2025
Advanced post-processing rules for object detection	Done in Q2 2025

2.2.2 Final application overview

The overall architecture of the application system is reported in the Figure 5 hereafter.

Figure 5. UC1 application architecture overview.

There are three main components in the system:

- **The Video Processing component:** This is responsible for all video processing and object detection with AI models. It is based on the Savant framework, which is in turn based in the NVIDIA DeepStream libraries [6] for fast real-time video inference. It consists of several Docker services (containers), working according to the general architecture of the Savant library. The video streams are incoming from the 23 cameras mounted around the central pedestrian areas of Stefan cel Mare Boulevard and the Palat area. The video processing component produces two types of output:
 - Streams of anonymous metadata for object detections (e.g., object class, position, bounding box, area), which are sent to the Data Processing component for further processing and storage.
 - Video streams with the detected objects overlaid on the original video streams, which can optionally be displayed in a web interface, or inspected for debugging purposes.
- **The Data Processing component:** This is responsible for managing and processing object metadata, generating alerts, and long-term storage of the data. It is based on the Kafka ecosystem together with a PostgreSQL database service. The Kafka ecosystem includes a Kafka broker, a schema registry, a ksqlDB server for real-time stream processing, and a Kafka Connect service configured for transferring data to PostgreSQL. The PostgreSQL database is based on the TimescaleDB extension [7] and is used for long-term storage of the data.
- **Reporting and Observability:** This component is responsible for visualization of data, using the Grafana observability platform [8], and possibly for generating reports and alerts based on the data. The component pulls data from the PostgreSQL database and from the Kafka ecosystem and displays it in a web interface. Optionally, it can display the video streams produced by the Video Processing component.

In the following, each component is further detailed.

Video Processing

The video processing pipeline is based on the Savant framework, and it consists of several Docker services (containers), either for direct video processing, or for supporting services. A general overview is provided here, as illustrated in Figure 6. For a more in-depth description of Savant, see the Savant documentation [5].

The AI models used for inference are from the YOLOv7 family, publicly available [9], pretrained on the Microsoft COCO dataset [10], as well as the Point-to-Point Network (P2PNet) [11], also publicly available, pretrained on the ShanghaiTech Part A dataset [12].

Figure 6. Architecture of the video processing component for UC1 and UC4 application.

There are three types of containers handling the video streams:

- **Source containers:** receive and decode Real-Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) video streams. Each source container internally captures the video from a single RTSP stream and publishes the decoded frames to the queue of an inference module. Each source container corresponds to a single camera, but several source containers can publish data to the same inference module, effectively achieving source multiplexing.

If a RTSP source goes down, the container stops and then is restarted automatically, without affecting the rest of the pipeline (if the Docker restart policy is set to always, as recommended). This is a particular advantage of the Savant architecture, which separates source and sink containers from the actual inference module.

- **Module containers:** handle inference for object detection, including post-processing via custom plugins developed. The processing includes:
 - Actual object detection (bounding box, class) and tracking across frames.
 - Determining and counting objects which are present in certain regions. These regions are statically configured for every camera, at the image level, as polygons.
 - Calculating the GPS coordinates of objects.
 - Publishing this metadata on the Kafka message broker.
 - Blurring the detected objects in the video data, for privacy reasons.

There can be several inference modules instantiated in the system, sharing the available GPUs. Each module container handles the video stream incoming from one or more source containers.

- **Sink container:** encodes and publishes the output video streams from inference modules.

There are several supporting services instantiated in the system which are not part of the video pipeline itself but are helpful alongside it. Among those is a Jaeger tracing service, which is used for keeping track of the latency introduced at every processing step.

Data Processing

The Data Processing component is built around the Kafka real-time message broker and a PostgreSQL-based database server (TimescaleDB), as illustrated in Figure 7. In general, the object metadata messages incoming from the video analysis module are processed using the ksqlDB stream processing server and eventually stored in a PostgreSQL database per-unit of time and per-region.

Figure 7. Architecture of the Data Processing component for UC1 and UC4 application.

The people counting data, as it is showcased in Figure 8, is stored in separate tables per camera and region, for every frame, and also as continuous aggregates averaged over windows of 1 second, 10 seconds and 1 minute, to enable different time resolutions and easier long-term storage policies.

Figure 8. Sample people count data: raw count message in the Kafka broker (top) and related table (bottom).

Reporting and Observability

A Grafana service is used to display dashboards with relevant information to the users. There is a dashboard for every camera view used in the system. The dashboard for camera 1 on pole 5, on the Stefan cel Mare pedestrian street in front of the Metropolitan cathedral, is depicted in Figure 9. The dashboard includes the following information:

- A (optional) low resolution output video stream, with detected objects (blurred) and regions marked. The video can be removed from the dashboard, for users which do not have the authorization to view the stream.
- Live people counters, for each defined region.
- A live heatmap depicting the crowd distribution, overlaid on a map.
- A detailed list and a summary of latest alerts. Ongoing alerts are marked red.

Figure 9. UC1 web dashboard for camera 1, pole 5, on the Stefan cel Mare pedestrian street.

The access to the dashboard web server, as well as access to each individual camera dashboard, can be assigned and tailored for each user, based on the User Management (UM) features of Grafana.

2.3 UC2: Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management

This use case, developed at the Athens site, involves a cutting-edge solution for Proactive Public Infrastructure Asset Management. Data is collected from sources like security cameras, drones, municipal vehicles, and AGVs, and processed with AI and Deep Learning (DL) to assess the condition of infrastructure assets. Initially tested in a lab at WINGS, the deployment was subsequently extended to the AIA and the Municipality of Athens. The solution helps monitor the structural health of buildings, pavements, and roads, improving maintenance efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing services. AR technology enables construction workers to communicate with remote experts, while AI provides predictive maintenance and safety alerts. A DT win tracks faults, and a B5G network ensures fast, reliable data exchange for better decision-making.

2.3.1 Update on development activities

Since D3.2, the development of the wi,MOVE platform (previously known as WINGSPARK) has seen significant progress, with multiple functionalities moving from a work-in-progress state to completion. These updates reflect the continued effort in integrating, testing, and refining the platform. Key advancements since the last deliverable include the full implementation of a secure user access control system with Keycloak, the completion of REST APIs for road damage and inspection functionalities to support public infrastructure monitoring, and the full integration of sensors and robots/drones with ROS to enhance autonomous and remote sensing operations.

The following activities concern enhancements in the admin interface and the video streaming-teleoperation interface:

- Visual Data Representation at wi.MOVE Admin Dashboard:** The latest version of the admin dashboard is presented in Figure 10. The dashboard displays key metrics, such as the total number of the detected damages and the number of damages classified in different categories with capabilities for specific time period, severity, damage type and device selection filters. These statistics are accompanied

by an interactive map that marks the devices and detected damages' locations along with the activities list & notifications concerning damage type and severity. By selecting a detection from the activities list, the admin has access to camera snapshots from the exact moments of detection.

Figure 10. Latest version of the admin dashboard platform.

- AGV Teleoperation Interface:** The Jackal Clearpath teleoperation interface features a streamlined video client optimized for low-latency, high-compression streaming, enabling safe, stable, and highly responsive remote control of the robotic platform. Operators can remotely navigate the vehicle and control the onboard camera while monitoring the vehicle's status, critical system components, and precise location in real time. This ensures effective and reliable teleoperation under diverse operational conditions (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Latest version of the AGV teleoperation interface.

- Statistics overview and device insights:** Statistical data is available in diagram format, offering users alternative views to analyze metrics over a specified period. For each selected device, the dashboard generates granular statistical data in diagram format for the chosen time period, enabling users to monitor individual performance and trends (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Analytics and statistics insights.

- **Live camera view:** The dashboard allows users to view real-time damage detections, activities and real time alerts from any selected camera or device, providing immediate access to live footage (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Realtime damage detection streaming.

- **Device management:** The system includes a device management interface, where users can view, configure, and manage the properties of all devices connected to the system (Figure 14).

Figure 14. List of devices and components.

These advancements reflect the progress of the wi.MOVE platform, ensuring a more stable, fully integrated, and feature-rich system. The transition of these components from partial development to completion signifies a more mature stage of the platform, making it more reliable for deployment.

Table 2 outlines the development steps for the components of UC2.

Table 2. Status for UC2 software development activities.

Software development activity / feature	Implementation status
Main video analysis pipeline	Done (Q3-Q4 2023)
Containerized application services	Done (Q4 2023)
Streaming and Restreaming module	Done (Q1 2024)
Authentication and Authorization	Done (Q1 2024)
Data Ingestion and Processing	Done (Q4 2023)
Datastore setup	Done (Q4 2023)
Rest APIs device configuration management	Done (Q1 2024)
Device Management – Admin Dashboard	Done (Q4 2024)
Support for additional devices	Done (Q1 2025)
Integration of additional detection models	Done (Q2 2025)
Establish a deployment procedure	Done (Q4 2024)
Visualization dashboard	Done (Q2 2025)

2.3.2 Final application overview

The final application design of the wi.MOVE Platform has evolved significantly, integrating multiple functionalities that have transitioned from development to completion. The architecture schema was reported in the previous deliverable D3.2 [1]. The system now consists of the following enhanced components:

- **Data Input:** The system supports various hardware, including sensors, robots, drones, and cameras, which communicate with the data processing layer. Each device is registered with its details to facilitate seamless access to information across the system. With the latest enhancements, the integration of sensors, robots, and drones has been fully realized, including ROS integration, bringing advanced capabilities for autonomous and remote sensing operations.
- **Data Ingestion and Processing:** This module manages data streams from devices, processes incoming data, and executes essential functions for different use cases. It supports real-time data ingestion via MQTT [13] brokers or live video feeds. Enhancements now include improved handling of frames for cameras installed on remote devices, where each frame is transmitted to a remote server using for further processing. Depending on the use case, data is either stored directly or processed through the intelligence module for advanced analytics and detections.
- **Intelligence Module Integration:** The intelligence module is activated based on specific use cases, processing video feeds and executing detections. A significant milestone in this development is the completion of the road damage-specific module, which detects and classifies various types of road damages, assesses severity, and triggers automated notifications. These updates enable more accurate monitoring of public infrastructure. All communication with the main system is now streamlined through a secure remote REST API.
- **Streaming and Restreaming:** The restreaming module is responsible for managing the streaming of processed frames through a media server. The system now supports multiple streaming protocols, including RTSP, Hypertext Transfer Protocol Live Streaming (HTPLS), and Web Real-Time Communication (WebRTC), ensuring flexibility based on specific needs. The dashboard has been enhanced to

provide real-time damage detection insights, allowing users to monitor live activities and receive immediate alerts.

- **APIs and Datastore Modules:** The platform's data management has been significantly improved. Data from devices are stored in a time-series database (InfluxDB) for future analytics, while other system data are managed in PostgresDB [14]. The permissions management system has been fully implemented using Keycloak [15] roles and groups, providing a robust authentication and authorization framework. The RESTful API now supports comprehensive device management, dashboard interactions, and access control functionalities.
- **Visualization Dashboard:** The latest version of the admin dashboard introduces several enhancements for improved data visualization and device insights:
 - **Visual Data Representation:** The dashboard now displays key statistics, including the total number of detected damages, classifications by severity and type, and selection filters for specific time periods, devices, and damage categories. Interactive Map & Statistics Overview: Users can analyze installation locations of devices via an interactive map and view statistical data in graphical formats for better trend analysis.
 - **Live Camera View:** Real-time monitoring of damage detections and alerts is now available, ensuring immediate access to live footage from any connected device.
 - **Device Management:** The system includes a dedicated interface for configuring and managing all connected devices, further improving system operability.

2.4 UC3: Autonomous APRON

This use case focuses on deploying an Autonomous APRON solution at AIA using B5G communications to optimize airport operations, particularly for baggage and cargo handling with AGVs. An APRON DT provides a real-time virtual representation of the physical environment, allowing operators to remotely control AGVs in critical situations. AI analyses data from onboard sensors (cameras, LiDARs, GPS) for accurate predictions and alerts, improving monitoring and efficiency. A distributed system tracks AGVs, collaborative robots, and other resources, detecting network anomalies and preventing failures. B5G communication ensures low-latency, high-speed data exchange for optimal performance.

2.4.1 Update on development activities

The software development activities for this use case have progressed significantly, enhancing the visualization dashboard and DT capabilities (Figure 15). A 360-degree camera has been integrated, allowing real-time video streaming from AGVs to the wi.SUPPLY platform (previously known as WINGSChariot) via WebRTC. The communication framework has been reinforced with MQTT, enabling seamless interaction between wi.SUPPLY's OpenHAB-run system and the Unity engine-driven DT.

Figure 15. Visualization dashboard & Digital Twin application.

To provide comprehensive operational insights, real-time AGV parameters are now displayed, including activity state, battery level, sensor consumption, Central Processing Unit (CPU) usage, and available Random-Access Memory (RAM). Additionally, real-time data on AGV location, velocity, rotation, and heading have been incorporated, allowing operators to track movements with high precision.

Obstacle detection has been enhanced with filtered LiDAR information, displaying distances from various obstacles located at the front, back, left, and right of the AGV. To further aid navigation, a mini-map now presents the indicative path the AGV follows, improving situational awareness for operators. These updates contribute to a more responsive and intelligent system, ensuring efficient and safe airport operations.

2.4.2 Final application overview

The realization of the Autonomous APRON use case has been significantly refined, incorporating a sophisticated architecture that enhances efficiency, scalability, and real-time responsiveness. The core of the system leverages ROS2 [16] and Docker [17] containers, ensuring seamless and standardized communication among deployed robots, whether in a controlled lab environment or a real-world airport setting. The robotic layer is fully containerized using Docker, providing a modular, isolated software environment for each robot, which enhances system flexibility and maintainability.

To address high-computational demands and real-time data processing needs, an edge computing device has been integrated. This allows resource-intensive processing nodes to run locally, optimizing the robots' performance without over-reliance on cloud computing. Key advancements include the addition of a 360-degree camera, streaming real-time video from the AGV to the wi.SUPPLY [18] platform via WebRTC [19]. This enhances situational awareness and remote monitoring capabilities.

The wi.SUPPLY platform serves as the central orchestration tool, residing on the cloud and utilizing OpenHAB [20] and MQTT protocols to collect, process, and distribute data from the robotic fleet. A critical enhancement is the newly developed MQTT to ROS2 bridge, facilitating seamless communication between the MQTT-based cloud platform and the ROS2-powered robotic system. This integration ensures real-time data flow and efficient command execution, improving adaptability and responsiveness.

The wi.SUPPLY dashboard remains the primary monitoring and diagnostic hub. Built on MQTT and OpenHAB, it enables real-time visualization of AGV parameters such as activity state, battery level, CPU usage, sensor consumption, location, velocity, rotation, and heading. Additional enhancements include real-time LiDAR-based obstacle detection, displaying precise distances to obstacles in all directions. A mini-map visualization has been introduced, showing the AGV's indicative path and improving navigation insights.

A major innovation is the integration of Unity-powered digital twinning within the wi.SUPPLY Dashboard. This feature allows a real-time virtual representation of AGVs, mirroring their real-world activities with high accuracy. The DT not only provides an immersive monitoring experience but also supports predictive diagnostics and performance analytics.

This comprehensive architecture optimizes robotic fleet coordination and operational efficiency while ensuring scalability for future developments. The UC3 final application design is illustrated in the previous deliverable D3.2 [1].

2.5 UC4: Smart Traffic Management

UC4 is piloted in the Podu Roş Intersection in Iaşi, Romania, focusing on improving traffic flow and safety. Traffic is monitored to provide reports that can be used for intersection rules optimization in order to reduce congestion. Safety enhancements target Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) by identifying hazardous situations generating alerts to SOC. Data from cameras, communicated over a B5G network, are integrated into a traffic monitoring platform for actionable insights. The system collects traffic statistics and identifies potential hazards, crucial for managing increasing road users. Video analytics applications run on TUIASI servers, processing data for inference and visualization. This solution aims to improve urban mobility and safety while supporting sustainable transportation growth.

2.5.1 Update on development activities

The software application framework for UC4 is the same as for UC1 (Iaşi), with differences mostly with respect to configuration, object detection models used, and video streams. As such, the software development activities reported for UC1 (Iaşi) are valid for UC4 as well, and the milestones reported in Section 2.2.1 are also relevant for UC4.

One of the challenges impacting UC4 in particular is the alerting and reporting tool, since the objects detected in the UC4 video pipeline are tracked in successive frames, which allows fine-grained alerts for individual objects. The alerting system was designed as follows. Several regions are defined for each camera view, and alert conditions are defined for objects of certain types which are present in a certain region for a duration exceeding a predefined limit. The camera regions and the alerts are statically defined in configuration files. All alert conditions are evaluated in real-time on the stream-based processing server ksqldb, which processes the live message stream from the Kafka system, and every alert raised is stored in the database and displayed on the dashboard.

The open-source software *Label-Studio* is used for defining regions in camera views, as illustrated in Figure 16 showing two areas defined for a camera view from Podu Ros intersection: a pedestrian crossing (left) and a forbidden area for vehicles (right).

Figure 16. The interface for defining regions in the camera view.

The UC4 also implemented the Zero-touch orchestration solution provided by IMEC as introduced in the deliverable D2.3. In preliminary experiments at IMEC, the MPTCP configuration has been successfully replicated in ORO's infrastructure, as illustrated in Figure 17. In particular, two separate 5G links, one operating in NSA mode and the other in SA mode, are now combined using MPTCP. This dual-link approach allows simultaneous use of both connections, providing enhanced reliability and aggregate throughput. Early measurements showed a notable boost in peak data rates when both links are active, while a more detailed analysis of the camera feed streaming performance under normal and throttled conditions is depicted in Figure 18.

Figure 17. Overview of the MPTCP architecture deployed at ORO.

In the non-MPTCP configuration, the client is restricted to using only the SA link. To emulate degraded network conditions, throttling was applied by injecting background traffic, thereby congesting the SA link. In contrast,

under MPTCP, the client was able to seamlessly aggregate traffic across both the SA and NSA links, maintaining higher throughput and stable video quality even in the presence of link congestion. These results demonstrate that MPTCP consistently improves camera feed throughput compared to the non-MPTCP baseline, even under throttled conditions. While the frame rate remains stable across all scenarios, the MPTCP solution offers a 20% gain in normal operation and a substantial recovery in congested conditions (28.85 Mbps vs 18.52 Mbps).

<p style="text-align: center;">Non-MPTCP, Unthrottled</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Network Statistics</p> <p>Client Connected: Yes</p> <p>FPS: 24.97</p> <p>Bitrate: 27779.54 kbps</p> <p>Total Frames Received: 689</p> <p>Total Bytes Received: 90.16 MB</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">MPTCP, Unthrottled</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Network Statistics</p> <p>Client Connected: Yes</p> <p>FPS: 24.97</p> <p>Bitrate: 33499.80 kbps</p> <p>Total Frames Received: 655</p> <p>Total Bytes Received: 99.85 MB</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Non-MPTCP, Throttled</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Network Statistics</p> <p>Client Connected: Yes</p> <p>FPS: 24.92</p> <p>Bitrate: 18420.48 kbps</p> <p>Total Frames Received: 268</p> <p>Total Bytes Received: 28.33 MB</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">MPTCP, Throttled</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Network Statistics</p> <p>Client Connected: Yes</p> <p>FPS: 24.97</p> <p>Bitrate: 28885.64 kbps</p> <p>Total Frames Received: 2491</p> <p>Total Bytes Received: 385.16 MB</p>

Figure 18. Video feed streaming performance over 5G links under different configurations.

2.5.2 Final application overview

The application used for UC4 is built on the same platform as the application for UC1, described in section 2.2.2. The common descriptions are not repeated in this section, however, specific differences for UC4 are highlighted below.

The overall architecture of the application system is the same, comprising three main components:

- **The Video Processing component:** which handles the video processing and AI object detection model inference.
- **The Data Processing component:** handling the metadata processing and storage.
- **Observability and Reporting:** which provides the visual interface for the end user.

In the following sections, each component is further detailed.

Video Processing

The video processing component is essentially the same as the one for UC1, and the reader is referred to section 3.2.2.1. The AI object detection model used is YOLOv7, with the option of using other variants from the same family as well. The 6 video streams are incoming from the 6 cameras mounted in the Podu Ros intersection area.

Data Processing

The overall architecture is the same as for UC1, described in section 2.2.2. However, the type of data handled, and the processing stages for UC4 are different. For every detected object, in every video stream, a message is published on the Kafka broker with the detections metadata, including tracking identifier, bounding box, and region(s) in which the object is located, as illustrated in Figure 19. There is one such message stream for each camera in the system.

Figure 19. UC4 raw message for a detected object.

The message streams then undergo two processing stages, implemented as SQL-based live queries in the ksqlDB server:

- **Stage 1:** Keep track, for every detected object, of the entry and exit times in every region (e.g., first and last detection of an object in a region). This enables determining the amount of time spent by every object in any region defined for the camera view (e.g., object ID 32541, of type *car*, spent 1.46 seconds in the region which covers a pedestrian crossing).
- **Stage 2:** Evaluate a set of predefined alerts, and log an entry in an alerting if a condition is detected. Alerts are defined as tuples (*object type(s), region, maximum duration, alert ID, alert description*), and are triggered if an object of the specified type spends a duration exceeding the allowed amount in a certain region, based on the entry and exit times evaluated in the previous step.

The entry and exit times of every object in every region, for every camera, are stored in the PostgreSQL database, as well as the alerts detected, as illustrated in Figure 20 and Figure 21. Note that the detections themselves are not stored in the database, for efficiency reasons.

	CLASS_ID integer	FIRST_TIMESTAMP bigint	LAST_TIMESTAMP bigint	REGION [PK] text	START_TIMESTAMP [PK] bigint	TRACKER_ID [PK] bigint
1	2	1720203758496	1720203759497	All	1720203745391	0
2	2	1720203751860	1720203751940	All	1720203745391	2
3	2	1720203754985	1720203755985	All	1720203745391	3
4	2	1720203752263	1720203752766	All	1720203745391	4
5	2	1720203751958	1720203789160	All	1720203745391	7
6	2	1720203752384	1720203753225	All	1720203745391	10

Figure 20. Entry and exit timestamps stored in the database, for each object in region “All”.

	ALERT_ID text	CLASS_ID integer	FIRST_TIMESTAMP bigint	LAST_TIMESTAMP bigint	REGION [PK] text	START_TIMESTAMP [PK] bigint	TRACKER_ID [PK] bigint
1	000003	2	1720204146252	1720204217270	Intersectie	1720203745391	478
2	000003	2	1720204149454	1720204215258	Intersectie	1720203745391	482
3	000003	7	1720204269306	1720204337202	Intersectie	1720203745391	629
4	000003	2	1720204508821	1720204577495	Intersectie	1720203745391	872
5	000003	2	1720204509261	1720204578733	Intersectie	1720203745391	873
6	000003	2	1720204626033	1720204697021	Intersectie	1720203745391	998

Figure 21. Sample alerts raised for region “Intersectie” during a traffic jam, as stored in the database.

Observability and Reporting

The relevant data for the user is displayed via web dashboards, served by a Grafana server instance. There is a dashboard for every camera in the system. Access to the dashboards is granted on a per-user, per-dashboard basis. The dashboard for the camera #5 is illustrated in Figure 22 and contains:

- A (optional) low resolution output video stream, with detected objects (blurred) and regions marked. The video can be removed from the dashboard, for users which do not have the authorization to view the stream.
- A summary of current traffic (running counters of traffic participants, aggregated over a selectable time range)
- A live map depicting the traffic participants
- A detailed list and a summary of latest alerts. Ongoing alerts are marked red.

Figure 22. UC4 web dashboard for camera 5 in the Podu Ros intersection.

2.6 UC5: Control Room in Metaverse

UC5 aims to develop a web-based application improving the operational efficiency of safety & security forces, as well as to measure the ability of the public 5G network to support the Application. This is pursued through the creation of a collaborative Metaverse Control Room (MCR) accessible from any location with a security code. The scenario refers to an emergency occurring in the Park of Valentino, which is one of the most visited public parks in Turin, where several large events are held [21]. The whole App has been designed in close collaboration with the Turin safety and security forces to respect their intervention protocols. However, it can easily be adapted to different cases and requirements.

2.6.1 Update on development activities

The MCR had already been partly developed and fully described in the deliverable D3.2 [1]. This was possible thanks to the user friendliness of the Mozilla Hubs platform that enables simple and quick programming. Since then, only minor changes have been implemented as follows.

The final design of the application architecture is given in Figure 23. As compared to the previous schematic, beside streaming cameras, an interface has been added for the streaming video from a drone in the field as suggested by the second design thinking session.

Figure 23. Final UC5 application architecture.

Also, from the second design thinking session, that took place in Turin on 5th February 2024 with representatives from different safety and security agencies, the design of the Control Room has been modified as shown in Figure 24 and consists of the following spaces:

- **Private Rooms:** One for each security force, namely police, fire fighters and ambulances, that allows the agents of individual security forces to coordinate among themselves. These rooms have been programmed so that they are acoustically isolated from the rest of the control room.
- **Data Room:** A common area where the agents enter with their avatars and find screens with video streaming and sensors.
- **Audiovisual Room:** A common area where the agents can upload images and videos of the site where the emergency occurs.

Figure 24. Final design of the Metaverse Control Room.

Finally, the Avatars of the different safety and security forces have been designed in a realistic way in order to improve their recognition as shown in the examples of Figure 25.

Figure 25. Examples of Avatar Designs.

Once the last developments had been completed the App was ready for the trial. This was preceded by extensive testing and preparatory activities. Its different features have been presented in a short video on YouTube in Italian [22] aiming at providing the participants in the trial with an introduction on the experience.

2.6.2 Final application overview

The main features of the final application are briefly described below along with the different operational steps:

- **Step 1:** After selecting its avatar and associating it with his/her name, an agent (with a smartphone or tablet) or the coordinator of a security force (with a headset) enters the App in the data room where the agent may find the avatars of other agents present in the metaverse (see Figure 26).

Figure 26. Entrance in the App.

- **Step 2:** In the data room are displayed the info's from the sensors, the streaming videos from the cameras and the drone as well as a map of the site being monitored. The resolution of an image improves as the avatar gets closer to it (see Figure 27).

Figure 27. Data Room.

- **Step 3:** The avatars can freely move in the control room by using the controls of the headsets or by touching two circled areas on the touchscreens, one for a 360° rotation and the other for moving up down, left and right.
- **Step 4:** The agents located on the emergency site upload images and video on the walls of the Audiovisual Room, which is directly connected to the data room (see Figure 28).

Figure 28. Audiovisual Room.

- **Step 5:** In order to coordinate with colleagues from the same security force, users can move to their respective private room (see Figure 29).

Figure 29. Example of a Private Room.

The Apps run on the Mozilla Hubs is open source and does not require any subscription. It is also web based and can be accessed from anywhere from any web browser. It can also be easily adapted to cater for the specific needs of different security forces.

3 Trials and results

This section presents the trial activities and results conducted for the TrialsNet WP3 use cases during the period from April 2024 (release of D3.2) to September 2025. For each use case, during this period, both pre-trial activities and final field trials have been performed.

3.1 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Madrid)

UC1 is dedicated to testing the efficiency of 5G networks for operating security devices in public or private venues for crowd monitoring purposes. This use case gathers KPIs on the performance of Ericsson's CPEs in providing network connectivity to a full deployment of security appliances, including cameras, LiDAR and robotic platforms, powered by AI.

3.1.1 Trial 1.1 - Crowd monitoring through static infrastructure and artificial vision

Trial 1.1 was focused on the implementation of a crowd monitoring system for high attendance venues based on static infrastructure and powered by artificial intelligence. The trial involved two cameras (one fixed and one PTZ camera) as well as a LiDAR sensor placed at strategic positions to cover one of the main entrances at the Movistar Arena in Madrid, Spain. Each of the devices was powered by AI for detection of security events such as intrusions, abandoned bags or aggressive behavior (fighting). Moreover, T1.1 was performed in a joint trial along with T1.2 reported in Section 3.1.2 which added more complexity to the security deployment by including robotic platforms.

3.1.1.1 Pre-trial activities

By D3.2 [1], preliminary tests had been carried out in 5Tonic lab from October 23rd to October 26th, 2023. For the laboratory-scale tests, the configuration and setup of the laboratory's local network were carried out to test different elements in a standalone mode. Two Video Management Systems, Genetec and Milestone, were compared for basic functionalities, video connection, and reception of alerts. Genetec was selected as it proved to be more versatile when integrating external solutions, thanks to Genetec Mission Control and its IoT plug-in. For LiDAR management, Surveill and Gemini were tested with an Ouster OS0 LiDAR. Even though Surveill had many more functionalities, Gemini was selected for its ease of integration within the use cases.

Subsequently pre-trial activities focused on testing AI analytics, system integration, and 5G connectivity to ensure readiness for the field trials. The first step involved evaluating AI algorithms in a controlled laboratory environment, where different providers' solutions were tested for intrusion detection, abandoned objects, and suspicious behavior. KPIs such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were measured, with intrusion detection reaching values up to 1.00 for most scenarios, while abandoned object detection showed lower scores in some cases (as low as 0.40 for accuracy). These results highlighted the sensitivity of some algorithms to environmental changes and confirmed the need for precise definition of detection areas to reduce false positives.

Following this stage, the system was tested in Prosegur's Co-studio facility using the commercial 5G network. Over several days of testing, remote monitoring, teleoperation of robots, and AI-based alerting were assessed as a complete system. The setup confirmed stable operations and proper configuration of the equipment under conditions similar to those expected in the field.

Connectivity tests were then performed at 5Tonic using Ericsson's prototype CPEs, since the new deployed infrastructure required to modify the previous setup. After reconfigurations, a full integration test at Ericsson's facilities validated the final architecture. Individual devices achieved uplink and downlink throughput values between 50–100 Mbps, while the simulation with multiple devices showed stable performance with throughput up to 350 Mbps and application round-trip latency around 12 ms. Although latency for the LiDAR remained slightly above the 10 ms target, the tests confirmed the overall system capability to support simultaneous operation of all devices under the UC1 requirements.

The complete results and detailed measurements from these pre-trial activities are provided in Annex A.

3.1.1.2 Trial description

The initial trial description in terms of equipment, set-up and architecture was reported in D3.2 [1] while the final setup has been described in Section 2.1.2 of this document. Both T1.1 and T1.2, explained in Section 3.1.1 and Section 3.1.2 respectively, took place in a single joint trial, with both fixed infrastructure and robotic platforms deployed onsite for security vigilance and crowd monitoring. The trial took place at Movistar Arena venue in Madrid (see Figure 30), Spain, during a sporting event. All security equipment was strategically placed to cover the Goya access area.

Figure 30. Device set-up for UC1 Trial.

Fixed infrastructure and artificial vision devices used for the part corresponding to T1.1 include:

- **HIKVISION DS-2CD2686G2T-IZS** bullet camera, substituting the bullet camera used for the pre-trial tests, which was AXIS PE-1447-LE, due to a request from the venue owner.
- **HIKVISION DS-2DE3A400BW-DE**, PTZ camera, substituting the camera used for pre-trial tests, which was an AXIS Q6135-LE, also due to a request from the venue owner.
- **LiDAR Ouster OS1**.

The cameras and LiDAR were operated from a remote iSOC set up on the second floor of the trial site, where all input images and alerts were received. From this control room, a professional iSOC operator was able to take control of the PTZ camera to verify alerts, as well as to control the robots remotely. The main role of both cameras and LiDAR was to provide insight into the access area and detect potential alerts, which would then be verified by the operator remote controlling the PTZ camera or the robots. Hence, the equipment has been selected to fulfill the needs related to security vigilance in this particular area of the venue.

Throughout the trial, the AI algorithms were deployed for the detection of potential security events (abandoned objects, trespassers in restricted areas, violent or suspicious behavior) happening during the event, and the iSOC operator was expected to verify them using the robotic platforms from the control room.

Operational validation of the joint trial encompassed the following cases:

- **Case 1:** After receiving an alert from the AI on the security cameras, the guard will dispatch one of the robots to a location if it is outside the PTZ camera's field of view, and the robot's cameras will verify the footage. After confirmation, he or she issues a warning to the on-site security guard to follow the established security procedures.
- **Case 2:** An alert is sent to the iSOC by AI operating on edge (on the robots' payload) when it detects a dangerous situation. Similar to Case 1, the PTZ is used to confirm the warning, and robots are dispatched to gather more detailed information. A physical security guard will respond according to the circumstances.

- Case 3:** The robot automatically performs security rounds that are launched through the iSOC via robot management platform. The on-board AI device, which has an NVIDIA GPU card, processes the video stream from the robot cameras. The iSOC receives the alerts and can take over the robot to verify the event on camera.

3.1.1.3 Trial execution and results

The trial took place during a basketball game on March 16th, 2025, in Movistar Arena as planned. During the trial, all devices (cameras, LiDARs and robots) were deployed in a joint trial following the device set-up displayed in Figure 31. All devices were connected to the 5G set-up provided by Ericsson and remotely controlled via the mobile iSOC position placed in the upper floor of the Movistar Arena Goya entrance (see Figure 32 and Figure 33). Therefore, data was taken for both T1.1 and T1.2 together during the implementation.

Figure 31. Final hardware set-up configuration for the joint T1.1 and T1.2 trial.

Figure 32. View of the entrance during the Trial, taken from the second floor.

Figure 33. View of fixed and robot cameras from the mobile iSOC.

The following devices were used for the implementation of the trial:

- Two security cameras, one bullet camera and a PTZ camera, equipped with AI algorithms, positioned one on each side of the entrance hall (T1.1).
- One LiDAR, positioned in an incline so that laser beams point to the entrance, and also equipped with AI for alerts (T1.1).
- Four computers, which included AI servers, the computer integrated into the mobile iSOC and laptops. T1.1 and T1.2).
- One tablet which was used as a controller for one of the robots (T1.2).
- Three robots: Boston Dynamics' SPOT, Temi, and Robotnik's SummitXL; each of them equipped with a unique payload (T1.2).
- Two CPEs (T1.1 and T1.2).

The trial session had an approximate duration of three hours, starting at 17:00, when the doors of the facility were opened to the public, and finalizing near 20:30, when the match was over, and most attendees left the premises. During the basketball match, the venue was at full capacity, meaning an approximate number of 2000 of visitors accessed the Goya Street entrance and were indirect participants of the trial, while 5 security agents were involved directly in the implementation itself, managing the security technology deployment.

KPIs

Several KPIs were measured to evaluate network capacity such as Downlink (DL) throughput per user (KPI#01), Uplink (UL) throughput per user (KPI#02), Downlink aggregate Throughput (KPI#03), Uplink aggregate Throughput (KPI#04) and Coverage (KPI#07). Latency (Application round trip latency, KPI#08) and Service availability (KPI#17) were also measured. For the KPI measurements, the LiDAR data traffic (point cloud) was sent from CPE 2 to CPE 1.

The set-up parameters were identical to the pre-trial tests and are reported in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3. Trial setup description for Trial 1.1 and Trial 1.2.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: MovistarArena
Radio access technology	5G NR Standalone
Network type	Private Network

Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	20W
Frequency band	n258
Bandwidth per component carrier	8x100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
MIMO	2x2
Duplex mode	Time Division Duplexing (TDD)

Table 4. Trial summary for Trial 1.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Trial setup ID	MovistarArena
Facility/Site	Movistar Arena
Objective	Measure network performance during the trial, all devices connected. Including: measurements for CPE1 (01), CPE2 (02), mean aggregate for both CPEs (03), CPE1 to App Server latency (04); CPE2 to App Server latency (05), CPE1 to CPE2 latency (06) and CPE2 to CPE1 latency (07)
Description	Network performance data taken during the trial via ERC's Grafana Tool.
Executed by	PROSE and ERC
Components involved	RB-SummitXL (Kiiro), Boston Dynamics SPOT (Yellow), Temi (Amarelo), Camera HIKVISION DS-2DE3A400BW-DE, Camera HIKVISION DS-2CD2686G2T-IZS, LiDAR: Ouster OS1, Router Ericsson 6675, Baseband Ericsson 6648, AIR 5322, LPG 1.3, SDX 75 Based Prototype CPE
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#02 (Uplink throughput per user) KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08 (Application round trip latency) KPI#07 (Coverage) KPI#17 (Service availability)
Measurement tools	Grafana showing 5G Network probes

In Table 5, the results for relevant KPIs have been summarised along with their validation. Results are shown in different case IDs given that throughput and latency were measured separately for each of the CPEs (per user) as well as aggregate.

Table 5. Measured KPIs results for Trial 1.1.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_MovistarArena_01	KPI#01: 200 Mbps KPI#02: 100 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#01: 251,30 Mbps KPI#02: 7,021 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied, understanding CPE1 was dedicated to managing most of the DL and not the UL
1.1_MovistarArena_02	KPI#01: 200 Mbps KPI#02: 100 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#01: 1,836 Mbps KPI#02: 219,947 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied, understanding CPE2 was dedicated to managing most of the UL and not the DL
1.1_MovistarArena_03	KPI#03: 200 Mbps KPI#04: 100 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#03: 148 Mbps KPI#04: 153 Mbps KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	All complied except KPI#03. However, functioning of devices was adequate
1.1_MovistarArena_04	KPI#08: 12 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#08: 6,088 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied
1.1_MovistarArena_05	KPI#08: 12 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#08: 5,318 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied
1.1_MovistarArena_06	KPI#08: 12 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 99%	KPI#08: 10,973 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied
1.1_MovistarArena_07	KPI#08: 12 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	KPI#08: 11,412 ms KPI#07: 0,0125 KPI#17: 100%	Complied

The trial results demonstrate the successful implementation of the use case. Service availability throughout the event was 100%, ensuring coverage of the stadium facility at all times with no issues, and the throughput maintained was sufficient for the correct operation of all devices even if the aggregate downlink throughput resulted lower than initially projected. In D3.1 [23], an application-level latency requirement of 100ms was established for UC1 – Madrid, which was considered sufficient for the security use case, and also accounted for AI server processing times and others. However, the network roundtrip latency (KPI#08) requirement set during the measurements has been determined based on the requirements of the devices used, such as 12ms for all devices and 10ms \pm 2ms error margin for the LiDAR, resulting in 12ms was selected as the maximum latency requirement.

To expand on the CPEs performance, Table 6 showcases the average, median and percentile values for each of the CPEs UL and DL throughput. In this trial. CPE 1 was managing most of the DL throughput while CPE2 was managing the UL throughput.

Table 6. Summary for CPE 1 and CPE 2 throughput measurements.

CPE	Avg. DL Throughput Mbps	Avg. UL Throughput Mbps	Median DL Throughput Mbps	Median UL Throughput Mbps	Percentile (10) DL Throughput Mbps	Percentile (10) UL Throughput Mbps	Percentile (90) DL Throughput Mbps	Percentile (90) UL Throughput Mbps
CPE2	1,836	219,947	1,349	320,150	1,051	26,577	2,065	330,277
CPE1	251,303	7,021	386,325	0,000	14,205	0,000	396,801	0,000

As can be observed in Figure 34 and Figure 35, the LiDAR's data had an important effect in the level of throughput.

Figure 34. Downlink Aggregate Throughput (KPI#03) timeline.

Figure 35. Uplink Aggregate Throughput (KPI#04) timeline.

Despite the large amounts of data transmitted from the LiDAR, network performance in terms of reliability, availability and latency were unaffected throughout the duration of the trial. Teleoperation of the robotic platforms from the remote iSOC was carried out successfully with a minimum delay, allowing the operator to respond to people traffic in real time while teleoperating a robot and moving it around the entrance hall. In summary, the trial was performed with success, and the Rel-17 5G network used satisfied the requirements rendering very positive results.

In regard to the AI performance, alerts were correctly received in the iSOC, but it was not possible to gather data to verify false positives and false negatives. It is extremely difficult to validate this in a real environment, moreover, ethical requirements of the project implied restrictions to gather the necessary information to calculate and report Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 score. Due to the ethical requirements of the project, no recordings were made from the trial's security cameras (included those mounted on the robots). Hence, operatives had no access to footage to verify false positive and false negative alerts for the duration of the trial. However, KPIs gathered during lab validation can be observed in Annex A.

KVIs

Several KVIs were also measured via survey to security agents involved in the trial consisting of 5 people.

The initially selected KVIs for the joint T1.1 and T1.2 trial implementation were Trust/Trustworthiness, Resilience and Security (see Table 18 of D3.1 [23]). To this initial selection, Societal Sustainability was also added as a KVI to be finally measured. In this context, trustworthiness is understood as the trustworthiness of the technological solution to work as intended and operate in a transparent way that facilitates the work of security guards. Resilience is understood as the capacity of the system to not experience significant and frequent interruptions, to bounce back when an error occurs, and to be reliable for the security guard to perform the job in a more efficient way. Security is understood in terms of the cybersecurity of the solution, given it is treating sensitive data, and also understanding that this solution does not cause any potential harm to involved parties. Finally, safety is understood as the solution's capacity to reduce potential risks and dangers for people involved in the security job.

In order to acquire the necessary information to evaluate the selected KVIs, an online survey was prepared including a set of questions for each of the KVIs, with responses set on a LIKERT scale. The questions that composed the survey are reported in in Annex E.

The questionnaire was designed to gather the perceptions of security professionals about the solution developed at this stage. The questions were translated into Spanish and shared via Microsoft Forms post-implementation of the use case, to be filled by the next day. It was responded by the 5 people involved in the implementation of the security use case, all of them working in security and security technology.

Figure 36. Mean KVI scores for UC1.

As observed in Figure 36, results from the questionnaire are overall positive, with mean KVI scores higher than 3 points out of 5 for all categories. In general, the system is seen as trustworthy to provide useful functionalities and accurate information for the improved performance of venue security. Trust is lower in regard to the AI algorithms accuracy, although still above the 3-point threshold, with a mean value of 3,25 out of 5 points for question 2. The latter score matches the KPIs recorded for AI computing, which showcases some shortcomings in the detection of abandoned objects when environmental changes occur in the surveilled site. In terms of security, however, the system is regarded as highly secure, with all mean values equal or higher than 4 points out of 5 for each of the security questions. With regards to safety, it is considered that the solution has potential to avoid possible dangerous situations for onsite security guards (mean score of 4,75 points out of 5 for question 2). The opinions on its capacity to solve potential security situations remotely are more divided, though they remain above the positive threshold of 3 points (mean score of 3,25 points out of 5 for question 1). This can be linked to the potential complexity of security events, particularly in crowded areas. Resilience means value lays at 3,6 out of 5, evidencing, on the one hand, respondent's concerns about the perceived capacity for the solution to bounce back and/or not suffer interruptions. Although no major interruptions happened for the duration of the trial, there were some issues at the beginning with connection of devices to the iSOC. On the other hand, the B5G connection's capacity to provide faster identification and faster reaction to security events has been regarded quite positively in terms of resilience. Figure 37 elaborates on the mean scores per question per KVI.

Figure 37. Mean scores per question per KVI.

During an informal interview with the security agents who managed the mobile iSOC for the duration of the trial, they demonstrated interest in the technology, particularly the robots, stating that although some improvements are yet necessary for a wide implementation, these can be useful tools for security vigilance.

In conclusion, KVI values are overall positive for the Use Case, although some potential improvements to the solution have been identified in the area of resilience, as well as trust, the latter particularly for the AI implementations.

3.1.2 Trial 1.2 - Crowd monitoring through programmed or tele-controlled robots with AI

Trial 1.2 was focused on the implementation of a crowd monitoring system for high attendance venues by deploying three platforms which can be tele-controlled or perform programmed routes. The trial makes use of three robotic platforms: two with a dedicated security role and one with assistance and security functions. The robots were programmed to perform routes around the perimeter, with the capacity to be tele-controlled in real time by a security guard on the iSOC position. T1.2 was performed in a joint trial with T1.1, which made use of static infrastructure for the purpose of crowd control.

3.1.2.1 Pre-trial activities

The pre-trial activities performed for Trial 1.2 are described in the following.

In the first lab tests performed for UC1 (see deliverable D3.2 [1]), the uplink and downlink throughput to the Kiiro robot was evaluated under different operational conditions. These include the robot operating in static mode and in movement, streaming video at different quality configurations, onboard LiDAR activation, and teleoperation from Nimbus. The results indicated that the 5G network can support the operation of the Kiiro robot under the required network quality parameters. However, high-quality stream transmission was not adequate, and the network reached a state of saturation when all devices were connected. Therefore, it was concluded that a B5G network with increased bandwidth and reduced latency would be required. Hence, for the following pre-trial tests, a CPE supporting 5G millimetric band spectrum was used.

Although initial plans were to add an additional robot and LiDAR, after optimizing the 5G network, the new trial plan granted further measurements were performed including the simultaneous operation of three robots, along with the LiDAR and cameras. Pre-trial activities for UC1 Trial 1.2 focused on validating the operation of robotic platforms, cameras, LiDAR, and AI algorithms. Initial tests were conducted in laboratory conditions to

benchmark AI performance, followed by integration tests at Prosegur's lab using a public 5G network and at 5Tonic with private B5G connectivity. The setup included CPE prototypes and final network configurations, ensuring that all devices—three robots, cameras, and LiDAR—could be connected and operated within the defined KPIs.

Connectivity and performance validation were carried out with three robotic platforms (SPOT, Kiiro, Temi), each tested separately for uplink, downlink, and latency. Results showed stable connectivity, with throughput values ranging between 4–9 Mbps against a 10 Mbps target and latency consistently at 12 ms. While throughput was lower than expected, the achieved latency ensured acceptable operation of the robots, supporting simultaneous integration with the fixed devices. Configuration tests with all devices confirmed the feasibility of full UC1 operation under the defined KPIs. The complete results, including detailed measurements and validation tables, are presented in Appendix A– Pre-trial activities.

3.1.2.2 Trial description

Trial description in terms of equipment, set-up and architecture can be found in detail in Section 2.1.2 of this document. As stated in Section 00, Trial 1.1 and Trial 1.2 occurred as a joint trial.

Robotic platforms used in the trial corresponding to T1.2 included the following:

- **SummitXL (Kiiro):** wheeled robot developed by Robotnik and equipped with a LiDAR, stereoscopic cameras and GPS.
- **SPOT (Yellow):** quadruped robot developed by Boston Dynamics, equipped with AI algorithms for detection of unusual behavior.
- **Temi (Amarelo):** personal AI assistant able to memorize pre-set locations and respond to pre-set commands.

All robotic platforms were connected to CPE1, which sent its data to CPE2 and the remote iSOC server in the control room (see Figure 31. Final hardware set-up configuration for the joint T1.1 and T1.2 trial.. The 5Tonic RAN setup and equipment, along with the 5G antenna set up by Ericsson at the venue, guaranteed the 5G high-band connection. Yellow and Kiiro were positioned to perform surveillance rounds on the ground floor of the location, both teleoperated and pre-set. Amarelo was static near the food kiosks at the entrance, ready to offer assistance to attendees. Amarelo was programmed to be able to guide attendants to key spaces within the area, such as bathrooms and the VIP zone. Images by the robot's mounted cameras were received in the control room, as well as related AI alerts. In case of a security event alert, the operator had the capacity to verify it by taking control of a robot via the iSOC.

3.1.2.3 Trial execution and results

The trial took place during a basketball game on March 16th, 2025. During the trial, all devices (cameras, LiDARs and robots) were deployed in a joint trial following the device set-up displayed in Figure 31. Cameras, LiDAR and robots were all connected to the 5G set-up provided by ERC and remotely controlled via the mobile iSOC position placed in the upper floor of the Movistar Arena Goya entrance. Therefore, data was taken for both T1.1 and T1.2 together during the implementation of the trial. Devices used and trial duration information are detailed in 3.1.1.3.

KPIs

KPIs measures match those of Trial T1.1 as seen in 3.1.1.3 (Table 5 and Table 6). As reported in the aforementioned section, the robots were monitored from the iSOC by a security guard. The robots were operated via controller and teleoperated via the iSOC. All video streaming and alerts were received successfully, although AI computing KPIs could not be collected due to constraints related to the ethics of the trial, which means no data could be reported on the accuracy, precision and recall of the algorithms.

KVIs

Several KVIs were also measured via survey provided to the 5 security agents involved in the trial. These results are reported in section 3.1.1.3. Furthermore, during the implementation of the trial, an observational study was implemented by Telefonica were observed spectators of the basketball game interacted with the technological solutions developed by Prosegur. Hence, an ethnography activity was conducted to evaluate the impact and subjective perception of the robots and complemented with an interview to the security agents who was facing the experience of controlling the robots for the first time. The observation shed light on the fact that spectators

did not understand the functional purpose of the robots as security devices and were curious and a little intimidated by robot Yellow due to its animal characteristics, while robot Kiiri's appearance did not generate that kind of reaction. This finding implies that there is a need to educate the public on these types of technologies, so that they can understand their function. It was also observed that police officers present were interested in the robots as a complement to their security activities.

3.2 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Iasi)

This section presents the results for Trial 1.3 and Trial 1.4 of UC1 in Iasi. For Trial 1.4, the devices were installed since mid-2023 and the activity consisted in performing trials with 5G NSA and SA network deployments.

3.2.1 Trial 1.3 - Crowd monitoring using Wi-Fi information

Trial 1.3 targeted crowd management at outdoor public gatherings by analyzing Wi-Fi data from Access Points (APs) positioned along Stefan cel Mare Boulevard and Piata Palat Square to monitor attendance, movement patterns, and crowd density and flow characteristics. The Wi-Fi performance measurements were conducted using a 5G NSA backhaul configured on a public 5G NSA network with cell power set at 50 dBm (~120 W), operating in band n78 with 100 MHz bandwidth per component carrier and 30 kHz sub-carrier spacing. The setup employed a 64T64R massive MIMO configuration in TDD duplex mode, ensuring high spectral efficiency and realistic capacity conditions for backhaul evaluation.

3.2.1.1 Pre-trial activities

As part of the preparations for the final trial held in May 2025, several activities were carried out. These included the installation of additional Wi-Fi AP in Stefan cel Mare boulevard in November 2024, the migration of AP backhauled from fiber connections to a 5G NSA-based solution in April 2025, and continuous KPI measurements. The earlier fiber backhaul phase provided stable performance, but flexibility was limited when adapting to changing event requirements. The 5G NSA backhaul solution introduced higher adaptability, faster deployment, and easier relocation of APs, which proved advantageous for managing large crowds during temporary events. KPI monitoring was performed not only under normal conditions but also during large-scale gatherings such as the yearly "Sf. Parascheva" events in October 2024 and the December 2024 Christmas holiday periods, to validate performance under peak traffic load. These datasets were analyzed using Wi-Fi analytics metrics which were integrated with camera-based analysis to support the objective of improving safety and situational awareness in high-density public areas (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Wi-Fi Coverage Map – Stefan cel Mare Bd., Palace Square, Iasi.

During the pre-trial phase, main activities were focused on analysis of how open spectrum technologies, specifically Wi-Fi, can be applied to generate crowd-related data and insights. Wi-Fi analytics were used to support the objective of improving safety and situational awareness in high-density public areas. At the same time, KPIs of the Wi-Fi service were monitored to confirm that network quality was maintained at levels required for analytics tools to operate effectively. Although the analytics system operates continuously, selected timeframes

were defined for focused evaluation. Moving from the Wi-Fi coverage map, the Wi-Fi Analytics (see Figure 39) heatmap provides a visualization of crowd density based on beacon signal detection and triangulation from access points.

Figure 39. Wi-Fi Presence Analytics Heatmap.

3.2.1.2 Trial description

Building on the insights gained from the 2023 and 2024 Sf. Parascheva pilgrimages, where Wi-Fi analytics revealed significant spikes in visitor numbers (40% increase in traffic and over 80% more unique users), Trial 1.3 explored during May 2025 new wave of measurements the potential of Wi-Fi-based crowd monitoring, enhanced by 5G backhaul connectivity.

The trial started by transitioning AP of the Wi-Fi hotspot on Ștefan cel Mare Boulevard from fiber-based to 5G backhaul connectivity. This shift enabled the possibility to assess network performance, latency, and stability in real-world conditions, providing relevant data on the viability of 5G-enabled Wi-Fi analytics.

To gain deeper insight into crowd dynamics, the trial also refined the Wi-Fi presence analytics methodology. Instead of treating the entire Wi-Fi hotspot as a single analytics zone, the system divided it into multiple zones, allowing to track how crowds move between different areas. This enhanced capability provided valuable data for urban planning, public safety, and smart city development.

Ultimately, Trial 1.3 validated the feasibility of using 5G-enabled Wi-Fi networks as real-time crowd monitoring tools, offering municipalities and event organizers an advanced, scalable solution for managing large gatherings more effectively.

3.2.1.3 Trial execution and results

The purpose of the Trial 1.3 held in May 2025 was to verify that Wi-Fi parameters supported the generation of reliable Wi-Fi analytics metrics using 5G as backhaul solution. As shown in Figure 38, 4 APs have been selected out of which one Access Point, No. 2, had the backhaul migrated to 5G solution.

In this specific location served by the four APs, parameters relevant for the operation of the Wi-Fi analytics service were analyzed. The analysis began with network signal information, where the AP identifier Basic Service Set Identifier (BSSID) was used for positioning confirmation, the distance between the test device and the Access Point was measured, and the received signal strength of the wireless network was recorded. After evaluating these wireless parameters, networking tests were performed to assess the QoS at the transport layer. Metrics considered included upload and download speeds, the ratio between Physical layer (PHY) and real throughput, as well as latency and jitter.

Measurements were performed with three terminals: a Xiaomi Mi9T, a Samsung S10 5G running Android, and an iPhone 12 running iOS. The values obtained were important to determine how much bandwidth was consumed by active users. Any degradation of these parameters indicated congestion at the transport layer and potential deterioration of the Wi-Fi Analytics data feed.

The trial setup implemented for this evaluation is detailed in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7. Trial setup description for Trial 1.3.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field02
Radio access technology	Wi-Fi
Network type	Experimental
Wi-Fi Standard	Wi-Fi 5 (802.11 ac wave 2)
Cell Power (Maximum Conducted Transmit Power)	Cisco 1562: 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz: 27 dBm Cisco 1572: 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz: 30 dBm
Frequency band	2.4 GHz & 5GHz
Bandwidth per component carrier	312.5 kHz
Sub-carrier spacing	OFDM
MIMO	4x4 MIMO, 3 Spatial Streams
Duplex mode	Half-Duplex
Device type	Wi-Fi Access Point
Device number	Cisco AIR-AP1562E-E-K9, Cisco AIR-AP1572EAC-B-K9
Device speed	Up to 450 Mbps on 2.4 GHz, 1300 Mbps on 5 GHz
Background traffic	Medium (Public Wireless Frequencies)

Table 8. Trial summary for Trial 1.3.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	1.3
Trial setup ID	Field02
Facility/Site	Iasi
Objective	Demonstration of the Wi-Fi analytics application capabilities and performance measurements for the supporting 5G network backhaul.
Description	The application focuses on several distinct scenarios of practical interest: a) estimation of crowd density in the surveyed area; b) total count of people passing through a specific access facility; c) crowd density dynamics and its real-time evolution.
Executed by	TUIASI & ORO
Components involved	Wi-Fi network, Access Points, Switches and Routers, edge-compute infrastructure, Wi-Fi analytics application
Targeted KPIs	Downlink throughput, Uplink throughput, E2E latency
Measurement tools	Wi-Fi Network Signal, nPerf, SpeedTest,

KPIs

The summary of the measurements is presented in Table 9. In this set of measurements, the trial case 4.1_Field02_02 considered a Wi-Fi Access Point connected to a 5G backhaul (see Table 10 for 5G configuration), while the other three measurements were based on fiber backhaul.

Table 9. Measured KPIs for Trial 1.3.

Measurement ID	Trial requirement	Measurement result	Validation
4.1_Field02_01	Wi-Fi Signal: > -75 dBm PHY: 90 Mbps (> 49.5 Mbps) Downlink: > 55% of PHY Uplink: > 55% of PHY Latency: < 40 ms Jitter: < 30 ms	Wi-Fi Signal: -74 dBm Downlink: 78.53 Mbps Uplink: 42.41 Mbps Latency: 27 ms Jitter: 35 ms	All KPIs met, jitter slightly above target due to Wi-Fi signal level.
4.1_Field02_02	Wi-Fi Signal: > -65 dBm PHY: 135 Mbps Downlink: > 55% of PHY Uplink: > 55% of PHY Latency: < 40 ms Jitter: < 30 ms	Wi-Fi Signal: -68 dbm Downlink: 120.1 Mbps Uplink: 101.41 Mbps Latency: 30 ms Jitter: 9 ms	Stable performance, throughput and jitter within targets.
4.1_Field02_03	Wi-Fi Signal: > -65 dBm PHY: 150 Mbps Downlink: > 55% of PHY Uplink: > 55% of PHY Latency: < 40 ms Jitter: < 30 ms	Wi-Fi Signal: -64 dBm Downlink: 67.82 Mbps Uplink: 75.41 Mbps Latency: 35 ms Jitter: 11 ms	Good results, downlink slightly below potential
4.1_Field02_04	Wi-Fi Signal: > -75 dBm PHY: 200 Mbps Downlink: > 55% of PHY Uplink: > 55% of PHY Latency: < 40 ms Jitter: < 30 ms	Wi-Fi Signal: -46 dBm Downlink: 175.74 Mbps Uplink: 96.92 Mbps Latency: 32 ms Jitter: 11 ms	Strong signal, very high throughput, all within thresholds

The overall results show that the Wi-Fi Access Point connected to the 5G backhaul achieved good and comparable performance when set against the fiber-based backhaul cases. Throughput, latency, and jitter remained within acceptable ranges, with values demonstrating stability and reliability. These findings confirm that 5G backhaul can provide a robust alternative to fiber, especially in scenarios where flexibility and rapid deployment are required, without significant degradation in service quality. From an engineering perspective, the 5G backhaul approach also introduces scalability potential, as it can support future Wi-Fi Access Point densification and temporary deployments in high-demand areas without the need for costly fiber extensions.

KVIs

The KVIs measurements have been provided together with Trial 1.4 and Trial 4.1, which results are presented in section 3.2.2.3.

3.2.2 Trial 1.4 - Crowd monitoring using cameras

Trial 1.4 focused on crowd monitoring using surveillance cameras connected over 5G. The target venues for this trial were the pedestrian area of the Stefan cel Mare Boulevard from Iasi, as well as the place in front of the Palace of Culture. The trial focused on two distinct scenarios of practical interest such as a) estimation of crowd density in the surveyed area and b) detecting objects entering within a restricted access area. Pre-trained AI/ML models were integrated into the Nvidia DeepStream framework running on the video analytics server. Video analytics are computed and displayed in terms of total number of people in a user-defined area of interest, and heatmaps estimating people density in the same area.

3.2.2.1 Pre-trial activities

The preparatory work for this trial was implemented in two main phases, with the setup designed specifically for the use case requirements. During the first phase (October 2023 – December 2024), the cameras were linked

via ORO's 5G NSA infrastructure to the TUIASI servers, where the analytics chain was configured using Nvidia DeepStream to detect pedestrians and generate alerts. The functionality was validated in the December 2024 which results are reported in Annex B. The second phase (January – May 2025) involved migrating the system to a 5G SA configuration, complemented by an external antenna to extend the coverage. This upgrade supported the optimized execution of the May 2025 trial described in the following section.

3.2.2.2 Trial description

As the 5G network upgrades to a SA configuration, Trial 1.4 deploys AI-powered video analytics to enhance real-time crowd monitoring and security in urban spaces. The trial follows two key security scenarios:

- **People counting in pedestrian areas:** Using pretrained neural networks for people detection, the system detect and count pedestrians in high-traffic areas like Ștefan cel Mare Boulevard, providing real-time data visualization with near-instantaneous updates.
- **Detection of unauthorized access in restricted areas:** AI-powered monitoring detects vehicles in pedestrian zones or people crossing outside designated areas, triggering automatic alerts for enhanced security.

3.2.2.3 Trial execution and results

Following 5G NSA trial performed in December 2024 which results are reported in Annex B, second trial was conducted in May 2025 in Iasi to demonstrate the capabilities of a 5G SA network in supporting intelligent video analytics applications for public safety. The objective of this trial was to validate how 5G-SA technologies enable scalable and low-latency video processing scenarios for crowd monitoring, movement analysis, and security applications, improving on the results obtained under the NSA configuration. Specific scenarios implemented included people counting, movement direction estimation, crowd density evaluation, and intrusion detection in restricted areas. The measurements focused on real-time video traffic processed at the edge infrastructure using high-resolution video streams.

The trials were performed based on the setup detailed in Table 10 while the summary is presented in Table 11.

Table 10. Trial setup description for Trial 1.4.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field03
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	50 dBm (~120 W)
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	64TX 64RX
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 11. Trial summary for Trial 1.4.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	1.4
Trial setup ID	Field03
Facility/Site	Iasi
Objective	Demonstration of the video analytics application capabilities and performance measurements for the SA network setup

Description	The application focuses on several distinct scenarios of practical interest: a) estimation of crowd density in the surveyed area; b) total count of people passing through a specific access facility; c) detecting objects entering within a restricted access area.
Executed by	TUIASI and ORO
Components involved	5G SA network, cameras and 5G routers, edge-compute infrastructure, video analytics application
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#05 (Downlink throughput per device) KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#09 (Application one-way latency) KPI#16 (Communication Availability) KPI#17 (Service availability)
Measurement tools	iPerf3, nPerf, Speed Test, ping, Netdata, Jaeger

KPIs

The KPIs measurements were performed in May 2025 to assess the solution's End to End (E2E) performance, including both the network side and the application side. The average results obtained from these measurements are showcased in Table 12.

Table 12. Measured KPIs for Trial 1.4.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.4_Field03_01	KPI#05: 500 Mbps KPI#06: 50 Mbps KPI#09: 50 ms KPI#07: 4 km ² KPI#16: 99.9 % KPI#17: 99.9 %	KPI#05: 512 Mbps KPI#06: 58.6 Mbps KPI#09: 25 ms KPI#07: 4 km ² KPI#16: 99.9 % KPI#17: 99.9 %	All KPIs were successfully met, confirming the system's robust performance, excellent coverage, and high reliability even during a high-traffic public event

Application-level measurements were performed by capturing and analyzing the video traffic streamed from one or more cameras devices up to the 5G Lab Edge Compute infrastructure. The cameras were mounted on three different poles. Measurement screenshots from the 5G smartphone are presented in Figure 40.

Figure 40. 5G smartphone measurements.

For Trial 1.4, three distinct configurations were designed to evaluate the capabilities of the P2PNet model under varying conditions and resource constraints. Each measurement incrementally increased complexity, providing valuable insights into the P2PNet model's performance, scalability, and resource optimization. In particular:

- **Single Camera on Pole 4 (1.4_Field03_02.1):** In the first configuration, the focus was on evaluating the performance of the system with minimal input. A single camera, identified as pole4cam4, located on Ștefan cel Mare street, was utilized. The configuration involved the crowd detection model, with both input and output video streams set to the highest available resolution: 2592x1944 pixels at 25 Frames per Second (FPS), using H.265 encoding. This setup provided a demanding baseline scenario for assessing the model's efficiency in processing high-resolution video data from a single source under realistic urban conditions.
- **All 4 cameras on Pole 4 (1.4_Field03_02.2):** In the second configuration, the setup was scaled to include all four surveillance cameras installed on pole #4, located along Ștefan cel Mare street. Each device streamed video at maximum resolution—2592x1944 pixels—running at 25 FPS and encoded using H.265. Given the high data volume and system resource constraints, input streams were selectively processed using a 0.20 sampling ratio, meaning only one in every five frames was analysed by the GPU (i.e., five frames every second). This measurement served to evaluate how effectively the system could manage and analyse concurrent, high-resolution video streams in real-time, despite hardware limitations.
- **13 cameras on Ștefan cel Mare street (1.4_Field03_02.3):** In the final configuration, the evaluation was extended to encompass a larger-scale deployment, involving a total of 13 surveillance cameras mounted along Ștefan cel Mare street—specifically across poles #2, #3, and #4. Twelve of these cameras operated at maximum resolution (2592x1944 pixels) and 25 frames per second, while one camera streamed at 1920x1080@25FPS. All feeds were compressed using the H.265 codec to ensure efficient transmission to the edge processing server.

Given the considerable data throughput from this multi-camera setup, aggressive down sampling was applied to the input streams—processing was limited to just 5%-10% of the incoming frames. To conserve processing resources and avoid video rendering overhead, output video generation was fully deactivated. The system continued to perform object detection and analytics in the background, but no visual feedback was generated for real-time monitoring. This scenario was designed to validate the system's ability to scale effectively and remain operational under high-load, bandwidth-intensive conditions with distributed, high-definition video sources.

Note that the throughput value depends on various factors, including the actual movement content in the view. The results are shown in Table 13 below.

Table 13. Application-level measured KPIs for Trial 1.4.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Description	Validation
1.4_Field03_02.1	KPI#01: 5 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 13.6 Mbps KPI#08: 148 ms KPI#09: 10 ms	A single camera running (pole4 cam1, resolution 2592x1944@25FPS, H265)	Not very busy pedestrian street impacting the volume of image data and KPI#01 measurements results.
1.4_Field03_02.2	KPI#01: 49.5 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 49.9 Mbps KPI#08: 222 ms KPI#09: 10 ms	All 4 cameras at pole 4, resolution 2592x1944@25FPS, H265	Average activity in all 4 camera views. Still not enough image details with impact on lower KPI#01

				measurements results.
1.4_Field03_02.3	KPI#01: 95.15 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 149 Mbps KPI#08: 248 ms KPI#09: 10 ms	13 cameras on Stefan cel Mare street Highest resolution settings: 12 cameras: 2592x1944@25FPS, H265 1 camera: 1920x1080@25FPS, H265	All cameras on the three poles are streaming simultaneously. Still not enough image details with impact on lower KPI#01 measurements results.

The KPI measurements demonstrate that the system consistently met throughput and latency requirements, even under increased load. With a single camera, the achieved throughput was 13.6 Mbps compared to the 5 Mbps target, while latency remained well below thresholds (148 ms vs. 500 ms, and 10 ms vs. 50 ms). Scaling up to four cameras, throughput reached 49.9 Mbps against a 49.5 Mbps requirement, showing stable performance with moderate activity levels. In both cases, the system achieved over 2–3× the required bandwidth and maintained latency margins that confirm the robustness of the processing pipeline under typical street conditions.

When extended to 13 high-resolution cameras streaming simultaneously, the system achieved 149 Mbps, well above the 95 Mbps requirement. Despite the heavier load and higher image detail demands, latency values remained stable at 248 ms and 10 ms, still significantly below the KPI thresholds. These results confirm that the deployed infrastructure can support large-scale, high-resolution video analytics in real urban scenarios.

KVIs

The evaluation of UC1 in Iași incorporates a detailed assessment of KVIs, focusing on trust, resilience, security, societal sustainability, and operational efficiency. These indicators were chosen to reflect both technical performance and the human-centric impact of the 5G-enabled digital systems deployed in public safety contexts.

The KVIs were assessed through a structured questionnaire completed by 19 participants representing different stakeholders. The same questionnaire, containing 18 questions, was also used for Trials 1.3 and Trial 4.1 to ensure consistency across evaluation performed during 14th May 2025. The questionnaire was designed to capture user perceptions and experiences with the system during operational trials.

Each KVI is represented by a set of items assessed on a 1–5 Likert scale, where 1 indicates strong disagreement or poor performance, and 5 indicates strong agreement or excellent performance. For each participant, responses related to a particular KVI were averaged to obtain an individual KVI score. Subsequently, the overall performance for each KVI was calculated as the mean score across all respondents. In addition to average scores, the analysis also considered the percentage of participants who rated each KVI above a neutral value (i.e., greater than 3), indicating a generally positive perception as presented in Table 14.

Table 14. KVIs results for Trial 1.4.

KVIs	Average Score	% Participants with Score > 3
Trust/Trustworthiness	4.3	84%
Resilience	3.9	79%
Security	4.2	79%
Societal Sustainability	4.3	74%
Operational Efficiency	4.4	84%

The results provide valuable insights into the strengths of the deployed 5G-enabled system in terms of trust, resilience, security, societal impact, and operational effectiveness. The high average scores across all indicators

and the substantial percentage of participants reporting positive perceptions highlight the promising performance and user acceptance of the trialed solutions.

The analysis of the questionnaire responses from the 19 participants reveals a broadly positive assessment of the system implemented in UC1 Iasi, as reflected by the high average scores across all five KVI. All KVIs recorded mean values above 3.9 on a 5-point Likert scale, confirming the general satisfaction of stakeholders - including city hall representatives, safety authorities, SMEs, and academic actors - with the system's performance.

Among the five indicators, Operational Efficiency achieved the highest average score (4.4), underscoring the system's practical utility in supporting operational decision-making and emergency management. Trust (4.3) and Security (4.2) also scored strongly, indicating that participants had confidence in the system's accuracy, transparency, and its capability to safeguard data and maintain end-to-end integrity. While Resilience had the lowest average score (3.9), it remained well above the neutral threshold, signalling a generally reliable performance. However, this result may suggest opportunities for enhancing system robustness, particularly under fault conditions or high-demand scenarios.

These measurements confirm that the majority of users across stakeholder categories found the system satisfactory or better in terms of functionality, security, and societal benefit.

3.3 UC2: Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management

Trials 2.1 and Trial 2.2 both validated the wi.MOVE platform for public infrastructure asset management but focused on complementary objectives, locations, and measurements. Trial 2.1, conducted at AIA in January 2025, primarily targeted the performance of the AI-based road damage detection model and the end-to-end video ingestion and analytics pipeline, with KPIs measuring accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Trial 2.2 extended the evaluation to two environments - AIA and Technopolis (DAEM) - and introduced additional system components such as streaming/restreaming modules, teleoperation services, and dual-mode video transmission, with KPIs focused on uplink throughput and application round-trip latency. This second trial assessed 5G-enabled teleoperation, live analytics visualization, and network performance under both compressed and raw streaming, highlighting bandwidth/latency trade-offs and the need for next-generation 6G capabilities for ultra-low-latency, high-throughput scenarios. Together, the two trials demonstrated the robustness, scalability, and operational feasibility of the wi.MOVE platform across airport and urban municipal contexts.

3.3.1 Trial 2.1 - Public Infrastructure Assets Management

3.3.1.1 Pre-trial activities

Pre-trial activities for Trial 2.1 and the results of the road detection model evaluation are reported in deliverable D3.2 [1].

3.3.1.2 Trial description

The first trial for UC2 was carried out at AIA in January 2025. The objective was to validate the functionality of the wi.MOVE platform in a real operational environment, focusing on the road damage detection model and the overall performance of the video analysis and ingestion pipeline. During this trial, an AMR equipped with depth cameras and connected over a 5G network was deployed in the AIA premises. The robot captured video data which was transmitted to the wi.MOVE platform for real-time analysis. The system successfully identified different types of road surface damages and provided immediate visualization through the dashboard.

The outcomes of this trial confirmed the correct integration of the video ingestion and analytics components, as well as the platform's ability to process high-bandwidth data under realistic conditions. These results are summarized in Section 3.2.1.3. It should be noted that the second trial related to UC2, performed later at Technopolis (City of Athens) and including additional evaluations at AIA, is presented separately in Section 3.3.2 related to Trial 2.2, focusing on complementary aspects such as streaming/restreaming modules and teleoperation.

3.3.1.3 Trial execution and results

KPIs

As reported also in D3.2 [1] the trial evaluated several KPIs, particularly the KPI#10 (Accuracy), KPI#11 (Precision), KPI#12 (Recall), and KPI#13 (F1-score). The field trial summary is presented in Table 15 and KPIs measurements are reported in Table 16.

Table 15. Trial summary for Trial 2.1 (AIA).

Trial summary	
Trial ID	2.1
Trial setup ID	Field01
Facility/Site	AIA
Objective	Demonstration of the performance of the road damage detection model
Description	Demonstration of the performance of the road damage detection model using data captured during the trial performed at AIA on 23 and 30 January 2025.
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	5G Network, Jackal Clearpath Robot, Analytics Component
Targeted KPIs	KPI#10 (Accuracy) KPI#11 (Precision) KPI#12 (Recall) KPI#13 (F1-score)
Measurement tools	Windows Task Manager, iPerf, Jackal Clearpath robot

Table 16. Measured KPIs for Trial 2.1 (AIA).

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
2.1_Field01_1	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.80 KPI#12: 0.60 KPI#13: 0.68	KPI#10: 0.88 KPI#11: 0.85 KPI#12: 0.92 KPI#13: 0.88	Comply

The Trial 2.1 measurements at AIA demonstrated strong performance of the road damage detection model under real operating conditions. All targeted KPIs exceeded their baseline requirements, with accuracy improving from 0.85 to 0.88, precision from 0.80 to 0.85, recall from 0.60 to 0.92, and F1-score from 0.68 to 0.88, confirming both the robustness of the AI analytics pipeline and the reliability of the 5G-connected robotic data collection setup.

KVIs

It should be noted that during Trial 2.1, no KVIs were collected. The main focus of this trial was on validating the technical performance of the AI-based road damage detection model as reflected in the reported KPIs. The evaluation of KVIs, including user perception aspects such as trustworthiness, resilience, and security, was conducted exclusively in Trial 2.2. Therefore, all KVI results are presented in 0, which reports on Trial 2.2 activities.

3.3.2 Trial 2.2 - Public Infrastructure Assets Management

3.3.2.1 Pre-trial activities

Prior to the execution of the official field trial for UC2, the robot's basic behaviour was initially evaluated in a simulated environment at WINGS premises as reported in D3.1 [23]. Preliminary system validation and fine-tuning were then carried out directly on-site at the respective field locations. These preparatory steps enabled

the team to assess the robot's baseline functionality, adjust configurations as needed, and ensure operational readiness within the real-world environments of the AIA and Technopolis (City of Athens).

3.3.2.2 Trial description

Trial 2.2 (AIA)

The field trial was conducted on 23 and 30 January 2025. The trial took place in the designated apron testing facilities, a secured area not used for passenger operations, providing an ideal environment to evaluate road infrastructure inspection methods and system performance under realistic but controlled conditions.

The main objective of the trial was to assess the condition of airport road infrastructure using a combination of 5G-enabled robotic systems and AI-based video analytics, enabling the proactive detection of surface damages - such as cracks and potholes - and supporting preventive maintenance operations. This approach is expected to contribute to cost savings, faster response times, and extended infrastructure longevity. The AIA trial involved participants from WINGS and AIA staff working in the operations and maintenance department.

The deployed setup centered on the Jackal Clearpath, an all-terrain autonomous mobile robot equipped with:

- **Quectel 5G connectivity module:** for low-latency, high-bandwidth communication,
- **Intel RealSense D435 depth camera:** for capturing high-resolution RGB and depth data,
- **2-DOF pan-tilt mount:** allowing dynamic camera positioning for thorough area coverage.

The Jackal Clearpath was remotely operated via a dedicated dashboard over the 5G network by AIA simulating real-world inspection workflows. The dashboard provided two video streams:

- **Live and low latency compressed feed:** to assist the operator with safe teleoperation,
- **High-resolution, processed video stream:** restreamed from the wi.MOVE platform after passing through AI-based analytics. This stream visualized in real time the detection of faults, severity estimation, and suggested corrective actions.

The analytics module supported the identification of structural faults, damage classification, and maintenance recommendations, transforming raw video into actionable insights. All data were transferred via 5G to the cloud-based wi.MOVE platform for processing and visualization. In addition to the teleoperated inspection, the dashboard manager at the terminal operations supervisors office was remotely connected via 5G to the wi.MOVE dashboard, where he observed both the live inspection and real-time analytic outcomes.

Key functionalities validated during the trial included:

- Responsive 5G teleoperation of the AMR,
- Dual-mode video streaming for safe navigation and analytic precision,
- Dynamic camera control for detailed inspection,
- AI-powered infrastructure analysis for real-time condition assessment.

The successful trial validated the use of autonomous systems, real-time video analytics, and 5G communications for infrastructure monitoring in an operational airport setting. Live demonstration images from the AIA locations where the trial took place are presented in Figure 41, Figure 42 and Figure 43.

Figure 41. View from the inspection at AIA Express facility utilising the Jackal Clearpath base.

Figure 42. View from the Terminal Operations Supervisors office while running UC2 trial at AIA.

Figure 43. wi.MOVE dashboard while AIA staff watch the outcome of the analysis and the stream from the AMR.

Trial 2.2 (Technopolis, City of Athens)

As a complementary field trial of this use case, a second trial was conducted on June 12th, 2025, at Technopolis City of Athens, in close collaboration with DAEM, the City of Athens IT company. Following the initial trial at AIA, this event extended the evaluation into an urban municipal context, enabling validation of the solution's adaptability across different types of infrastructure. Technopolis, a well-known venue for cultural and technological events, provided an ideal real-world urban setting for assessing the system's ability to detect and analyze infrastructure faults, such as pavement cracks or road surface issues, using 5G-connected robotic platforms and AI-based analytics. The trial aimed to assess the teleoperation capabilities of a 5G-connected robotic platform and to measure the integration and functionality of the wi.MOVE dashboard, which aggregates, analyses, and displays real-time detection results for infrastructure faults.

The trial featured the Jackal Clearpath, configured with:

- **Teltonika 5G module:** enabling real-time data transfer with ultra-low latency,
- **Fixposition Real-Time Kinematic 2 (RTK) and MicroStrain GX5-25 IMU:** sensors for precise localization,
- **Ouster OS1 3D LiDAR:** for spatial awareness,
- **Intel RealSense D435:** depth cameras and feeds from fixed surveillance cameras.

During the trial, the Jackal Clearpath was remotely teleoperated across selected pathways of Technopolis, while video and sensor data were streamed in real time over the 5G network. The wi.MOVE dashboard provided live camera views, interactive maps showing the robot's position, and an immediate display of detected damage including type, severity, and location. System operators were able to (i) safely navigate the AGV using the live

video stream, (ii) monitor damage detections as they appeared in the system, and (iii) review historical data, alerts, and activity logs. This second trial successfully confirmed the scalability and flexibility of the proactive infrastructure management system in an urban municipal context. When combined with insights from the AIA trial, the Technopolis deployment highlighted the solution's potential to support data-driven, cost-effective maintenance strategies for both airport and city infrastructures using 5G, AI, and robotics technologies. Live demonstration images from Technopolis are presented in Figure 44, Figure 45 and Figure 46.

Figure 44. Live demonstration of UC2 solution features.

Figure 45. Teleoperation platform for remote monitoring demonstration.

Figure 46. wi.MOVE platform live demonstration.

3.3.2.3 Trial execution and results

The trial summary is reported in Table 17 while the results that were executed in the two locations of AIA and Technopolis (City of Athens) regarding Trial 2.2 are reported separately below.

Table 17. Trial summary for Trial 2.2.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	2.2
Trial setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	AIA, Technopolis (City of Athens)
Objective	Demonstration of the performance of the streaming and restreaming modules of wi.MOVE
Description	The idea is to measure the performance of the solution for the 2 locations (AIA, DAEM) as defined above
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	Streaming and restreaming module, Teleoperation Service, wi.MOVE dashboard
Targeted KPIs	KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) KPI#08 (App round-trip latency)
Measurement tools	Windows Task Manager, iPerf, Jackal Clearpath robot

KPIs (AIA)

The trial results for AIA regarding Trial 2.2 are reported below.

While streaming raw video is essential for achieving better algorithmic results in road damage analysis, it significantly impacts network performance. Measurements results reveal enabling raw video streaming:

- Increases latency from an average of 30 ms to 130 ms, and
- Upload throughput spikes from 1 MB/s to 100 MB/s.

The Figure 47 highlight the limitations of current commercial 5G networks, particularly in handling large-scale data while maintaining real-time responsiveness.

Such a substantial increase in latency and bandwidth demand poses a challenge for applications that rely on rapid decision-making and precise teleoperation, as delays of 130 ms are not viable for technologies requiring instantaneous feedback. The ability to balance the demands of high data throughput and low latency is paramount, underscoring the necessity for next-generation networks. Consequently, 6G networks offer promising solutions by delivering ultra-low latency, enhanced bandwidth efficiency, and optimized network slicing to support these high-demand scenarios.

Figure 47. Streaming and restreaming modules performance.

The trial also evaluated several KPIs (see Table 18), particularly the KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) and KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency), both with raw streaming and compressed streaming.

Table 18. Measured KPIs for Trial 2.2 (AIA).

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
2.2_Field01_01 (raw streaming)	KPI#08: 800ms	KPI#08: 195,66ms	Comply
2.2_Field01_02 (compressed streaming)		KPI#08: 45,27ms	Comply
2.2_Field02_01 (raw streaming)	KPI#06: 30Mbit/s	KPI#06: 100,68 Mbit/s	Comply
2.2_Field02_02 (compressed streaming)		KPI#06: 0,77 Mbit/s	Value obtained was lower than expected due to the compression applied.

KPI measurements confirm that both uplink throughput (KPI#06) and application round-trip latency (KPI#08) comply with trial requirements for both raw and compressed streaming, with compressed streaming achieving significantly lower latency (45 ms) and more efficient bandwidth usage (0.77 Mbit/s). These results highlight the importance of carefully selecting streaming modes based on operational needs—using compressed streams for real-time teleoperation and raw streams for high-precision analytics where latency tolerance allows. Overall, the findings underline the need for next-generation network capabilities, such as ultra-low-latency communication, dynamic network slicing, and edge-cloud processing, to simultaneously sustain high-throughput data flows and deterministic responsiveness required for future mission-critical robotics applications.

During testing, streaming 640×480 at ~30 fps as uncompressed raw yielded an uplink of ≈100.68 Mbit/s with ≈195.66 ms reported latency. The high bit rate increases serialization time and queueing on the uplink, which elevates latency. When the same signal was compressed (H.264-class), the uplink dropped to ≈0.77 Mbit/s and the reported latency to ≈45.25 ms. In short, these measurements match expectations: raw VGA at 30 fps demands on the order of 100–150 Mbit/s and incurs higher latency, whereas modern codecs achieve the same frame rate well under 1 Mbit/s with significantly lower latency on the same link.

KPIs (Technopolis, City of Athens)

The measurements reveal that even a minimal MQTT (see Figure 48) data stream (~0.2 Mbps) on a 5G network exhibits average RTT on 20-25 ms, with peak spikes exceeding 50 ms and pronounced jitter, while sustained video stream (~5 Mbps) yields slightly higher average RTTs of 20-30 ms, frequent excursions above 40 ms, and similarly erratic latency variation.

Such performance falls well short of the sub- 10ms, and ultimately sub- 1 ms, latency and deterministic delay bounds required by emerging applications such as real-time haptic control, autonomous systems, and immersive extended-reality experiences.

These results underscore the necessity of next-generation 6G networks, which are designed to guarantee ultra-low, ultra-stable end-to-end latency, vastly improved jitter control, and integrated AI-driven resource management to meet the stringent quality-of-service demands of tomorrow’s mission-critical services.

Figure 48. RTT and Upload throughput over time for data transferring (left) RTT and Upload throughput over time for video streaming (right).

The trial also evaluated several KPIs (see Table 19), particularly the KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) and KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency), concerning the video streaming and the data transferring.

Table 19. Measured KPIs for Trial 2.2 (Technopolis, City of Athens).

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
2.2_Field01_01 (video streaming)	KPI#08 RTT: 800ms	KPI#08: 24,87ms	Comply
2.2_Field02_01 (data transferring)		KPI#08: 25,29ms	Comply
2.2_Field01_02 (video streaming)	KPI#06 Uplink: 30Mbit/s	KPI#06: 48,2 Mbit/s	Comply
2.2_Field02_02 (data transferring)		KPI#06: 0,029 Mbit/s	Value obtained was lower than expected due to the compression applied.

Trial evaluated 5G-enabled teleoperation and real-time analytics, focusing on uplink throughput (KPI#06) and application round-trip latency (KPI#08) for both video streaming and data transfer. Video streaming RTT was 24.87 ms—well below the 800 ms requirement—while data transfer RTT was 25.29 ms, demonstrating stable low-latency performance suitable for teleoperation and live analytics. Uplink throughput for video streaming reached 48.2 Mbit/s against a 30 Mbit/s requirement, and data transfer throughput was 0.029 Mbit/s, sufficient for lightweight telemetry.

Both the video stream and the MQTT telemetry place only a light load on the 5G uplink, leaving ample head-room. Because queuing is minimal, end-to-end latency stays low and stable for both services. In short, these traffic levels do not stress the 5G link, which is why the RTT remains consistently low and the KPI is met.

KVIs

The main KVs that have been addressed by Trial 2.2 of UC2 are Trustworthiness, Resilience, and Security. The questionnaire that has been provided to the users makes use of a Likert scale [24] to assess the aforementioned key values. For each statement, the participants had to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagree, using a scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Annex E reports the questionnaires that were provided while the KVI results are presented in the Section 0.

According to the respondents, the AI-based infrastructure management system is perceived as highly reliable and secure across all major dimensions evaluated (see Table 20). The feedback gathered during the trials reflects strong user confidence in its trustworthiness, resilience, and security.

Trust in the system was particularly high, with an average rating of 4.3 out of 5, and 100% of participants giving scores above 3. Respondents expressed strong confidence in the reliability of the data sources and the system's ability to accurately detect damage in infrastructure. These results indicate that users found the AI analytics both credible and actionable. While trust was universally positive, a few comments suggested that improving transparency in how data is used and how detection results are generated could make the system even more trustworthy.

The system's resilience, its ability to function reliably and recover quickly from potential issues, was also rated highly, with an average score of 4.3. 88% of respondents provided ratings above 3, highlighting satisfaction with the system's performance, even under demanding conditions. Some users mentioned that real-time responsiveness and recovery from interruptions were particularly strong points. Nonetheless, there were isolated concerns related to how the system handles multiple concurrent streams or updates during unexpected downtimes, suggesting room for enhancement in performance consistency under stress.

Security was equally well-rated, also scoring an average of 4.3, with 88% of users indicating confidence in the system's security features and data protection measures. Respondents felt that the platform provided robust safeguards against cyber threats and handled sensitive data appropriately. A few neutral responses, however,

point to a potential benefit in increasing visibility and user awareness of the security protocols in place, such as data encryption and access controls, to further reinforce a sense of digital safety.

The strong and balanced scores suggest that the system is well-regarded by its users, with a solid foundation in trust, technical reliability, and security assurance. Small refinements in transparency and performance communication could further elevate user confidence and system adoption in future deployments.

Table 20. KVI average scores for Trial 2.2.

KVIs	Average Score	% Participants with Score > 3
Trust/Trustworthiness	4.3	100%
Resilience	4.3	88%
Security	4.3	88%

3.4 UC3: Autonomous APRON

3.4.1 Trial 3.1 - Autonomous APRON

This section presents the results of the UC3 trials at AIA, focusing on the demonstration of the robot's autonomous capabilities as well as the evaluation of KPIs and KVIs. The data collected provides valuable insights into the technical performance and operational impact of the system in a real-world airport environment.

3.4.1.1 Pre-trial activities

Prior to the execution of the official field trial for UC3, the robot's basic behaviour was initially evaluated in a simulated environment at WINGS premises. Preliminary validation and fine-tuning of the system were then performed directly on-site at the respective field locations. These preparatory steps enabled the team to assess the robot's baseline functionality, make necessary configuration adjustments, and ensure operational readiness within the real-world environment of AIA.

3.4.1.2 Trial description

The Trial 3.1 was conducted on March 6, 2025, at the designated apron testing facilities of AIA "Eleftherios Venizelos". The trial area, not used for passenger gate operations, was prepared specifically to evaluate autonomous baggage transportation using an AGV equipped with advanced sensor technologies and supported by B5G communications. The trial involved 10 users from both airport and project personnel.

The primary objective of the trial was to demonstrate the AGV's ability to autonomously navigate from a pre-defined starting point (Point A) to a destination (Point B) using RTK-based localization for centimeter-level accuracy. The AGV continuously monitored satellite signal integrity to maintain reliable navigation. The robot was tasked with safely transporting a trolley carrying a cabin-size luggage item within the controlled area, ensuring efficient, secure, and autonomous operation.

The trial setup included:

- **Wi.SUPPLY platform (formerly WINGSChariot):** used by the operators as the central control and monitoring interface for the autonomous baggage transport system and provided real-time status overview, navigation and system diagnostics and control capabilities.
- **Jackal Clearpath robotic system:** a compact, rugged unmanned ground vehicle designed for challenging terrain. The AGV was operated autonomously, with remote control capabilities enabled via a high-speed, low-latency 5G network.
- **DT application:** provided the operators real-time monitoring of the AVG with intuitive visualization that include 360-degree video streaming, real-time data display from sensors and map representation. This application is connected to Wi.SUPPLY platform for real-time communication and data display.

Key components of the AGV system configuration included:

- **Intel RealSense D435:** for real-time depth sensing and RGB video streaming,
- **2-DOF pan-tilt mount:** for dynamic camera positioning,

- **Fixposition RTK2 sensor:** delivering centimeter-level GNSS localization accuracy,
- **MicroStrain GX5-25 IMU:** for precise motion sensing,
- **Ricoh Theta 360 camera:** for panoramic situational awareness,
- **Ouster OS1 3D LiDAR:** for high-resolution environmental perception and collision avoidance,
- **5G connectivity module:** for real-time data exchange and remote system monitoring.

More specifically, the autonomous baggage trailer in this setup is built on a Jackal Clearpath AMR mobile base, integrated with a Teltonika 5G module for high-speed, low-latency connectivity, ensuring seamless communication in airport environments. For precise localization, it utilizes a Fixposition RTK2 sensor, achieving centimeter-level accuracy. A 3D LiDAR is employed for collision avoidance and 3D mapping, enhancing environmental awareness. Additionally, the system features both a 360-degree camera and a depth camera, enabling real-time monitoring and precise navigation. To further refine motion sensing, a MicroStrain GX5-25 IMU is included, providing high-fidelity data on speed and acceleration. This comprehensive sensor suite ensures the AGV operates efficiently and safely within the autonomous airport operations ecosystem.

The trial process involved evaluating the autonomous navigation and baggage transport capabilities of the robot within the designated airport testing area. The robot was controlled through the integrated dashboard, where preconfigured waypoint goals define the loading and unloading zones for luggage. These waypoints are real-world latitude and longitude coordinates, forming a predefined safety path that the robot must follow with high precision. The robot autonomously navigates between these waypoints using RTK-based localization to ensure accuracy. Upon reaching each goal, the robot pauses and waits for the next command, verifying its position before proceeding, ensuring safe and efficient operation throughout the measurement scenario. Live demonstration images from the AIA locations where the trial took place are presented in Figure 49, Figure 50 and Figure 51.

Figure 49. Wi.SUPPLY dashboard live demonstration during the field trial of UC3 at AIA.

Figure 50. Digital Twin application live demonstration during the field trial of UC3 at AIA.

Figure 51. Jackal Clearpath live demonstration during UC3 field trial at AIA.

3.4.1.3 Trial execution and results

During the trial, the AGV followed a route composed of smaller waypoints to ensure movement within the predefined safe path. The real-time position was constantly verified, and if the localization error exceeded a defined threshold, the system would initiate a safe-stop protocol. Upon reaching the destination, AIA responsible collected the luggage, and the AGV autonomously returned to the starting point, awaiting its next task.

Throughout the trial, WINGS and AIA staff monitored the system via the Wi.SUPPLY platform and the user digital twin application. Live data streams, including video, telemetry, and sensor outputs, were transmitted through the 5G network to allow real-time decision-making, incident handling, and performance evaluation. Multiple operators at different airport locations, connected via the B5G infrastructure, were able to access the platform and observe the trial in real-time.

During the trial, the position accuracy was always under 0.2 meters in the x-y plane, proving the crucial need of RTK technology for outdoor localization (see Figure 52).

When upload throughput increases, RTT latency sometimes decreases, suggesting that network congestion is minimal and the connection is efficiently handling the data up to this load. There are moments where the RTT latency has noticeable peaks. These could be due to transient network congestion, interference, or handovers between 5G cells.

Figure 52. Position accuracy over time (left) and comparison between latency and upload throughput over time for UC3 Trials at AIA (right).

KPIs

Table 21 presents the trial summary for Trial 3.1. The evaluation focuses on a combination of KPIs, some of which have already been measured in the laboratory, while others were measured during the trial such as KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device), KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency), KPI#15 (Service reliability), and KPI#17 (Service availability).

Table 21. Trial summary for Trial 3.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	3.1
Trial setup ID	Field01
Facility/Site	AIA
Objective	Demonstration of the performance of the robot's autonomy and service layer KPI measurement
Description	Demonstration of the performance of the robot's autonomy and service layer KPI measurement
Executed by	WINGS
Components involved	Jackal Clearpath robot, Wi.SUPPLY platform, User Digital Twin application
Targeted KPIs	KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#15 (Service Reliability) KPI#17 (Service Availability)
Measurement tools	Windows Task Manager, iPerf, Jackal Clearpath robot

In terms of KPIs, Table 22 details the requirements and results of the measurements.

Table 22. Measured KPIs for Trial 3.1 at AIA.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
3.1_Field01	KPI#06: 30Mbit/s KPI#08: 80ms KPI#15: 99.99% KPI#17: 99.99%	KPI#06: 1.33Mbit/s KPI#08: 42.9ms KPI#15: 99.99% KPI#17: 99.99%	Comply

The KPIs measured in Trial 3.1 at AIA indicate that all requirements were successfully met, with uplink throughput (KPI#06) at 1.33 Mbit/s, application round-trip latency (KPI#08) at 42.9 ms, and service availability/reliability (KPI#15 and KPI#17) maintaining 99.99%, demonstrating full compliance with the target performance.

KVIs

Following the completion of the UC3 trial at Athens International Airport, participants were invited to complete a structured questionnaire aimed at evaluating the system's performance across four KVIs such as Trust/Trustworthiness, Resilience, Security, and Operational Efficiency. The assessment utilized a 5-point Likert scale, with questions tailored to each KVI to reflect specific system capabilities and user perceptions. Below and in Table 23, a synthesis of the results is presented, incorporating both the average scores and the proportion of participants (out of 10) who rated each indicator positively (score >3). Annex E reports the questionnaires provided to the participants.

Trust/Trustworthiness received a high rating, with an average score of 3.9 and 100% of participants assigning a score greater than 3. Participants expressed confidence in the system's ability to provide accurate insights and timely notifications, particularly in relation to AGV operations and anomaly detection via the APRON Digital Twin. The clarity of real-time visual feedback, such as 360-degree video and map-based monitoring, enhanced

this perception. While the system was seen as credible and supportive of operational tasks, further improvements could focus on increasing transparency regarding data usage and the logic behind alerts.

Resilience was the lowest-rated KVI, with an average score of 3.8 and 70% of participants rating it above 3. While the AGV and sensor infrastructure were generally viewed as reliable, some users noted concerns about fault recovery and performance stability under high-load or failure conditions. This suggests opportunities to strengthen fault-tolerance, improve feedback during errors, and make recovery processes more transparent to users.

Security emerged as the highest-rated dimension, with an average score of 4.1 and 90% of participants assigning it a score above 3. Participants expressed strong confidence in the system's ability to safeguard sensitive data, including sensor outputs and analytics, from unauthorized access or cyber threats. This trust was reinforced by the secure integration of B5G communications, robust encryption, and controlled access mechanisms, highlighting security as a key enabler for future deployments in critical environments.

Operational Efficiency also performed strongly, earning an average score of 4.0 and a 90% positive rating. Participants emphasized the AGV's precise and timely execution of tasks, including autonomous luggage transportation. Features such as real-time visual tracking and centimetre-level localization contributed to productivity gains and process optimization. Additionally, the system's intuitive interface and support for manual intervention during emergencies were well received.

Overall, user feedback from the trial was positive, particularly in the areas of security and operational efficiency, with trust closely following. While resilience was still positively rated, it emerged as the area with the most room for enhancement. These findings validate the effectiveness of the UC3 solution in real-world airport operations, while also offering actionable insights for future refinements and scalability considerations.

Table 23. KVI results for Trial 3.1.

KVIs	Average Score	% Participants with Score > 3
Trust/Trustworthiness	3.9	100%
Resilience	3.8	70%
Security	4.1	90%
Operational Efficiency	4.0	90%

3.5 UC4: Smart Traffic Management

The following sections present the trial activities performed for UC4 in Iasi.

3.5.1 Trial 4.1 - Smart Traffic Monitoring

Trial 4.1 focuses on smart traffic management using surveillance cameras connected over a B5G network. The location for this trial was the Podu Roş intersection in Iaşi, Romania, a key urban traffic hub. The trial explores several relevant scenarios such as: a) real-time detection and classification of vehicles and VRUs, and b) triggering alerts when specific traffic conditions or safety risks are detected.

3.5.1.1 Pre-trial activities

Preparatory activities for UC4 at the Podu Roş intersection in Iaşi were carried out during October 2023–December 2024, when cameras were connected through ORO's 5G NSA network to TUIASI servers, where the analytics pipeline was adapted with Nvidia DeepStream for vehicle detection and alerts.

3.5.1.2 Trial description

5G NSA and 5G SA configurations have been trialed in UC4 by measuring KPIs in December 2024 and KPIs and KVIs in May 2025. The aim was to assess critical performance metrics such as latency, uplink throughput, and sustainability (KVIs).

To evaluate the effectiveness of the solution, detailed feedback from 19 use case operators was collected in May 2025, through structured questionnaires, providing practical insights into real-world implementation challenges.

Additionally, the full set of application features was deployed and measured, unlocking advanced smart traffic monitoring functionalities such as real-time traffic participant detection and trajectory estimation. Following applications scenarios were implemented and evaluated from KPIs and KVI measurements:

- **Sensing traffic participants:** The scenario counts the number of pedestrians and vehicles passing through the Podu Roş intersection in Iaşi. Live video feeds from multiple cameras were processed, considering only the objects within a predefined region of interest that covers the most relevant sections of the intersection. The application utilizes the same YOLO v7 neural network model as described for UC1, with modifications in configuration to adapt to the intersection scenario. The detected objects are categorized and counted in each frame, with the resulting time series optionally smoothed using an exponential moving average filter. The processed data is published in real-time to a Kafka messaging system, from where it is ingested by a dashboard application that visualizes traffic trends dynamically.
- **Car flow estimation:** The scenario aims to estimate and display vehicle trajectories as they cross the Podu Roş intersection. Using the same YOLO v7 neural network model, the system detects vehicles in each frame and converts detection centroid coordinates to GPS locations through an extrinsic calibration procedure. The GPS data is published in real-time to the Kafka server and visualized on the dashboard.
- **Car detection in forbidden areas:** In this scenario the objective is to detect when a car is inside a predefined forbidden area and trigger a visible alert on the video. The analysis and display are done in real-time, at the FPS value of the video feed (25 FPS), with no significant delays.

In conclusion, both 5G NSA and SA configurations were evaluated across the two trial sessions, enabling a progressive validation of the smart traffic monitoring system. The final trial, conducted over the upgraded 5G SA network, showcased the full implementation of application features and reinforced the system's advanced capabilities for real-time analytics and intelligent traffic management.

In synthesis, both trials based on 5G NSA and 5G SA network configurations respectively demonstrated the system's ability to support low-latency, high-throughput applications, ensuring seamless data processing and communication. The results of the trial over 5G NSA are reported in Appendix C while the ones related to the 5G SA deployment are details in the following section.

3.5.1.3 Trial execution and results

This trial performed in May 2025 followed the deployment of the 5G SA infrastructure and built upon the earlier 5G NSA trial campaign completed in December 2024.

The primary goal of this trial was to confirm how the 5G SA network supports reliable, low-latency data processing at scale for smart traffic applications. The implemented scenarios included vehicle classification (cars, buses, trucks), detection of traffic pedestrians, identification of abnormal behavior (e.g., passing through forbidden areas), and issuing safety alerts to application operators.

The trial was performed using the configuration outlined in Table 24, while Table 25 presents the trial summary.

Table 24. Trial setup description for Trial 4.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field03
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	50 dBm (~120 W)
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	64TX 64RX
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 25. Trial summary for Trial 4.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	4.1
Trial setup ID	Field03
Facility/Site	Iasi
Objective	Demonstration of the video analytics application capabilities and performance measurements for the SA network setup
Description	The application focuses on several distinct scenarios of practical interest: a) estimation of vehicles density in the surveyed area; b) total count of vehicles and people passing through a specific access facility; c) detecting cars entering within a restricted access area.
Executed by	TUIASI and ORO
Components involved	5G SA network, cameras and 5G routers, edge-compute infrastructure, video analytics application
Targeted KPIs	KPI#05 (Downlink throughput per device) KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) KPI#07 (Coverage) KPI#09 (Application one-way latency) KPI#16 (Communication Availability) KPI#17 (Service availability)
Measurement tools	iPerf3, nPerf, Speed Test, ping, Netdata, Jaeger

KPIs

The KPI measurements were carried out in May 2025 to evaluate the E2E performance of the solution, covering both network-level and application-level aspects. The summarized results from these network-level measurements are presented in Table 26 while the 5G CPE measurements are presented in Figure 53.

Table 26. Measured KPIs for Trial 4.1.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
4.1_Field03_01	KPI#05: 200 Mbps KPI#06: 50 Mbps KPI#07: 0.5 km ² KPI#09: 50 ms KPI#16: 99.9 % KPI#17: 99.9 %	KPI#05: 220 Mbps KPI#06: 83.5 Mbps KPI#07: 0.5 km ² KPI#09: 20 ms KPI#16: 99.9 % KPI#17: 99.9 %	All key KPIs were met, confirming the system's robust performance, excellent coverage, and high reliability even during a high-traffic public event.

Figure 53. 5G CPE measurements.

To assess the system’s performance under realistic operational conditions, application-level measurements were conducted by capturing and analysing the video traffic generated by surveillance cameras positioned at the Podu

Roş intersection in Iaşi. The video streams were transmitted over the SA 5G network to the edge computing infrastructure for processing.

From application-level, two primary configurations were designed to evaluate system behaviour in both low-load and full-load scenarios. These configurations enabled the validation of throughput, latency, and overall system responsiveness in traffic monitoring applications. In particular:

- **Single Camera Evaluation (4.1_Field03_02.1):** The first configuration focused on measuring system performance with one active video source. A single camera (camera #5), installed at the Podu Roş intersection, streamed video at 2688x1512 resolution, 25 FPS, using H.264 (Main profile) with a maximum bitrate of 10.240 Mbps. This configuration represented a baseline for latency and throughput evaluation under minimal load. This setup helped establish a reference measurement for optimal conditions using a single camera in a high-resolution traffic surveillance scenario.
- **Multi-Camera Full Load Scenario (4.1_Field03_02.2):** The second configuration extended the evaluation to the full setup, involving all six cameras mounted at Podu Roş. All video feeds were configured at maximum resolution (2688x1512@25FPS, H.264 Main profile, 10.240 Mbps bitrate). The goal was to observe how the system handled simultaneous high-definition streams and to validate real-time video analytics performance.

This full-scale trial demonstrated the solution's capability to operate under increased data volume, representing typical urban traffic monitoring conditions.

It is important to note that the measured throughput is influenced by multiple factors, particularly the level of movement and traffic dynamics within the camera's field of view. The corresponding results are detailed in Table 27.

Table 27. Application-level measured KPIs for Trial 4.1.

Measured ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Description	Validation
4.1_Field03_02.1	KPI#01: 10.24 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 11.3 Mbps KPI#08: 216 ms KPI#09: 18 ms	A single camera running (cam5), resolution 2688x1512@25FPS	Measurement was carried out during a period of typically high traffic, reflecting standard daytime activity at the intersection.
4.1_Field03_02.2	KPI#01: 65 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 67.6 Mbps KPI#08: 316 ms KPI#09: 18 ms	All 6 cameras in intersection, resolution 2688x1512@25FPS	The trial day exhibited sustained vehicle flow, representative of regular peak-time conditions for the intersection.

The KPI measurements performed in May 2025 demonstrated that the 5G SA solution met required performance levels under real-world conditions. During a busy public event, downlink throughput reached 220 Mbps and uplink 83.5 Mbps, with latency as low as 20 ms and full-service availability. These results confirm the robustness of the 5G SA setup even in dense urban scenarios with heavy user presence.

Application-level measurements at the Podu Roş intersection validated system performance further. With a single camera, throughput was 11.3 Mbps and round-trip latency 216 ms. When all six cameras streamed simultaneously, throughput scaled to 67.6 Mbps, though latency rose to 316 ms due to processing delays. This

shows the system handles high data volumes well but needs optimization to reduce video processing time for real-time analytics.

In conclusion, the 5G SA solution supports smart city applications like traffic monitoring effectively. Still, enhancements in processing hardware, video encoding, and bandwidth management will be essential to maintain low latency and scalability as the system grows.

In the context of the KPIs addressed in the trial, E2E latency is a pivotal KPI in vehicular services where safety and responsiveness are of great importance. Designed for high-mobility environments, these services are expected to operate with E2E latency below 100 ms. Such mission-critical performance directly impacts the protection of VRUs such as pedestrians and cyclists. In the context of UC4 for Smart Traffic Management, video vigilance systems equipped with object detection capabilities must therefore operate with minimal delay to enable timely and accurate decision-making.

To address these stringent requirements, the Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) framework provides continuous monitoring and management of multiple Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) domains within a unified environment. It integrates and coordinates diverse components and technologies, such as orchestration modules, monitoring tools, and NFVI domains, under a common control system, ensuring that service quality can be maintained even under demanding conditions. Its adaptability was first demonstrated during the IMEC-NXW integration tests, where the orchestrator successfully managed two distinct NFVI deployments in Belgium and Italy, extending the framework beyond the Smart Highway testbed. Building on this, the IMEC-ORO trials conducted at the Romanian site validated the framework’s ability to maintain stable service performance under varying load conditions. In these trials, E2E latency was measured between a UE in a lab environment and a video service instance deployed across multiple nodes spanning three virtual machines in the 5G NFVI edge environment as seen in Figure 54..

Figure 54. ZSM Framework GUI displaying live performance status and service orchestration at ORO 5G infrastructure.

The UE received a live video stream from the same service used in the UC4 trials, while latency metrics were continuously reported to the ZSM orchestrator running on a GPU-enabled VM. When latency exceeded the 100 ms threshold, the orchestrator migrated the service to a node with more resources, maintaining low latency. This

dynamic adaptation kept latency within ~20 ms range even under stress scenarios with up to 1000 concurrent users, preserving the QoS essential for real-time traffic monitoring and VRU protection.

In this trial, the hosted services were run with a number of concurrent users exceeding UC4 limits, in order to push and evaluate the resilience of the ZSM Framework under these conditions. These users were introduced gradually, with 500 new users joining every second, meaning the full load was reached in just about two seconds. To avoid excessive sensitivity to natural latency fluctuations and prevent counterproductive oscillations between nodes, a 30 ms tolerance threshold was introduced. This mechanism minimized unnecessary migration or scaling actions, which could otherwise add overhead and increase response times.

Under stress conditions, latency increased from 17.468 ms to 497.045 ms in the node ztm2-vm. Once the orchestrator triggered a redeployment to a better-performing pod, latency rapidly dropped to 18.878 ms as seen in Figure 55. This confirmed the effectiveness of the framework in stabilizing QoS during high-load scenarios. It is worth noting that deployment actions may introduce temporary delays, as seen in earlier experiments reported in deliverables D2.4 [26] when orchestrating across both the Smart Highway and NXW NFVI domains. However, such additional lag was not observed in the ORO 5G infrastructure, since all components of the ZSM framework were co-located in the same geographical domain.

id integer	node_id integer	node_name character varying	latency double precision	timestamp double precision
515136	224	ztm2-vm	17.468	1756286593.0232673
515137	224	ztm2-vm	17.468	1756286593.0232673
515138	224	ztm2-vm	17.468	1756286593.0232673
515139	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286594.032876
515140	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286594.1478348
515141	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286594.1478348
515142	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286594.1478348
515143	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286595.2655272
515144	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286595.2655272
515145	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286595.2655272
515146	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286596.36779
515147	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286596.36779
515148	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286596.36779
515149	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286597.4919448
515150	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286597.4919448
515151	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286597.4919448
515152	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286598.604006
515153	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286598.604006
515154	224	ztm2-vm	497.045	1756286598.604006
515155	223	ml-vm	18.878	1756286599.170688
515156	223	ml-vm	18.878	1756286599.170688
515157	223	ml-vm	18.878	1756286599.170688
515158	223	ml-vm	18.878	1756286600.190877
515159	223	ml-vm	14.201	1756286600.7606382

E2E latency increases in node ztm2-vm

Switch to node ml-vm and E2E latency decreases

Figure 55. Extract of ZSM orchestrator decision traces showing service migration actions triggered by E2E latency variations.

The progression of this behavior is illustrated in the accompanying chart in Figure 56, where E2E latency increased under stress in node ztm2-vm until the orchestrator shifted the service to node ml-vm with greater resource availability, thereby restoring the expected QoS.

Figure 56. E2E latency variations and the ZSM orchestrator decisions showing node selection changes.

These traces represent the orchestrator’s decision records, showing both the KPI values of the selected node and the corresponding actions taken to maintain service quality when latency surpassed the 100 ms tolerance threshold for this type of service.

The IMEC-ORO trials demonstrated that the ZSM framework is able to meet sub-100 ms latency requirements under demanding conditions, highlighting its potential for enhancing B5G/6G network applications in Smart Traffic Management scenarios.

KVIs

The KVIs defined for UC4 are to the same of those established for UC1 in Iași (see section 3.2.2.3), as both use cases were measured on the same trial day in May 2025. Feedback was collected from the same group of 19 responders, ensuring consistent evaluation across both scenarios.

3.6 UC5: Control Room in Metaverse

This section provides data and information regarding both the pre-trial activities carried out since the laboratory tests as well as the final trial.

3.6.1 Trial 5.1 - Control Room in Metaverse

3.6.1.1 Pre-trial activities

Pre-trial activities for UC5 were conducted to verify the capacity of the commercial 5G NSA network in the Talent Garden building and in selected spots of Parco del Valentino. Tests were carried out on 8 and 30 July 2024 using six smartphones and tablets, with speed tests measurements. The complete results and measurement details are reported in Annex D. In the park, the downlink throughput ranged between 40 and 200 Mbps, with a mean of 130 Mbps in the first session and up to 312 Mbps in the second, while the uplink varied from 25 to 70 Mbps, with mean values around 47–57 Mbps. The uplink did not meet the 100 Mbps requirement, although downlink consistently exceeded the 100 Mbps throughput.

Additional validation was performed at the Talent Garden site with two headsets connected through a 5G CPE. Here, the system achieved stable results, with 135 Mbps downlink and 42 Mbps uplink, meeting both defined requirements (100/20 Mbps). These measurements confirmed that the network conditions at the control staff location were adequate, while the park locations showed variability, particularly for uplink capacity.

3.6.1.2 Trial description

Preparing for the trial required substantial effort and time, beginning three months prior to the scheduled date of the field tests described above. Particular attention was taken in the preparatory work, as it would not have been feasible to repeat it with the involvement of Turin’s security forces, who made a special effort for the trial day. The detailed planning of the trial is shown in Table 28.

Table 28. Detail Planning of Trial 5.1.

T = Trial Day	Activities
T- 90 days	Perform Field Test
T- 70 days	Prepare detailed scenario and demo video
T- 50 days	Send invitation with agenda, scenario and video link to participants
T- 30 days	Send first reminder to participants
T- 30 days	Prepare list of devices and network connections
T- 30 days	Prepare questionnaires for KVI
T- 15 days	Send second reminder to participants
T- 1 day	Bring and test devices and network onsite
T	Trial with KPI, KVI and picture/video capture
T+ 7 days	Send feedback to participants with video possible KVI questions complement

In order to ensure a smooth and efficient execution of the trial, the agents of the security forces received before various material including a description of the use case, a video clip in Italian explaining the different features of the application and a detailed scenario of the trial that is summarized in Table 29.

Table 29. Scenario for Trial 5.1.

Scenario description	
1	In anticipation of a big concert, the four Operations Centers of the security forces (Police, Fire Brigade, 118(Ambulance), 112) are already connected to the MCR in the Data Room using 3D viewers.
2	A video camera and a people counter sensor are installed in the vicinity of the car park, also connected to the Control Room. The camera frames the area where there are people (who will have signed a waiver with respect to GDPR obligations), while the sensor detects the number (density) of people within a 50m radius.
3	A person at the event site reports to the two local police officers already on site (they are part of the event patrol) a serious incident near the Event Area car park (car park in front of Latteria Svizzera).
4	The two police officers take their tablet (or smartphone) already connected to the MCR and verbally communicate the emergency status describing the following situation: two cars have collided violently and are jammed into each other. One person is lying lifeless on the ground, while another is unconscious inside one of the cars whose door can no longer be opened (two dummies and two cars will be used in the measurement).
5	The 112 Centre asks officers to take photos and a video of the accident and upload them to the MCR.
6	The 118 Team (rescuers) present at the event, also connected to the MCR, will go to the scene to examine the vital parameters of the person lying inanimately on the ground and to provide him/her with first aid and provide voice information to the MCR.
7	The Central Unit 118 organizes the rescue by sending a second medical ambulance requested by the rescue unit on the scene.

8	The medical personnel in the ambulance on the way analyze the situation of the accident in the Data Room and request further video/images from the other 118 operators on the scene to analyze the state of the injured.
9	The Fire Station asks the police officers present to provide a video stream and detailed images with footage from different perspectives of the accident to better equip themselves. An officer takes the footage and uploads it to the MCR.
10	The Police Headquarters requests the activation of the drone (which will not fly, only framing people who have signed the release) to monitor the situation from above to identify further potential anomalies and verify the accessibility of the adjacent streets. The drone sends a streaming video directly to the MCR.
11	The fire brigade, police and ambulances go to their respective Individual Rooms to coordinate their respective modes of intervention.
12	The first to arrive at the scene of the incident are the two police officers of the second patrol who, on route, talk to their colleagues and to the police station in the MCR's private police room to coordinate.
13	The measurement closes with the firemen opening the car door and extracting the injured man who is transported in the medical ambulance together with the second injured man, the police officers arriving by relieving the first officers and fencing off the accident area.

The trial agenda is presented in Table 30. The event began with a welcome speech by the Head of the Turin Police, who attended alongside the Vice-Prefect. Staff from the company Aventura Urbana recorded the entire event, creating media material for dissemination across web platforms and social networks. The agenda also included a two-hour training session on the use of the devices.

Table 30. Agenda of Trial 5.1.

Time	Agenda of Trial 5.1 on 15/10/2024
09h30	Opening (project leader, authority, etc)
10h00	Introduction of TrialsNet and UC in auditorium of Talent Garden
10h30	Training on use of devices
12h30	Quick lunch offered
13h30	Start of trial in park with KPI measurement
15h00	Back to auditorium for KVI questionnaire
16h30	End of Trial

3.6.1.3 Trial execution and results

The trial took place on 15 October 2024 in Turin, partly in the Talent Garden Building and partly in the Park of Valentino, which are at walking distance one from the other.

The participants were 21 agents from four security forces, namely Police, Ambulance, Firefighters, and Civil Protection. Many of the agents were the same ones who participated in the two Design Thinking + sessions in May 2023 and February 2024. They all signed release forms regarding their participation in the exercise and the use of video/photos in dissemination material, which were reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the Turin Municipality. The trial followed the planned scenario with only minor deviations.

The devices that were used in the trial were the following:

- 4 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the control room operators).
- 8 5G tablets, for the agents onsite to communicate and upload images/sounds/videos.

- 2 5G smartphones, one for uploading images from the drone and the other to take KPI measurements onsite.
- 1 streaming video camera onsite
- 1 DJI drone with streaming camera (it was just manually held because of GDPR constraints),
- A box with people counting sensors onsite.
- 2 5G CPE at the Talent Garden

Selected pictures of the Trial 5.1 are provided in Figure 57.

Figure 57. Selected pictures of Trial 5.1.

The setup parameters of the network and the trial summary are illustrated in Table 31 and Table 32.

Table 31. Trial setup parameters for Trial 5.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR R.15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	massive MIMO (mMIMO)
Duplex mode	TDD
Device type	Smartphones and Tablets
Device number	19
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	commercial

Table 32. Trial summary for Trial 5.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	5.1
Trial setup ID	Trial
Facility/Site	Parco del Valentino, Latteria Svizzera
Objective	To check the functionality of the App and the mobile network.
Description	18 persons, with mobile devices
Executed by	M. Mazzaglia, A. Basso, G. Caratti
Components involved	mobile devices, drone and sensors outdoor and VR headsets and CPEs indoor
Targeted KPIs	Aggregate Downlink (KPI#03) Aggregate Uplink (KPI#04) Latency (KPI#8) System Availability (KPI#17)
Measurement tools	Speed-test Ookla, Packet Capture app (PCAP)

KPIs

The 5G network functioned well during the trial allowing to perform the scenario that was envisaged. In line with the planning, the following KPI have been measured during the trial using an additional smartphone with a PCAP application measuring network traffic [25]. The KPI average values are shown in Table 35.

Table 33. Measured KPIs for Trial 5.1.

Measurements ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
5.1_Trial_1	KPI#01: 1 Mbps KPI#02: 1 Mbps KPI#03: 12 Mbps KPI#04: 20 Mbps KPI#8: 100 ms KPI#17 (VR): 98% KPI#17 (Tablets): 98%	KPI#01: 10 Mbps KPI#02: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 35 Mbps KPI#04: 35 Mbps KPI#08: 30 ms KPI#17: 98% KPI#17: 75%	Only KPI#17 (for tablets) was not validated, due to the complexity of using tablets in emergency situations

KVIs

The selected KVIs were measured through the questionnaires distributed to the agents after the trials. Their average values are presented in Figure 58 while Figure 59 distinguishes the average value from those agents who remained in the control room (with helmets) and those who went to the emergency site.

Figure 58. Initial Average Values of KVIs for Trial 5.1.

Figure 59. Average Values of KVIs for Trial 5.1 with Distinction of Function.

Since most agents confirmed the app's usefulness in enhancing inter-agency communication and improving intervention efficiency, the lower KVI scores given by field agents might be attributed to the complexity of using a tablet during emergencies, which requires both hands and is less practical than bodycams. Consequently, agents were asked to complete a new online questionnaire (see Table 34). The analysis of the new questionnaire showed an average appreciation of the experience of 76% beyond the target of 70%.

Table 34. New questionnaire sent online after the Trial 5.1.

My opinion on the proposed technology assuming the suggestions from the trial are adopted	Score
I am interested and would adopt it once integrated to existing tools	76% (13 agents)
I am interested but would not adopt it	18% (3 agents)
I am interested but only marginally	6% (1 agent)

After all participants completed the KVI questionnaires, they were also invited to share comments on their experience and suggestions for improvement, which are compiled in Table 35. Although the app's design was developed based on feedback from agents during the Design Thinking+ process, the trial revealed that initial ideas often differ from practical experience.

Table 35. Suggestions from participants in Trial 5.1.

Suggestions	
1	App should not replace the present radio communication tools, but add to them additional functionality for sharing data, images and communications.
2	Operations performed in the current App configuration are too cumbersome and complex for their use in the field.
3	To avoid overlapping audio/video in the common rooms, it is suggested to only allow station operators (helmeted coordinators), to access the common rooms, as well as to limit the presence of field agents to their private rooms. It will be the task of the coordinators to share data, videos and voice messages with both their own agents and the coordinators of other agencies by posting them in the relevant rooms and informing them verbally.
4	The use of tablets in the field will only be appropriate when these are already provided, such as in the case of medical ambulances where tablets are currently used to transmit medical information and data.
5	The use of Bodycams is considered a preferable solution to Tablets, as they leave the operators' hands free by transferring videos to the App independently when required.
6	The use of a drone with geolocation is paramount also to help teams identify the best route to the intervention site.

4 Considerations on Use Cases deployment

For the transition from trial activities to the goal of widespread commercial service deployment, a critical re-evaluation of the use cases results becomes imperative. While the current 5G NSA and 5G SA networks have fulfilled the immediate performance requirements in the considered trial environments – in some cases with optimized setups, limited concurrent users and/or devices, or specific equipment configurations – the further challenge is scaling these solutions to meet the pervasive demands of a smart city.

This section delves into the main aspects that underpin the commercial viability of the WP3 use cases, identifying any inherent limitations or necessary improvements that transcend the capabilities of current 5G technology. Based on the robust trial results, a scalability evaluation is done for each use case. This will facilitate the identification of precise performance enhancements and functional advancements that 6G should deliver to support a seamless, city-wide service.

4.1 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Madrid)

Moving beyond the initial successful trials, this section critically examines the journey of the Smart Crowd Monitoring system in Madrid towards widespread commercial deployment, highlighting key performance and functional considerations for 6G.

4.1.1 Performance requirements

Low latency is a particularly important issue for remote control of robotic platforms, which is the key feature of the solution. The trial had successful results, always allowing operators to remote control robots with minimal delay (>12ms latency). However, although the fixed LiDAR sensor can be operated with 12ms latency without major issues, lower latency levels (below 10ms) would be a requirement for a mobile LiDAR. 6G should be able to provide this lowered latency which would allow for the widespread installation of mobile sensors.

Adequate throughput is another key requirement of the solution. The solution architecture tasked one of the two CPEs (CPE1) to manage DL throughput, and another one to manage Uplink (UL) throughput (CPE2). During the trial itself, throughput requirements have been met, in general, for the Use Case deployment. The only exception are the values for DL Aggregate Throughput (KPI#03) (200Mbps) which were lower during the trial implementation (148Mbps), however, no significant performance issues were observed during the implementation. Supporting higher throughputs, 6G should be able to support higher traffic (1Gbps) for more complex security systems using a variety of sensors.

4.1.2 Network Functionalities

No new network functionalities were envisaged for this use case. However, 6G is expected to significantly enhance network functionalities by ensuring ultra-low latency below 10ms, a critical enabler for the widespread deployment of mobile LiDAR sensors, while also supporting substantially higher throughput levels of up to 1Gbps. These advancements would allow for more complex and reliable security and monitoring systems, capable of integrating a variety of sensors and handling increased traffic demands, thus moving beyond the limitations observed during the current trial phase.

4.1.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

B5G technology could support security devices to perform without access to optical fibre connection, enabling the implementation of automatized security systems in isolated areas. However, in the process of preparation and implementation of the UC1 Madrid trial, the coverage capacity of the millimetric band was identified as a limitation to deployment in bigger areas, which becomes a limitation factor for the implementation of this technology in wider areas, such as critical infrastructures, which could greatly benefit from B5G/6G technology for monitorization and security.

Consistent service availability is a key necessary feature for remote security deployment, since lack thereof can leave critical premises in a vulnerable state. Service availability for the duration of the UC1 Madrid trial was 100%, meeting this requirement with success; however, improvements are due, given the aforementioned limitations for coverage and throughput which could greatly affect service availability in larger areas. Ensuring

seamless, high-capacity connectivity for all devices is the key to guarantee the quality of the security deployment.

4.1.4 Other aspects

AI lab tests showcase a tendency of the systems used to generate false positives when environmental changes happen. Further lab tests and simulations in client premises would be necessary to measure KPIs, as well as the explorations of other newly developed solutions. Moreover, it will be necessary to train operators on the functioning of the algorithms and ensure that human supervision of the AI detection systems is meeting the standards promoted by the EU Artificial Intelligence Act. It's also worth noting that certain technologies are not yet prepared to connect to B5G/6G networks, which constitutes a shortcoming for the implementation of this solution. This is the case with LIDARs, that were designed to process information on the edge due to pre-5G communication limitations instead of using the cloud. This has an effect on the solution's architecture which can affect scalability.

4.1.5 Final observations

B5G connection provided by Ericsson's CPEs in the trial provided the necessary capacity to support the traffic of the selected security equipment, including two cameras, three robots and one LiDAR; and their remote control from an iSOC position with minimal latency. Network performance complies with most of the necessary KPIs for adequate operation of these devices, but it still runs into some problems when it comes to operating the LiDAR, caused by the device's heavy traffic and configuration limitations. Limited coverage of millimetric band 5G can be of difficult implementation in large areas, hence generating a need to develop 6G solutions to address this issue. AI tests in the laboratory have also provided insights into shortcomings of the technology and the need to improve its application.

In conclusion, the path to commercializing a B5G/6G solution requires improvements mainly in the area of coverage and, in some cases, performance as well. Conducting further pilot programs within client facilities to refine the offering is also a necessary step. It is essential to engage the end clients in this process to ensure their expectations and needs are thoroughly addressed.

4.2 UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Iasi)

The evolution of the deployment from an NSA configuration in December 2024 to a SA architecture in April 2025 has significantly enhanced the system's capabilities, particularly in achieving lower latencies through a dedicated URLLC slice. Software enhancements, including advanced AI models for object detection and density analytics, have further refined the application's functionality. While current measurements indicate the fulfillment of initial use case requirements, the trials have also brought to light key scalability challenges that necessitate further consideration for commercial service deployment.

4.2.1 Performance requirements

Based on the trials, the smart crowd monitoring system shows strong performance, especially with the 5G SA deployment. Downlink throughput reached 512 Mbps and uplink 58.6 Mbps (KPI#05 & KPI#06), meeting the 500/50 Mbps targets. Application-level throughput (KPI#01) ranged from 13.6 Mbps for a single camera to 62.7 Mbps for 13 cameras at 2592x1944@25FPS, H265. While adequate for the current setup, higher throughput will be needed for commercial deployments with over 100 cameras per site, requiring 6G uplinks above 1 Gbps to handle high-resolution streams.

Round-trip latency including video processing (KPI#08) ranged 148–248 ms, below the 500 ms target. Video processing latency remains dependent on server hardware, suggesting 6G should target sub-10 ms network latency to reduce computational overhead and enable near-instantaneous anomaly detection. Current 5G coverage spans Ștefan cel Mare Boulevard, but 6G must provide seamless, high-capacity coverage across larger urban areas, including integration with indoor monitoring systems.

4.2.2 Network functionalities

The trials confirmed that network functionalities are critical for smart crowd monitoring and highlighted areas where 6G could advance performance. The current 5G SA setup uses a dedicated URLLC slice effectively, but

scalability is limited with increasing numbers of cameras and higher-resolution streams. 6G should provide dynamic resource allocation and real-time self-optimizing network management, enabling seamless support for hundreds or thousands of concurrent streams per site coverage area without manual intervention.

Video processing latency depends on server hardware, indicating the need for 6G to support intelligent computational load distribution across edge and cloud resources to minimize delays. While current reliability is 100% (KPI#16 & KPI#17) on limited areas, 6G should offer self-healing and predictive maintenance for city-wide deployments. Advanced network slicing would allow concurrent URLLC, mMTC, and eMBB services with isolated performance guarantees. Finally, AI-driven orchestration is needed to automate deployment, monitoring, and scaling of complex multi-component applications, reducing operational overhead and supporting rapid expansion.

4.2.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The current infrastructure provides a solid foundation, but city-wide scalability requires further 6G considerations. Coverage must extend beyond a single boulevard to dense urban areas, ensuring seamless connectivity for all cameras and devices through a higher density of small cells and integrated access/backhaul solutions. Edge and cloud computing, successfully integrated at the Iași 5G Lab, should be extended closer to data sources at pole or street furniture level to reduce latency, improve privacy, and minimize backhaul traffic.

Data management currently relies on real-time processing with metadata storage in PostgreSQL. For 6G, hybrid strategies such as federated learning and secure distributed ledgers could enhance analytics, model training, and data integrity. Integration with emerging technologies—including DTs, AI/ML frameworks, and possibly quantum computing—requires standardized APIs and interfaces for seamless interoperability with city management platforms, emergency services, and other smart city systems.

4.2.4 Other aspects

Beyond technical functionalities, several aspects are crucial for commercialization and acceptance of smart crowd monitoring system. Security relies on IPsec VPNs and privacy measures, but 6G must integrate advanced encryption, strong authentication, AI-based threat detection, and protection of AI models from attacks. AI accuracy is central, requiring continuous improvement in object detection and density analytics, supported by diverse datasets and federated learning for model updates.

Extensive measurements under varied real-world conditions is needed, including stress testing, E2E performance validation, and operator acceptance. Energy efficiency must be prioritized across devices, network layers, and AI inference to manage increased infrastructure load sustainably. Finally, stakeholder engagement—including municipal authorities, law enforcement, privacy advocates, and the public—is essential to ensure compliance, societal acceptance, and trust in the system.

4.2.5 Final observations

This use case in Iași successfully demonstrated the transformative potential of 5G, particularly with the transition to 5G SA, in enabling real-time video analytics for urban safety. The achievement of low latency and robust throughput within the trial scope is commendable. However, the identified challenges, particularly concerning scalability, emphasize the critical role of 6G in facilitating a full-scale commercial service deployment.

For 6G, the key requirements stemming from this use case are:

- **Massive Uplink Capacity:** To support at least 100 of high-resolution cameras simultaneously per site, 6G must deliver sustained more than 10 Gbps uplink capabilities at the cell level.
- **Ultra-Low Latency:** Pushing network latency to sub 10 ms will further enhance the responsiveness of real-time analytics and enable immediate action in critical situations.
- **Pervasive and Intelligent Edge Computing:** A highly distributed and dynamically managed edge computing architecture is essential to process vast amounts of video data close to the source, minimizing backhaul and optimizing latency.
- **Advanced AI-driven Network Orchestration and Resource Management:** 6G must intrinsically support AI-powered automation for dynamic resource allocation, load balancing, and self-healing, ensuring the network can adapt to varying demands and maintain high performance.

- **Enhanced Security and Privacy by Design:** Given the sensitive nature of crowd monitoring, 6G must offer unparalleled security features, including robust data protection and privacy-preserving AI techniques.

By addressing these core aspects, 6G will not only enable the seamless commercial deployment of advanced smart crowd monitoring systems but also unlock a new generation of intelligent city services that are more responsive, reliable, and secure. The current trials serve as a vital foundation for defining the future capabilities that 6G must deliver to realize the full vision of smart and safe urban environments.

4.3 UC2: Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management

This section analyzes the output of the UC2 from its trial phase to the requirements for full commercial service deployment.

4.3.1 Performance requirements

The UC2 trials at AIA and Technopolis confirmed that remote inspection through 5G-connected AMRs and real-time AI analytics requires uplink throughput of at least 30 Mbps, as compressed streams reduce precision and raw video streaming peaked close to 100 Mbps. Teleoperation depends on low-latency communication, with trials showing that RTT values below 50 ms ensure responsiveness, while delays beyond 100 ms begin to degrade control. Stability is equally critical, as jitter greater than 15 ms during simultaneous video and MQTT traffic negatively impacted control accuracy. These results highlight that achieving stable uplinks and latencies consistently below 50 ms is essential for seamless teleoperation and will be a fundamental driver for the tighter performance guarantees expected in 6G networks.

4.3.2 Network functionalities

Enabling proactive public infrastructure asset management requires advanced network functionalities to manage real-time and high-throughput conditions effectively. Trials demonstrated that latency increases under raw video streaming can be mitigated through dynamic resource allocation and edge processing, while fault tolerance and fallback mechanisms are necessary to maintain continuity during uplink drops or jitter spikes. Computational load distribution between robots, edge, and cloud proved essential for preserving responsiveness, supported by orchestration strategies that adapt to changing network conditions. Network slicing emerged as a critical enabler, allowing traffic isolation between control, video, and analytics streams to prevent mutual interference, while enhanced reliability and scalability will be needed for multi-robot deployments. These functionalities establish the blueprint for 6G to provide deterministic performance, stronger QoS, and highly adaptable slicing for large-scale autonomous systems.

4.3.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

Field trials emphasized the importance of reliable 5G connectivity for teleoperation and video streaming, with network coverage generally sufficient but subject to occasional degradation due to obstacles or interference, reinforcing the need for optimized deployment strategies such as private networks or signal boosters. A hybrid computing approach was implemented, combining edge-based video and AI processing for latency reduction with cloud-based data storage and large-scale analysis through the wi.MOVE platform, ensuring responsiveness and scalability. The robotic platforms successfully integrated 5G modules, LiDAR, depth cameras, and GPS/IMU systems through standardized interfaces, while secure cloud-based storage and logging enabled structured monitoring and post-analysis. Integration with operational tools at AIA and DAEM confirmed the interoperability of the system, even in environments with mixed legacy and modern technologies. These deployment experiences underline the role of 6G in supporting large-scale, heterogeneous infrastructure systems through seamless integration of connectivity, edge intelligence, and cloud resources.

4.3.4 Other aspects

Throughout the trials, secure data transmission and restricted access protocols were strictly enforced, giving users confidence in the system's resilience against cyber threats. The AI model for infrastructure damage detection delivered reliable, real-time classifications of road and pavement issues, validated both in controlled and live conditions, while the refined wi.MOVE interface allowed operators with minimal training to manage

inspections effectively. Users appreciated the real-time visual feedback from AI analytics combined with live camera feeds, which strengthened trust in remote operations and improved usability. Moreover, the sustainability benefits were clear, with reduced physical site visits leading to lower operational costs and emissions, while active engagement with stakeholders ensured alignment with operational requirements. These findings reinforce that 6G must integrate secure, AI-driven, and user-centric features to scale sustainable infrastructure monitoring to urban and regional levels.

4.3.5 Final observations

The trials demonstrated the feasibility of combining 5G-enabled robotics and AI-based analytics for proactive infrastructure monitoring, validating key aspects such as data security, real-time accuracy, and intuitive usability in operational environments. Stable connectivity and low-latency streaming were confirmed as essential for remote operations, setting the foundation for 6G enhancements in ultra-reliable communication, native AI integration, and advanced edge intelligence. With these advancements, future networks will enable responsive, scalable, and automated monitoring systems capable of supporting complex urban infrastructures at scale. The trial outcomes confirm that this approach can lead to smarter, safer, and more efficient city operations, while clearly positioning 6G as the technology to unlock the full potential of large-scale digital infrastructure management.

4.4 UC3: Autonomous APRON

This section explores the transition of the UC3 from a successful trial at AIA to a comprehensive commercial solution, detailing the performance and functional enhancements that future 6G networks will be essential in delivering.

4.4.1 Performance requirements

The UC3 trial confirmed that 5G can sustain autonomous baggage transport under controlled conditions, with uplink throughput, downlink throughput, latency, and service reliability within acceptable thresholds. Uplink throughput of at least 5 Mbps per AGV proved sufficient for stable video and telemetry, while downlink needs were lower at ~2 Mbps for command delivery and diagnostics. RTT values of 20–30 ms enabled responsive control, though peaks above 40 ms were observed, emphasizing the need for strict ≤ 30 ms performance at scale. Jitter tolerance was around 10 ms, but larger fluctuations could disrupt safety-critical navigation when multiple AGVs operate simultaneously. In large-scale deployments, higher-resolution video streams, concurrent AI-driven analytics, and multi-AGV coordination will demand uplinks closer to 20–50 Mbps per device, with consistent jitter below 1 ms for teleoperation. These requirements align with 6G capabilities such as URLLC at scale, deterministic latency guarantees, and adaptive bandwidth allocation across hundreds of devices to ensure safe and efficient airport-wide operations.

4.4.2 Network functionalities

While 5G proved adequate for a single AGV, scaled deployments require more advanced functionalities. Fault tolerance during handovers is crucial, as even short connectivity losses could halt operations; 6G envisions multi-link and multi-operator connectivity to provide seamless session continuity. Dynamic resource allocation will need to evolve into AI-driven, predictive orchestration that adapts network priorities in real time, ensuring critical video and navigation data always receive guaranteed resources. Edge computing and network slicing, only tested conceptually during UC3, will need to be native in 6G to support latency below 10 ms for autonomous navigation and isolation of control, video, and analytics slices. Additionally, 6G will need to support DT synchronization at scale, ensuring low-latency data exchange across multiple AGVs and airport systems. These functionalities point toward a future where 6G provides not only higher performance but also self-adaptive orchestration and resilience for mission-critical automation.

4.4.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The trial benefited from dedicated coverage, but full deployment requires uniform connectivity across baggage halls, aprons, and open-air zones, which is challenging due to interference and obstructions. 6G will need to provide ubiquitous coverage through cell-free massive MIMO for non-line-of-sight areas, and multi-band operation across multiple frequency bands. Integration of multiple devices and vendors requires flexible interfaces,

and 6G's native interoperability frameworks will be essential to harmonize AGVs, IoT sensors, and airport management systems. Edge intelligence will need to handle real-time video analytics and navigation decisions at scale, requiring distributed edge-cloud hierarchies with sub 10 ms coordination. Finally, data management systems must evolve to manage petabyte-scale datasets from thousands of devices with privacy-preserving distributed storage and federated learning. These enhancements show that 6G infrastructure will be foundational for scalable airport logistics.

4.4.4 Other aspects

Security was a strong aspect of the trial, but scaling deployments will introduce higher exposure to cyber threats. 6G must embed zero-trust security architectures, quantum-resistant encryption, and hardware-level identity management to ensure robust protection of critical airport assets. AI algorithms for route optimization and anomaly detection will need real-time learning at the edge, supported by 6G's integration of native AI/ML frameworks within the network control plane. From a user perspective, future systems will require adaptive interfaces, with personalized dashboards driven by context-aware AI assistants to support different operator roles. Sustainability is also critical, and 6G will need to support energy-efficient connectivity, including wake-up radios for AGVs and green edge processing, to minimize power usage across large fleets. These aspects show that 6G is not only about performance, but also about enabling secure, adaptive, and energy-conscious operations at scale.

4.4.5 Final observations

The UC3 trial at Athens International Airport successfully validated autonomous baggage handling with 5G, but scaling to airport-wide operations will introduce challenges of density, mobility, and resilience beyond current capabilities. Future 6G networks will need to deliver deterministic latency below 10 ms, jitter within 1 ms, multi-gigabit throughput per AGV for advanced sensing, and near-100% service availability. Key enablers will include AI-native orchestration, intelligent network slicing, multi-connectivity for seamless handovers, RIS-assisted coverage, and pervasive edge intelligence. These capabilities will ensure that autonomous baggage handling evolves from controlled pilots to fully operational airport systems. In conclusion, UC3 demonstrates feasibility with 5G, while 6G will provide the foundation for scaling this use case into a resilient, secure, and sustainable backbone of future airport logistics.

4.5 UC4: Smart Traffic Management

While the UC4 trial outcomes confirm the immediate viability of the solution, a critical examination of scalability and future requirements is essential for a truly comprehensive and commercially viable deployment.

4.5.1 Performance requirements

UC4 trials show that the smart traffic management system performs well under current conditions, particularly with 5G SA. Data throughput in May 2025 reached 220 Mbps downlink and 83.5 Mbps uplink, exceeding target requirements of 200 Mbps and 50 Mbps, respectively. At the application layer, a single camera (2688x1512@25FPS) produced 11.3 Mbps uplink, while six cameras at the same resolution generated 67.6 Mbps. Although sufficient for the current setup, city-wide deployments with dozens of intersections will require significantly higher aggregate uplink capacity, with 6G targeting more than 10 Gbps per cell to handle concurrent high-resolution streams without bottlenecks.

Latency was improved, with end-to-end delay at 20 ms, below the 50 ms target. Round-trip latency, including edge processing, ranged from 216 ms for one camera to 316 ms for six cameras, showing that processing is the main bottleneck. For city-scale deployments, 6G should reduce network latency to sub-millisecond levels to enable instantaneous traffic adjustments and AI-driven decisions. Current coverage spans the Podu Roş Intersection, but 6G must provide seamless, high-capacity coverage across larger urban areas.

4.5.2 Network functionalities

The trials highlighted the critical role of network functionalities in advanced traffic management and areas where 6G can improve performance. The current 5G SA slice works effectively, but scaling to dozens of intersections requires AI-driven dynamic resource allocation to optimize network performance during peak traffic.

Latency dependence on server hardware shows the need for distributed computational load management. 6G should enable real-time offloading and load balancing across edge and cloud nodes, maintaining low latency as camera numbers and analytics complexity grow. Reliability must be enhanced with self-healing and predictive maintenance, ensuring uninterrupted service. Future 6G networks should offer flexible, granular slicing for URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC, while AI-driven orchestration automates deployment, configuration, monitoring, and scaling, reducing operational overhead and adapting to evolving urban needs.

4.5.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The Podu Roş infrastructure has proven effective for trialing, but city-wide commercial deployment requires expanded 6G capabilities. Widespread coverage across Iaşi will need high-density networks with small cells and advanced integrated access and backhaul to handle dense buildings, high traffic, and numerous cameras.

Edge and distributed cloud computing will be essential, pushing processing closer to data sources, such as street furniture or traffic poles, to reduce latency, improve privacy, and limit backhaul traffic. For data management, 6G should support hybrid strategies, including federated learning on edge-processed video and secure distributed ledger technologies, ensuring efficient AI model training, privacy, and metadata integrity.

4.5.4 Other aspects

Beyond the core technical infrastructure, several factors are key for the successful deployment and societal acceptance of the smart traffic management system. Security must be integrated at every layer of the network and application architecture. While the current system uses IPsec VPN tunnels and image blurring to preserve privacy, 6G will require advanced encryption, strong authentication for devices and users, AI-driven threat detection, and resilience against sophisticated cyber-physical attacks.

Equally important is the continuous optimization of AI models. The system's effectiveness depends on accurate object detection and traffic analysis, which must adapt to diverse environmental conditions, varying traffic patterns, and subtle anomalies. Finally, sustainability and energy efficiency are crucial as deployments scale. 6G should ensure low power consumption through efficient device designs, intelligent network-level power management, and optimized edge AI processing, minimizing the overall energy footprint.

4.5.5 Final observations

The UC4 has compellingly demonstrated the transformative potential of B5G, particularly with the transition to 5G SA, in enabling real-time video analytics for enhancing urban safety and flow. However, the identified challenges, notably concerning the computational overhead and scalability for broader city-wide adoption, underscore the indispensable role of 6G in realizing a comprehensive commercial service deployment.

For 6G, the critical mandates emerging from this use case are:

- **Massive Uplink Bandwidth:** To effectively support a pervasive network of ultra-high-resolution cameras, 6G must deliver aggregate more than 10 Gigabit per second uplink capabilities at the cell level.
- **Near-Instantaneous Latency:** Driving network latency to true sub-millisecond levels will dramatically enhance the responsiveness of real-time analytics, enabling immediate intervention and predictive traffic management.
- **Intelligent, Pervasive Edge Compute:** A highly distributed and dynamically managed edge computing architecture is essential to efficiently process vast volumes of video data close to its source, minimizing backhaul reliance and optimizing latency.
- **Autonomous AI-Driven Network Orchestration:** 6G must inherently support AI-powered automation for dynamic resource allocation, intelligent load balancing, and self-healing, ensuring the network can seamlessly adapt to ever-changing traffic demands and maintain peak performance.
- **Enhanced Security and Privacy Embedded by Design:** Given the sensitive nature of traffic monitoring, 6G must offer unparalleled, intrinsically designed security features, including robust data protection and privacy-preserving AI techniques.

By comprehensively addressing these core requirements, 6G will not only enable the seamless commercial deployment of advanced smart traffic management systems but also unlock a new generation of intelligent urban services that are more responsive, reliable, and fundamentally secure.

4.6 UC5: Control Room in Metaverse

This trial, which mobilized 18 agents from different safety and security forces, was successful regarding both the KPI and KVI results. The main considerations are reported below.

4.6.1 Performance requirements

During the trial, several key network performance indicators were established and subsequently measured in order to evaluate system performance.

During the trial, several key network performance indicators were established and measured to evaluate system behavior under realistic operating conditions. The downlink aggregated throughput requirement of 12 Mbps was exceeded, with an average of 35 Mbps recorded. This margin indicates that the system could comfortably support additional VR headsets and tablets beyond the 12 devices used in the trial. However, scalability considerations highlight that during a massive commercial deployment, the initial model loading phase could become a critical performance bottleneck, as each new participant's connection increases bandwidth demands linearly. For a fully operational UC5 deployment with hundreds of concurrent users, careful dimensioning of edge servers and optimized content delivery (e.g., progressive loading, edge caching) will be necessary to maintain the same level of performance and avoid latency spikes.

The uplink throughput performance also achieved 35 Mbps, exceeding the required 20 Mbps and demonstrating robust support for real-time video streaming from multiple sources. Nonetheless, in a large-scale deployment, additional uplink traffic from numerous drones, cameras, and user devices would create contention and require intelligent network slicing and dynamic bandwidth allocation to ensure quality of service for critical video streams. Latency performance was strong, with a measured round-trip time of 30 ms, well within the 50 ms target. At scale, maintaining this low-latency performance will require MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing) integration and efficient traffic prioritization, particularly during simultaneous user joins and video conferencing events.

System availability was 98 % indoors but fell to 75 % outdoors due to coverage limitations, resulting in an average of 86.5 %. While acceptable for a controlled trial, in real-life emergency deployments this gap would need to be addressed through enhanced outdoor coverage, potentially using dedicated private 5G/6G infrastructure or temporary network extensions (e.g., deployable cells). Overall, the results demonstrate that the trialed system architecture is capable of delivering the required performance for small-to-medium-scale deployments, and with 6G's expected higher throughput, sub-10 ms latency, and native support for massive XR traffic, a full-scale UC5 deployment should achieve smooth multi-user operation with minimal service degradation — provided that scalability measures such as edge offloading and optimized content distribution are implemented.

4.6.2 Network functionalities

Although WebRTC's peer-to-peer architecture helps offload multimedia traffic from the central Hubs server by routing it directly between users, it highlights the importance of network-level coordination and resource management. Each new participant joining a virtual room triggers signaling exchanges, session establishment, and model-loading requests, which must be efficiently orchestrated by the network to avoid congestion. This behavior underlines the role of intelligent network functions such as session admission control, dynamic bandwidth allocation, and edge caching, which become critical as the number of participants grows and traffic patterns fluctuate.

In dense, multi-user scenarios where simultaneous high-data-rate services are required—such as collaborative VR, live video feeds, and drone telemetry—network orchestration must guarantee quality of service through prioritization and isolation mechanisms. Network features like network slicing and MEC can ensure that mission-critical services remain unaffected by non-critical traffic bursts. Additionally, automated network monitoring and AI-driven traffic steering can detect load imbalances and reconfigure resources in real time to sustain service continuity.

For UC5 emergency-response use cases, network functionality must go beyond throughput and latency targets to ensure reliability and resilience. This involves seamless mobility support for field agents, redundancy mechanisms for uninterrupted connectivity, and deterministic data delivery for time-sensitive communications. These functionalities are essential for guaranteeing continuous situational awareness, enabling coordinated response

actions, and supporting future large-scale deployments where many users and devices interact simultaneously in a shared virtual environment.

4.6.3 Infrastructure deployment aspects

The UC5 trial was carried out in a designated trial area characterized by relatively weak 5G connectivity. For effective real-world deployment, it is crucial to ensure consistent and robust 5G coverage across all potential emergency zones. Reliable network infrastructure is a foundational requirement for supporting critical communication and real-time data exchange in high-stakes environments.

A key component of the system involves the integration of diverse edge devices—including sensors, cameras, and wearable technology—which must communicate seamlessly via the metaverse platform. This demands not only stable network performance but also low-latency, high-bandwidth cloud-to-edge communication to support real-time situational awareness and decision-making.

Interoperability between hardware from different manufacturers presents another challenge. As the metaverse platform incorporates devices from various brands, ensuring cross-device compatibility is essential to maintain a cohesive and functional system.

Additionally, the platform must offer seamless integration with existing security systems and institutional databases, such as those operated by law enforcement agencies, emergency services, and healthcare providers. Support for proprietary communication protocols and legacy systems will be necessary to enable smooth data exchange and collaborative response efforts.

Scalable data management is also critical. The platform must be capable of handling both real-time and historical data generated by a growing number of connected devices. This includes efficient storage, retrieval, and analysis, all while adhering to stringent data privacy, protection, and retention policies.

4.6.4 Other aspects

The trial was deemed successful, with an overall satisfaction rate exceeding 70%. However, one key drawback reported by agents at the emergency site was the need to use tablets for communication, which limited their ability to operate hands-free. In future implementations, this limitation could be addressed by incorporating wearable devices—such as bodycams or smart glasses—that enable hands-free interaction and more seamless communication.

In addition, two critical aspects were not covered by the current platform but could be effectively addressed through future research and innovation efforts:

- **Cybersecurity:** Currently, the platform is secured only by a password, which is insufficient for an application that may be used in high-risk emergency scenarios, including those involving terrorism. A dedicated security module should be developed to enhance the platform's resilience. This could involve implementing strong encryption protocols, multi-factor authentication, and other advanced cybersecurity measures to ensure data integrity, confidentiality, and system reliability.
- **AI:** Integrating AI capabilities would significantly enhance the platform's functionality. AI could be used to automatically monitor video streams for anomalies—such as overcrowding, the presence of weapons, or suspicious materials—and to perform facial recognition to identify potential threats. Additionally, AI could be employed to simulate and generate emergency scenarios, such as optimized escape routes or response strategies, to support decision-making in real time.

Lastly, ethical considerations must remain at the forefront, especially in the context of European regulations. Strict compliance with frameworks such as the GDPR and the forthcoming EU AI Act is imperative. These regulations govern not only data handling practices but also the responsible development and deployment of AI-driven technologies, ensuring transparency, accountability, and protection of individual rights.

4.6.5 Final observations

The trial was successful from both a KPI and KVI standpoint, except for system availability, which should ideally exceed 98% for mission-critical applications. During the trial, uplink and downlink data loads were significantly lower than anticipated. This was primarily due to agents on-site relying mainly on audio communication via their tablets, with minimal transmission of images or video. Their usage patterns were shaped by

existing standard operating procedures and some discomfort with the tablet devices. However, it is expected that the use of video - particularly through bodycams - will increase in future deployments. As a result, uplink and downlink loads are likely to be much higher than those observed in this trial.

Having highlighted the potential advantages of the next generation of mobile networks in terms of performances, the following additional considerations emerge regarding the commercial deployment of the developed solution.

Given the high sensitivity of emergency response operations, it is paramount to ensure the security of data, video streams, and information flows throughout all phases of operation. Protection via password alone is inadequate and does not align with the stringent security protocols typically enforced by public safety and law enforcement agencies.

The introduction of AI could significantly improve the management of the emergency by automatically detecting anomalies and predicting optimized scenarios. Although the introduction of network slicing could offer enhanced security and prioritization of communications, its implementation would likely necessitate a comprehensive redesign of the system architecture to allow for deployment within the proprietary infrastructure of these organizations. This would require close collaboration with local emergency services and significant investment in the development of a customized, secure solution tailored to their specific operational needs.

Despite these challenges, the system shows immediate potential for application in training scenarios. By incorporating the feedback provided by agents during the trial, the solution could be effectively deployed in controlled environments to support preparedness, coordination, and procedural training.

5 Additional Use Cases and trials from the Open Call

This section presents a comprehensive overview of the technical and operational aspects of the additional use cases of the Open Call sub-projects within the ITSS domain, structured through a series of detailed tables. The information reported here are based on the sub-projects Final Reports that will be included in the deliverable D7.3 being released in December 2025.

The additional trials span eleven distinct use cases, covering Options 1a, 1b, and 2, and involve several newly introduced sites, thereby extending the geographical and technological coverage of the experimentation campaign. Specifically, the new sites include Florence, Madrid, Turin, Iasi, Antwerp, Athens, Peania, and Patras, providing a diverse mix of urban, transport, and industrial settings. The use cases were deployed across multiple network configurations, including 5G standalone setups, edge computing platforms, and AI-enhanced orchestration frameworks, demonstrating the adaptability of the project solutions to real-world conditions. Trials were performed under Option 1a (SkyLink Vision, AI-PREMSET-MCX), Option 1b (MILESTONE, AdaptoFlow), and Option 2 (Connected Rails, 5GS3, CITY4ALL, ATOS, i-CNC, AI4RTC, Cities Without Barriers), thus covering a wide range of architectural alternatives and deployment models.

For each sub-project, the content begins with a description of the realted use case, outlining the system's purpose, the environment in which it operates, and the main technological components involved. Following this, the developed applications and technologies are explored, providing insight into the software and hardware solutions implemented, the communication technologies used, and how these elements are integrated within the system architecture. The trial activities are then described, highlighting the different phases of measurements, the locations where trials took place, the conditions under which the systems were operated, and the challenges faced during real-world validation. Subsequently, the outcomes of the KPIs validation are presented, offering quantitative data on important metrics such as latency, throughput, positioning accuracy, network coverage, and overall system reliability. In addition to technical performance, the outcomes of the KVI validation are detailed, capturing qualitative and quantitative feedback from stakeholders. Together, these tables provide a full picture of the entire process, from development and deployment to evaluation, revealing valuable insights into the performance and stakeholder perceptions of advanced 5G-enabled intelligent transport and surveillance solutions.

The section concludes with an integrated analysis of all sub-projects, identifying their collective contributions to 5G validation, common challenges across ITSS domain, and insights for future network development, particularly in the context of 6G.

5.1 Connected Rails

The Connected Rails use case demonstrates the integration of advanced positioning and communication technologies within an active urban tramway environment. As part of the project, real-world trial was conducted using Florence's operational tram system to validate both functional performance and stakeholder value.

Table 36. Connected Rails: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>In this use case, Tram 1013, part of the Florence tramway fleet operated by GEST, is used in regular revenue service operations. Hitachi Rail GTS, responsible for the maintenance of the entire tram fleet under an ongoing agreement with GEST, has deployed experimental systems onboard Tram 1013 as part of the CONNECTED RAILS project. Due to the unavailability of spare vehicles within the fleet, installation and tuning of onboard systems was minimally invasive and carried out without disrupting operational service.</p> <p>The tram has been equipped with the New Generation Autonomous Positioning system (NGAP), referred to as SYS-NGAP within the project context. SYS-NGAP represents an advanced onboard positioning solution that eliminates reliance on ground-based infrastructure, instead utilizing integrated sensors including Inertial Measurement Units (IMU), RADAR, and Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). The system achieves an estimated position accuracy below one meter, which marks a significant improvement over existing state-of-the-art technologies based primarily on ground sensors. SYS-NGAP is being further</p>

enhanced within the CONNECTED RAILS framework to incorporate additional functionalities beyond positioning.

In parallel, a secondary system identified as SYS-SDR has been installed and integrated with SYS-NGAP. SYS-SDR is tasked with capturing 5G signal measurements along the tramway line, predominantly Line T1. The collected 5G data is retrieved and subjected to post-processing in order to estimate tram positioning based on signal characteristics. These estimations are then compared against the baseline positioning data provided by SYS-NGAP for validation and performance analysis.

Additional enhancements to SYS-NGAP have been implemented to enable real-time evaluation of the 5G signal bandwidth delivered by a commercial network operator. This functionality allows assessment of 5G network availability and quality along operational tram routes, contributing to the overall analysis of communication-based services and positioning accuracy within the scope of the CONNECTED RAILS project.

Table 37. Connected Rails: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies

The 5G signal-based positioning system was developed to detect tram position when GNSS is not available. This system exploits a radio interface to capture the 5G SSB and extract useful 5G communication link information that are processed by a deep learning framework to detect tram position.

NGAP SW modules were enriched with Python scripts to analyze the commercial 5G services bandwidth and coverage.

The information relating to coverage considered that relevant measurements were made by equipment installed on tram 1013 which is obviously always moving along the railway which never change. Hence, the relevant figure is the percentage of the Line T1 (where TX/RX packets were not lost) rather than an area.

Sandbox environment has been developed using Minikube, which has allowed assessing the capabilities of Kubernetes policies to ensure the requirements of applications through prioritization of computational resources among applications.

Table 38. Connected Rails: Trial activity.

Trial activity

The trials of CONNECTED RAILS project were performed in the tramway system of Florence, specifically along the railway of T1 line where tram 1013 is normally in service.

Tram 1013 is a normal vehicle that Hitachi is allowed to use for hosting trial equipment for:

- Positioning system (NGAP)
- Obstacle detection (ODT)

As part of the Connected Rails project, the NGAP system was modified and integrated with the 5G signal collection system.

SYS-SDR is the system which can capture 5G signals present in the area travelled by tram 1013 (Line T1). Collected data were post-processed off-line to estimate the tram's position.

Hence, the Connected Rails project involved a single device installed on tram 1013 operating in revenue service.

A significant part of the trial work was the preparation, measurement and installation of such systems on board the tram. The vehicle operated, in fact, in active service and the availability for technical activities on the vehicle itself was always limited due to the priority of maintaining the vehicle in service.

Table 39. Connected Rails: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The KPI assessment during the field trials confirms that the deployed 5G system can support connected rail operations with good performance in key areas. Notably, the 5G-based positioning method achieved an average localization error of 8.3 meters, showing potential as a complementary solution to GNSS within the NGAP system.</p> <p>Network performance met expectations in terms of bandwidth and latency. Downlink throughput reached 253 Mbps (vs. 100 Mbps target), uplink 31 Mbps (target: 20 Mbps), and latency results were well within limits—33 ms for end-to-end and 20 ms one-way. These figures validate the 5G network’s suitability for real-time applications.</p> <p>Coverage and service continuity presented some challenges. The 98.5% network availability fell short of the 99.9% goal, largely due to coverage distribution along the T1 line. KPI#15, related to overall communication availability, was also unmet, with only 53% operational continuity due to uplink, downlink, and latency fluctuations.</p> <p>In summary, while throughput and latency KPIs were successfully validated, improvements in network coverage and reliability are needed to meet all operational performance targets.</p>

Table 40. Connected Rails: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>The evaluation of KVIs for the tramway use case focused on three major dimensions: societal, environmental, and economic impact. Responses were collected through structured questionnaires using a 1–5 Likert scale.</p> <p>From a societal perspective, the integration of autonomous capabilities into tram operations is perceived to enhance both service availability and safety. Respondents affirmed—scoring 4.7/5 on average—that increasing automation contributes to a more reliable and punctual service. Similarly, a score of 4.6/5 was recorded regarding the perception that autonomy will reduce the number of incidents involving trams, supporting safer transportation in mixed traffic scenarios.</p> <p>The environmental dimension highlighted strong expectations regarding energy efficiency and pollution reduction. Stakeholders rated the impact of 5G-based systems on energy saving at 4.5/5, and on pollution reduction at 4.4/5. These results reflect the system's potential to contribute to more sustainable urban mobility by optimizing tram cruising and minimizing idle time through precise positioning.</p> <p>From an economic standpoint, the deployment of a unified 5G communication infrastructure was seen as a valuable enabler of cost efficiency. The use of 5G to replace multiple legacy communication links (Wi-Fi and Fourth Generation- 4G) received a positive evaluation of 4.6/5 for its potential to lower both capital and operational expenditures. The perceived improvement in service quality and customer satisfaction scored 4.5/5, while the system’s contribution to increased infrastructure utilization was rated 4.3/5. The potential for accident reduction also scored well (4.4/5), reinforcing the broader impact of advanced positioning and sensing technologies.</p>

5.2 5GS3

The following section outlines the 5GS3 use case, a technology-driven solution designed to improve surveillance and response operations in critical infrastructure environments. It details how autonomous robotic platforms, supported by 5G/B5G connectivity and AI-based analytics, are deployed to enhance situational awareness and security - particularly within airport settings.

Table 41. 5GS3: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The 5GS3 use case is designed to enhance security surveillance within critical infrastructure environments, with a particular focus on airport scenarios. The solution revolves around the deployment of autonomous robotic platforms that operate over 5G and B5G networks to deliver advanced monitoring and response capabilities. These robots perform real-time patrolling of sensitive zones, continuously scanning for anomalies or unauthorized objects to ensure a high level of situational awareness.</p> <p>Live video feeds from the robots are transmitted via 5G to a centralized dashboard, enabling remote navigation and real-time operator control. The system integrates AI-based object detection and autonomous navigation technologies to minimize human intervention, reduce operational workload, and significantly improve response times during incidents.</p> <p>The communication backbone of the solution is built on low-latency, high-reliability 5G connectivity, leveraging both private and public infrastructures to maintain service continuity and responsiveness. Designed with scalability and adaptability in mind, the 5GS3 framework can be easily tailored to other high-security environments beyond airports, offering a modular and future-proof approach to intelligent surveillance.</p>

Table 42. 5GS3: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The 5GS3 solution brings together AI-based analytics, real-time communication, and autonomous navigation within a modular robotic surveillance platform tailored for critical infrastructure monitoring. At the core of the system is a comprehensive software and hardware architecture designed to ensure responsiveness, scalability, and operational reliability.</p> <p>The frontend is implemented as a React-based web application that allows operators to view live video feeds, interact with environmental maps, and control robotic units remotely. This interface is supported by a backend composed of microservices built using Node.js and Golang, which maintain persistent, low-latency communication with the robotic agents via WebSockets and Server-Sent Events (SSE).</p> <p>The robotic units themselves operate within a containerized ROS2 (Humble) environment, utilizing the Nav2 stack for waypoint-based autonomous navigation and real-time environmental mapping. AI-driven object detection is performed onboard using a lightweight implementation of YOLOv8n, optimized to run efficiently on edge devices with limited computational resources.</p> <p>All operational data—including telemetry, patrol activities, and incident records—is stored in a PostgreSQL database. The full system has been trialed over both private 5G infrastructure, using Open5GS with a CableFree gNB, and commercial 5G networks, confirming its capability to support real-time, low-latency robotic operations. Deployment and orchestration of all components are handled via Docker Compose, ensuring the platform remains portable, modular, and easy to scale or adapt across different deployment environments.</p>

Table 43. 5GS3: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The 5GS3 system was trialed through several stages, moving from internal checks to real-world deployment. First, initial tests were carried out in a controlled lab environment. These tests focused on verifying key system components such as navigation, connectivity, and object detection. Next, pre-trials took place at Citiwave's premises in Patra. Using their private experimental B5G network, the team worked on integrating the system, executing predefined waypoints, and evaluating detection performance.</p> <p>The final trial was conducted at AIA on April 16, 2025. During this phase, the system demonstrated real-time patrolling, anomaly detection, and collaboration between multiple robots. In the trial scenario, one</p>

robot patrolled the airport perimeter and detected an object placed near the fence. This detection triggered an alert and prompted a second robot to verify the situation.

Airport security personnel observed the system in operation and provided feedback through structured questionnaires. Throughout the trials, a centralized dashboard was used for monitoring and control, displaying live video feeds, alerts, and robot telemetry in real time.

Table 44. 5GS3: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The system's technical performance was thoroughly evaluated through measurements taken during both pre-trials and real trials, focusing on KPIs to assess if requirements were met.</p> <p>Latency performance was excellent, with the one-way application latency measured at approximately 25 milliseconds—well below the required 0.5 seconds. This low latency was observed on the private 5G network and validated the system's responsiveness.</p> <p>The AI/ML modules demonstrated high accuracy, consistently achieving between 90% and 95% detection rates across multiple sessions. Precision was maintained between 85% and 90%, with only minor false positives reported that did not impact overall operations.</p> <p>Location accuracy was confirmed to be within the required range, staying below 1 meter based on Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) data. This allowed the robot to follow mapped routes precisely during patrols and incident responses.</p> <p>Service availability was flawless, achieving 100% uptime during all trial sessions and exceeding the 99% requirement. The system reliably identified objects, with a detection rate close to 95.</p> <p>Alerts were promptly handled, with resolution times recorded at under one minute, much faster than the required three minutes. This demonstrated effective, low-latency collaboration between robotic units.</p> <p>Throughput measurements showed some deviation—downlink throughput experienced a 64% deviation and uplink throughput a 40% deviation. However, these values remained within acceptable operational ranges, ensuring stable communication.</p> <p>Overall, all critical KPIs were validated, confirming the system's strong performance in latency, detection, precision, location accuracy, availability, and responsiveness throughout the trials.</p>

Table 45. 5GS3: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>After the final trial, user feedback was collected through a structured 1-5 Likert-scale questionnaire. Results showed strong positive responses across usability, performance, and trust.</p> <p>Usability & Interface: Users found the system intuitive and easy to navigate. Interface clarity received high scores (4.5 for usability, 4.3 for video and detection), indicating it's accessible even to non-technical staff.</p> <p>Robot Behaviour: The robot's movement was rated as smooth and predictable (score: 4.4). Participants confirmed it followed waypoints reliably and returned to base when required.</p> <p>Detection Confidence: Detection accuracy was well received, with scores around 4.2–4.3. Minor misclassifications were noted but did not affect trust in the system's output.</p> <p>Trust & Acceptance: High trust was expressed in operational use. Statements like <i>"I would trust the system in a real incident"</i> and <i>"This could assist daily patrols"</i> scored 4.2 and 4.7, showing strong acceptance.</p> <p>Workload Impact: Users believed the system could reduce manual tasks and improve situational awareness. Productivity and decision-making benefits were highlighted.</p>

In Summary, Average scores across key areas ranged from 4.2 to 4.7. Suggested improvements included better object classification and clearer robot status indicators. Despite a small user group, feedback strongly supported the system's usability and operational potential.

5.3 Skylink Vision

The SkyLink Vision (SLV) project showcases an innovative approach to real-time aerial surveillance by integrating UAVs with AI analytics and 5G connectivity. The following sections outline the system's architecture, implemented technologies, measurements activities, and the validation of both technical and operational outcomes.

Table 46. Skylink Vision: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The SLV project integrates UAVs equipped with high-definition cameras and 5G connectivity to enable real-time aerial surveillance for traffic management applications. Unlike conventional UAV systems that perform onboard video processing—limiting performance due to constraints on power consumption and payload—the SLV system transmits video streams directly to ground-based AI processing units via high-speed 5G links. This offloading approach improves UAV efficiency and allows the use of more powerful analytical tools.</p> <p>The ground-based AI system processes the incoming video in real time, enabling the detection and tracking of vehicles. By fusing visual data with UAV sensor inputs, the system calculates vehicle coordinates and movement without relying on additional positioning systems. Operators monitor the surveillance feed through a user-friendly, map-based interface, which enhances situational awareness and supports timely decision-making.</p> <p>Overall, the SLV system is developed to improve public safety and operational efficiency for municipalities, emergency services, and law enforcement agencies.</p>

Table 47. Skylink Vision: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>SLV has developed an advanced aerial surveillance system that combines high-resolution UAV-mounted cameras with high-speed 5G connectivity. In this architecture, UAVs transmit live video streams directly to ground-based servers using WebRTC technology, thereby offloading computationally intensive tasks from the UAVs to more capable ground infrastructure.</p> <p>The system employs AI algorithms—developed with the PyTorch framework—for real-time video analysis, with a focus on license plate recognition and vehicle tracking. To accurately determine the geolocation of identified objects, SLV utilizes a Java-based algorithm that processes UAV telemetry data, including attitude, GPS position, and camera orientation. This algorithm integrates Digital Elevation Models (DEM) to enhance spatial accuracy.</p> <p>The analysed data is distributed via the MQTT protocol and visualized through a web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) developed using Flutter and implemented as a Web Progressive Application (WPA). The GUI provides operators with real-time tracking, monitoring, and control features.</p> <p>The SLV platform is designed with a modular architecture comprising dedicated services for video analysis, target localization, data storage, and frontend interaction. This modularity ensures seamless integration and scalability across various deployment scenarios.</p> <p>By combining UAV technology, AI-driven video analytics, and low-latency 5G communication, the SLV system offers a high-performance, scalable, and cost-effective solution for applications such as security surveillance, emergency response, and traffic monitoring.</p>

Table 48. Skylink Vision: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>A test bench was established to replicate the complete hardware chain of the UAV helicopter system, including the camera, autopilot simulator, single-board computer and 5G communication links. This setup streams synchronized video and telemetry data over a 5G network to a ground server, where real-time analysis is performed using PyTorch with YOLO and OpenCV for vehicle detection and license plate recognition.</p> <p>The processed results are made available for multi-client access and visualized through a user-friendly interface that combines live video feeds with a map-based display of detected targets. The system was evaluated remotely by sixteen UAV pilots with diverse technical backgrounds, who provided feedback on its reliability, low-latency performance, and overall usability.</p> <p>The test bench is designed for flexibility and can be adapted to alternative detection tasks or different operational environments by updating the AI model and adjusting platform parameters. Deployed at the 5Tonic lab facilities, the system demonstrated effective real-time analytics and confirmed its suitability for large-scale trials in areas such as traffic safety, security, and situational monitoring.</p>

Table 49. Skylink Vision: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>During the final trial phase, both downlink and uplink throughput exceeded initial targets, consistently achieving data rates above 150 Mbps in each direction. These results confirmed sufficient bandwidth availability to support real-time video streaming and telemetry transmission.</p> <p>Latency emerged as the most challenging requirement. Measurements with a commercial datalink recorded an average one-way latency of approximately 42 milliseconds—exceeding the 25-millisecond threshold required for fully manual UAV control. However, by utilizing a non-commercial communication link with optimized encryption configurations, latency was reduced to around 23 milliseconds, meeting the target specification for real-time responsiveness.</p> <p>Packet loss remained below the maximum acceptable threshold, confirming that communication reliability objectives were fulfilled. Vehicle detection precision reached 97.2%, exceeding the 95% benchmark and validating the system’s capability to maintain accurate recognition under dynamic operational conditions.</p> <p>While the critical latency requirement was only met under specific hardware configurations, the results demonstrate the viability of 5G networks in supporting advanced UAV applications. The findings also suggest that future enhancements—such as improved link-layer protocols or the application of network slicing—could further reduce latency and improve the safety and effectiveness of real-time UAV control.</p>

Table 50. Skylink Vision: Outcomes of the KVis validation.

Outcomes of the KVis validation
<p>Confidence in the connection reliability increased significantly among participating UAV pilots, with repeated measurements scenarios demonstrating uninterrupted 5G connectivity. This consistency contributed to a measurable rise in operator trust regarding 5G-based UAV control. Perceived safety also improved, as pilots reported enhanced flight oversight and reliable telemetry as key factors in reducing concerns about mid-air emergencies.</p> <p>Usability assessments showed that most operators were able to navigate the system interface intuitively. Additionally, the removal of the dedicated tracking antenna reduced average deployment time by approximately four minutes, resulting in a total setup duration of around sixteen minutes. Feedback collected through satisfaction surveys indicated that this streamlined setup process was particularly valuable in rapid-response scenarios.</p>

Quantitative survey results revealed that pilot trust in system stability and its performance in beyond visual line of sight missions exceeded a score of 4.0 on a five-point scale—surpassing initial projections.

5.4 CITY4ALL

The CITY4ALL project explores the use of VR and 5G technologies to create immersive experiences that raise awareness about disabilities and promote inclusive communities. This initiative integrates innovative cloud-rendered VR simulations with AI assistance and is evaluated through educational trials and network performance measurements.

Table 51. CITY4ALL: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The CITY4ALL project focuses on the development of a VR game aimed at raising awareness among younger students about the importance of collective action in creating inclusive communities for individuals with disabilities. Financially supported by the Piedmont Region in Italy, the project began with a prototype that simulated experiences related to motor disabilities.</p> <p>Over the course of the project, the initial VR prototype was expanded to include additional functionalities. These enhancements introduced a virtual AI assistant and new immersive experiences designed to simulate visual and auditory impairments. To demonstrate the benefits of 5G connectivity combined with cloud rendering, an upgraded version of the deafness simulation was developed. This enhanced experience features advanced effects and improved quality of service compared to the baseline implementation.</p> <p>All three simulations—motor, visual, and auditory impairments—share a common narrative objective: reaching and attending a stadium concert. Each scenario begins with an invitation from a friend, but the specific challenges encountered by the player vary according to the selected disability. These variations aim to provide users with a deeper understanding of the barriers faced by individuals with different types of disabilities, while also showcasing the potential of emerging technologies such as 5G and cloud-based rendering in delivering accessible and high-quality VR experiences.</p>

Table 52. CITY4ALL: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The CITY4ALL project developed a VR game using the Unity engine, featuring three immersive experiences designed to simulate different types of disabilities. The application is intended for VR headsets connected to a cloud rendering server via a high-bandwidth, low-latency 5G network, enabling high-quality graphics and smooth real-time performance.</p> <p>The first scenario, simulating deafness, reproduces the experience of auditory impairment through the perspective of a user with a cochlear implant. Dialogue comprehension is imperfect and depends on the player's visual focus. When the user looks directly at a character's lips, speech becomes clearer; otherwise, audio is muffled. A desaturated color palette visually reinforces the sense of isolation and reliance on lip-reading.</p> <p>The second scenario simulates blindness, immersing the user in complete darkness and requiring navigation with a virtual white cane. Spatial orientation relies on enhanced auditory and olfactory cues, with olfactory information presented visually. Spatialized audio provides directional awareness, while environmental familiarity and memory are used to aid movement. Collisions are indicated by red visual flashes, and essential context is conveyed through in-game voice cues.</p> <p>A third enhanced experience builds on the deafness scenario, leveraging 5G connectivity and cloud rendering to deliver improved visual quality while preserving VR frame rate stability. Upgrades include volumetric lighting, advanced colour grading for warmth and depth, realistic reflections, and microdetail textures to enhance realism. Atmospheric particle effects were added without degrading performance.</p>

An AI assistant, implemented using the open-source LLaMA 3.1 large language model, was integrated into a dedicated virtual room. This assistant provides users with additional information about disabilities, supporting the educational purpose of the simulation environment.

Table 53. CITY4ALL: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>Two experimental trials were carried out in different educational environments to evaluate the CITY4ALL VR experience. The first trial took place on March 10–11, 2025, at the "Don Milani" Comprehensive Institute in Druento, involving 76 students aged 12–13 and 7 teachers. The second trial was conducted on March 24, 2025, at the Faculty of Architecture of the Politecnico di Torino, with 34 university students aged 20–26 enrolled in the Inclusive Design course.</p> <p>Both trials followed a standardized structure, including an introductory session, testimonials from individuals with disabilities, hands-on immersive VR experiences, and follow-up reflection and feedback activities. The content and delivery were adapted to suit the audience. At the Druento school, the focus was placed on promoting awareness and empathy among younger students. At the Politecnico, the session emphasized the design process behind the VR game, and participants engaged in a workshop focused on inclusive design principles.</p> <p>In both settings, the initiative successfully promoted emotional involvement and increased awareness of accessibility and inclusion challenges, highlighting the educational value of VR in fostering inclusive thinking across age groups and disciplines.</p>

Table 54. CITY4ALL: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>Trialing activities were conducted using a commercial 5G NSA network to evaluate the performance of the CITY4ALL VR application. While the trials did not consistently meet the defined KPIs, gameplay completion was possible in certain cases. These evaluations provided valuable insights into the current capabilities and limitations of commercial 5G networks for VR-based applications.</p> <p>Initial expectations that a commercial 5G NSA network could deliver satisfactory performance across different deployment scenarios were not fully confirmed during the 062_Lab01 test in Rome. However, a subsequent measurement (062_Lab02), designed to simulate a private 5G SA environment, offered clearer validation of the network requirements. This measurement successfully met the targeted KPI values. A key outcome was the recorded round-trip delay of 3 milliseconds, a critical metric for ensuring user comfort and reducing motion sickness, especially for sensitive users.</p> <p>Despite not meeting all KPIs, the 062_Lab01 measurement still provided a playable experience due to lower packet loss compared to earlier trials conducted in Ivrea, Druento, and Turin. These results highlight the current limitations of commercial 5G infrastructure in fully supporting advanced, latency-sensitive applications like VR. They also underscore the importance of continued investment in mobile network evolution, particularly in edge computing solutions, to bring services closer to end-users and unlock the full potential of next-generation applications.</p>

Table 55. CITY4ALL: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>The first trial was conducted with 76 students from the "Don Milani" secondary school. Results showed strong positive feedback: 98.68% of students rated the game positively, indicating improved understanding of inclusion values and increased awareness of the daily challenges faced by individuals with disabilities. Additionally, 81.6% of students found the game dynamics intuitive and easy to understand, while 89.3% expressed high satisfaction with the experience. Furthermore, 94.7% of participants indicated a willingness</p>

to repeat the experience. Teacher feedback was similarly positive, with 100% of the seven participating teachers affirming the game's educational value.

The second trial involved 34 students enrolled in the Inclusive Design course at the Politecnico di Torino. In this group, 94.12% of students evaluated the game positively, reporting enhanced understanding of inclusion and heightened awareness of disability-related challenges. Among these participants, 85.3% found the game intuitive, and the same percentage gave high satisfaction ratings. A total of 97.1% would recommend the experience to others and were open to repeating it.

Overall, the immersive VR approach demonstrated effectiveness and meaningful engagement in both educational settings. These findings underscore the significant potential of immersive technologies as tools for fostering inclusive education and promoting impactful learning experiences across diverse student populations.

5.5 AI-PREMSET

This section presents the AI-PREMSET use case, which focuses on optimizing and assessing 3GPP-compliant MCX over 5G and future networks to enhance emergency response capabilities. The use case combines dynamic network optimization, AI/ML-driven data analysis, and real-time system adaptation to improve communication reliability and efficiency in critical scenarios.

Table 56. AI-PREMSET: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The use case focuses on optimizing and assessing 3GPP-compliant MCX over 5G networks and beyond to improve handling of various emergency conditions and scenarios. The objective is to develop mechanisms that dynamically optimize MCX performance across both the RAN and 5G Core domains. This optimization uses coverage data, initial and expected traffic demand from first responders or end users, and characterization of MCX traffic profiles.</p> <p>Data collection combined with AI and ML techniques processes these metrics and exported data to support network dimensioning, proactive resource and service allocation, demand forecasting, service placement strategies, and service adjustment planning. Through this approach, the solution has been enhanced with AI/ML capabilities, generating relevant datasets for future research.</p> <p>Additionally, the project validates the Romanian site infrastructure as a capable ecosystem to host third-party services or vertical applications, particularly in the domain of Security and Safety.</p>

Table 57. AI-PREMSET: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>Nemergent's 3GPP-compliant MCX system has been improved by adding metric exporting and retrieval mechanisms for its microservice-based modules, as well as for integration with external components related to radio access and core network infrastructure. This integration provides the necessary context awareness to enable dynamic service configuration.</p> <p>The original microservice solution was extended with a data collector that acts as a central hub for gathering metrics. Additionally, storage modules were introduced to interface between the data collector and data consumers, ensuring data persistence. The system also includes enhanced metrics dashboards and AI/ML modules for training and inference purposes. These modules expose multiple services to support proper interconnection, data exchange, and operation triggering.</p> <p>From a technology perspective, the 3GPP MCX services were deployed within Kubernetes clusters located at both Nemergent and ORO facilities. For network access, Wi-Fi, 5G NSA, and 5G SA networks were configured and trialed, with additional VPN tunnels established as needed. Key technologies used in these enhancements include HTTP APIs for data exchange; PostgreSQL, InfluxDB, Kafka, and Parquet files for</p>

data storage and dataset management; Python scripts for data curation and dataset generation; and TensorFlow and Scikit-Learn frameworks for AI/ML model training and inference.

Simulation tools involve the one simulator and the application of mathematical optimization methods focused on Location Covering Set Problems, with calculations aligned to 3GPP standards.

Table 58. AI-PREMSET: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>On April 14th and 15th 2025, Nemergent's MCX system underwent end-user training and live evaluation to assess its real-world performance on next-generation broadband networks. The activity began with an on-site training session held at TUIASI facilities, involving participants from emergency organizations and university students. The group included up to 15 active users, 26 active and passive end-users, and a total of 34 people, including staff and university members.</p> <p>The training combined theoretical explanations of MCX technology with a live technology demonstration and hands-on setup. During the trial, group communications via MCX were measured, including the use of supergroups, which allow regrouping multiple communication groups to coordinate across all participants.</p> <p>The system was deployed over a hybrid network combining 5G SA and NSA configurations in Stefan cel Mare boulevard. Performance data related to MCX communications was collected throughout the trial to evaluate system behaviour under varying coverage and resource constraints. The system and trial execution were adapted in real time based on this data.</p> <p>End-users included personnel from Serviciul de Telecomunicații Speciale (STS) emergency services and university students.</p>

Table 59. AI-PREMSET: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>In scenarios with adequate coverage, the system successfully met all target KPIs, particularly after optimizing group deployment across the area and scaling the microservice-based components. In areas with limited coverage, some errors occurred, but these were valuable for identifying system limitations and validating the effectiveness of the monitoring and real-time adaptation mechanisms.</p> <p>Coverage proved to be the most critical factor during measurements. Therefore, improvements in network coverage are expected to significantly enhance the overall performance of critical communications. More stable and proactive radio access networks will further benefit MCX services in next-generation mobile networks.</p> <p>Additional measurements assessed the impact of core and cloud link connectivity. Results showed that the microservice-based architecture effectively supports dynamic adaptation by allowing service placement across different nodes based on current network conditions. This flexibility helps minimize latency and reduce information loss during connection issues.</p> <p>Overall, this experience confirmed the robustness of the MCX solution under realistic conditions and demonstrated that context-aware metrics combined with data-driven system adjustments can improve performance in dynamic, user-driven deployment scenarios.</p>

Table 60. AI-PREMSET: Outcomes of the KVis validation.

Outcomes of the KVis validation
<p>The trial results and related survey indicate an overall positive outcome, with an average rating of 3.8 out of 5 from 26 participants. Notably, 92% of respondents gave a general evaluation above the threshold value of 3.</p>

Looking into specific areas, the perception of waste management during both the training session and trial execution scored 4.3. Regarding safety and the technology's impact on the community, the ratings were as follows: 4.2 for the potential to create safer and happier communities, 3.6 for the solution's ability to improve communication during disasters, 3.7 for the simplicity of the toolset for first responders in daily operations, and 3.6 for the MCX solution's efficiency as a communication tool.

Additional questions focused on AI-PREMSET-MCX's effectiveness in addressing existing and emerging challenges in the Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) sector yielded scores above 3.4.

These results demonstrate that the solution met expectations and provided valuable insights for future improvements and enhancements.

5.6 MILESTONE

The MILESTONE project addresses the critical need for enhanced worker safety in public infrastructure environments by integrating 5G connectivity with AI-powered computer vision and secure access control. Designed to provide real-time monitoring and rapid incident detection, MILESTONE leverages technologies to ensure compliance with safety regulations and facilitate proactive management of potential hazards.

Table 61. MILESTONE: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The MILESTONE system combines 5G connectivity with computer vision-based AI models and secure access control mechanisms to provide a real-time safety monitoring and assessment solution tailored for public infrastructure environments. By leveraging 5G's high-speed, low-latency communication and robust APIs for context-aware data queries, MILESTONE handles and processes data securely.</p> <p>Worker safety is a critical concern in public infrastructure sites such as public buildings, where workers must wear PPE to protect themselves. Ensuring real-time safety monitoring and assessment in these environments is essential to maintain worker protection at all times. The integration of 5G technology plays a key role in achieving this goal by enabling fast and reliable transmission of data from multiple surveillance sources, such as cameras. This allows for quick detection and response to potential safety hazards.</p> <p>MILESTONE collects real-time information from IoT devices, such as cameras, to monitor worker compliance with safety regulations, including the proper use of helmets and vests. The system alerts safety managers immediately when incidents occur, such as a worker without a helmet or unauthorized individuals entering restricted areas. These alerts, generated by advanced computer vision AI models, enable timely interventions to prevent serious accidents.</p>

Table 62. MILESTONE: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The MILESTONE project developed a 5G-based video streaming application to support an AI-driven decision-making system focused on worker safety. This solution integrates video streaming, AI analytics, and data space technologies to enable real-time workplace monitoring.</p> <p>Video feeds are captured at the network edge and transmitted over the 5G network to the cloud. In the cloud, AI computer vision models like YOLOv8 analyse the video streams to detect potential safety hazards. The system includes access control mechanisms to manage permissions for data producers and consumers, ensuring secure and selective sharing of video data.</p> <p>A key element of the architecture is the FIWARE Orion Context Broker, which acts as a data space enabler and manages DTs. It maintains metadata about all available video streams, allowing cloud components to dynamically discover and connect to the correct edge devices. Once connected, video streams are accessed and frames are extracted for AI analysis.</p>

This design ensures efficient, scalable, and interoperable communication between edge devices and the cloud. It supports high-performance video delivery and intelligent decision-making in safety-critical environments.

Table 63. MILESTONE: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The MILESTONE solution was demonstrated in a trial conducted at the Technopolis venue in the City of Athens. This venue is a dynamic environment that represents typical public infrastructure industrial work activities, making it suitable for rigorous measurements and evaluation of the MILESTONE system.</p> <p>During the trial, workers performed public infrastructure tasks while complying with safety rules, such as wearing protective helmets and vests. A network of cameras was installed to monitor these activities. The cameras used the 5G network alongside MILESTONE's AI-driven modules to detect safety incidents in real time, ensuring security, privacy, and strong access control.</p> <p>Safety supervisors and managers were able to monitor ongoing activities and receive real-time alerts through MILESTONE's user interface.</p> <p>In total, 32 individuals participated in the trial, including both workers and safety supervisors/managers. Specifically, the MILESTONE interface was demonstrated in real time to three supervisors from the City of Athens municipality, while six experienced civil engineers in construction supervision provided additional feedback on the solution.</p>

Table 64. MILESTONE: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>From a network performance perspective, the two most important KPIs evaluated were UL throughput per device and application RTT. These KPIs were continuously measured throughout the trial and consistently exceeded the target values. Specifically, the average UL throughput per device was 10.10 Mbit/s, well above the target of 1.5 Mbit/s. The average application RTT was 72.4 ms, remaining below the target threshold of 100 ms.</p> <p>To ensure continuous monitoring during the trial, two dedicated measurement scripts were developed and deployed on the mini-PC at the Technopolis site. This mini-PC acted as the local aggregation and processing unit for the incoming video streams.</p> <p>Regarding AI performance, Precision, Recall, and F1-score were measured to evaluate the PPE detection capability of the MILESTONE system. Using data from five cameras installed at Technopolis, the system achieved a Precision of 91.6%, Recall of 87.7%, and an F1-score of 89.6%.</p> <p>Overall, all KPIs for the MILESTONE project were successfully validated, reaching the initial targets.</p>

Table 65. MILESTONE: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>During the MILESTONE trial, several KVIs were measured and validated, ensuring alignment with the relevant TrialsNet Use Case 2 targets to maintain consistency with ongoing project activities. The KVIs assessed included resilience, which reflected the confidence participants had in the reliability of the devices, network infrastructure, and the over-the-top services and applications. Security was evaluated by measuring the perceived safety of the digital devices, systems, and services used throughout the trial. Sustainability focused on the confidence in the use of sustainable digital technologies within the system, while trustworthiness represented the extent to which the system was seen as reliable, secure, safe, and inspiring confidence in its users.</p>

To gather data on these indicators, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to the trial participants, resulting in 32 completed responses. The results showed that all KVIs significantly met their initial target thresholds, which ranged between 60 and 70 percent. Specifically, resilience was measured at 94%, security at 96%, sustainability at 94%, and trustworthiness at 96%.

5.7 ATOS

This section summarizes the key aspects and outcomes of the ATOS Driving project, which focuses on the development and validation of a comprehensive teleoperation system for remote vehicle control over a B5G network. The project involves deploying experimental B5G core and radio infrastructure, integrating advanced teleoperation applications, and conducting extensive trials to assess system performance under real-world conditions.

Table 66. ATOS: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The use case involves deploying a new experimental B5G core and radio infrastructure that supports the Network Exposure Function (NEF) and provides adequate coverage for tele-operation scenarios. This infrastructure, combined with a complete tele-operation system for both service and test vehicles, aims to demonstrate the ability of B5G networks to support remote vehicle operation. The test vehicle operated within a designated area covered by a B5G network co-owned by TNO and its partners in The Netherlands.</p> <p>To support sustainable tele-operation, TNO added three APIs to the 5G core. The first API enables dynamic requests to adjust QoS parameters for specific Protocol Data Unit (PDU) sessions used by the test vehicles. This ensures that necessary service quality levels are maintained, such as guaranteeing minimum uplink bandwidth to support video streaming from vehicle cameras. The second API allows the tele-operation service to subscribe to periodic network performance metric data during trials. This data includes metrics such as downlink and uplink throughput per PDU session, the total number of packets per session, and the total number of PDU sessions. These metrics are used for offline analysis to evaluate how network performance affects the tele-operation service at the application level. The third API collects energy consumption metrics, which are utilized by the IMEC network orchestrator to enable more energy-efficient orchestration of services running on the B5G infrastructure.</p>

Table 67. ATOS: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The ATOS Driving project developed a comprehensive teleoperation system designed to enable remote vehicle control by integrating multiple technologies. Central to this system is the Quality of Demand (QoD) Manager application, which allows users to establish sessions between the remote-control station and the vehicle using a selected QoS profile through the QoD API. The application also supports subscribing to performance metrics for each session. These metrics are collected by a containerized HTTP server that receives the data and forwards it to a centralized Graylog system for aggregation.</p> <p>The Graylog system compiles KPIs at the stream level, including latency, frame rate, packet loss, vehicle movement, and disconnection events. To support real-time teleoperation evaluation, Roboauto developed a specialized packet loss analysis tool tailored to the system's needs. The overall application integrates the teleoperation interface with the Graylog logging system, providing detailed information and visualizations of the collected data to support performance monitoring and analysis.</p>

Table 68. ATOS: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial activity for the ATOS Driving project took place at the DoIoT Field Lab within the Unmanned Valley in the Netherlands. The trial utilized a DAF XF truck equipped with teleoperation hardware and supported by a 5G network infrastructure. The trial was conducted in three phases over three separate weeks from November 2024 to March 2025.</p> <p>The first phase focused on integrating the various systems and verifying their individual functionalities. The second phase concentrated on data collection and measurements different operational scenarios. The final phase involved more extensive measurements aimed at improving the overall robustness of the teleoperation system. The trial incorporated a range of technologies and applications designed to evaluate the performance and reliability of teleoperation under different network conditions.</p> <p>Remote control was operated both from Roboauto's office in the Czech Republic and from the test site itself. Throughout the trial, multiple measurements sessions were conducted, resulting in approximately 25 hours of recorded data, with an average data throughput of 104 gigabits per hour.</p>

Table 69. ATOS: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The ATOS Driving project successfully validated several KPIs during its trials. The most critical trial scenario involved teleoperation under background network traffic with active QoD requests, closely simulating real-world operating conditions. The measured performance metrics included an UL throughput of 25.59 Mbps, an application one-way latency of 29.75 ms, and a packet loss rate of 0.21%, all meeting the strict requirements necessary for teleoperation.</p> <p>Although the service reliability was slightly below the target at 98.49%, there were no noticeable service interruptions experienced by the tele-operator. The trial demonstrated the system's ability to reliably transmit large volumes of data, maintain responsive control and feedback, and sustain dependable communication even under challenging network conditions. These results underscored the importance and effectiveness of the QoD application in enhancing system performance during network overloads or poor connectivity. Overall, the trial successfully validated the KPIs, confirming that the system is suitable for real-world deployment, with only minor areas identified for further improvement.</p>

Table 70. ATOS: Outcomes of the KVIs validation.

Outcomes of the KVIs validation
<p>The societal KVIs of teleoperation in truck logistics were evaluated with a focus on labour market dynamics, quality of life, technology acceptance, and the changing identity of the truck driver profession. Teleoperation helps address the shortage of truck drivers in Europe by separating the act of driving from the physical presence inside the vehicle, allowing for more flexible and attractive working conditions. Trials demonstrated that teleoperation could enhance drivers' quality of life by enabling them to control vehicles remotely from centralized stations or even from home, supporting standardized shift work.</p> <p>Economic sustainability was another important KVI, concentrating on operational efficiency, cost reduction, and infrastructure requirements. Simulations explored various teleoperator-to-vehicle ratios, indicating potential operational savings and improved fleet management. Larger logistics operators could achieve more favourable ratios due to variable idle times and flexible task handover protocols, paving the way for new business models centred around centralized teleoperation services.</p> <p>Additionally, the service sustainability was assessed to reflect the system's ability to maintain performance while minimizing energy consumption. Measurements showed that the system could reduce energy use</p>

during non-peak periods by scaling down resources or offloading tasks to more energy-efficient components, further supporting sustainable operation.

5.8 i-CNC

This section provides a detailed overview of the i-CNC project, presenting how the integration of IIoT, 5G connectivity, and AI-driven chatter detection contributes to advancing manufacturing processes through enhanced monitoring, analysis, and operator support. The obtained results demonstrate the technical performance, practical validation, and value impact of the i-CNC system within real industrial environments.

Table 71. i-CNC: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The i-CNC project falls under the IIoT category with a focus on cloudification. Its primary objective is to detect chattering during milling processes by reliably measuring and analysing key indicators related to machine states, workpiece conditions, and milling operations. The system is designed to notify and alert operators to intervene when process deviations occur, ensuring compliance with manufacturing standards.</p> <p>This project contributes to the ITSS domain by introducing a new use case and deploying an E2E infrastructure that combines a real industrial environment with a commercial 5G network. Thanks to 5G's high reliability and low latency, sensor data from milling machines can be transmitted from the shop floor without interfering with existing networks, thus minimizing safety risks. This approach centralizes the processing at a dedicated edge evaluation platform for chatter prediction, removing the need for heavy local computing resources on the machines themselves.</p>

Table 72. i-CNC: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The i-CNC project uses a decentralized architecture consisting of three independent modules that communicate through the cloud.</p> <p>The data acquisition system is installed at the Paiania and Patra shop floors. It includes Micromega IAC-CM-U-03 accelerometers mounted on milling machines, a LabJack T8 data acquisition device for high-resolution sampling, and a Raspberry Pi 5 processing unit connected directly to a 5G router (RUTX50 from Teltonika Networks). The Raspberry Pi runs Python scripts to format and send data via MQTT to the cloud and also hosts the CNC operator's graphical user interface, which displays the assessment results in real time.</p> <p>The database module is hosted at FOGUS premises and includes an MQTT broker for data ingestion. It provides centralized storage using an InfluxDB database with a Telegraf agent to collect data from the MQTT broker. All components in this module are managed within a Kubernetes cluster to ensure scalability and reliability.</p> <p>The assessment module consists of a containerized AI application deployed on LMS's server. This module processes the vibration data to generate chatter detection assessments using an AI algorithm, achieving 95% accuracy in identifying chatter events.</p>

Table 73. i-CNC: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The i-CNC trial event was held on March 13th 2025 at CNC Solutions in Paiania. It involved 30 participants from diverse backgrounds, including industry representatives, academic members (PhD candidates, professors, undergraduate students, and publishers), and CNC operators, distributed in a 20-20-60 ratio respectively.</p>

The event combined theoretical presentations with practical demonstrations of the i-CNC system's operation. Attendees were introduced to CNC machines, the chatter phenomenon, and the integration of 5G networks and AI applications within the manufacturing sector.

The trial showcased the system's capabilities, including real-time monitoring and data collection across multiple, geographically distributed sites. Participants also had hands-on experience with CNC machines, allowing them to observe and control chatter events and directly explore the i-CNC system's functionality in a real manufacturing environment.

Table 74. i-CNC: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation

The network round-trip latency was measured within the target KPI range of 50 to 100 ms, with an average value of 75 ms. The application round-trip latency was identified as the most critical requirement. It met the target KPI of 140 ms when the assessment module was hosted within the i-CNC system's compute infrastructure. When the assessment module was moved to a separate infrastructure, the latency remained below 200 ms, demonstrating the capability of the 5G network and AI algorithms to support manufacturing applications.

These results highlight the significant impact of these technologies on both product quality and business efficiency, offering potential savings in cost and time. However, the findings also indicate the need for further deployment of 5G Non-Public Networks (NPNs) to address link-level challenges, especially in industrial environments where 5G signals must penetrate steel and concrete walls, such as those found in the CNC machine shop used for the i-CNC demonstration.

Table 75. i-CNC: Outcomes of the KVis validation.

Outcomes of the KVis validation

The value-driven analysis of the i-CNC project aims to connect KVis with KPIs to identify the primary areas of impact. Environmentally, the combination of AI algorithms and 5G connectivity enables instant communication between CNC machines and the AI model, allowing for immediate corrective actions. This capability reduces machine inefficiencies and downtime, lowering operational expenses by 4% to 6% per machine. Since chatter causes defective workpieces that must be scrapped, resulting in wasted raw materials, early detection with 95% accuracy helps reduce material waste caused by chatter by up to 80%, significantly enhancing resource efficiency.

From an economic sustainability perspective, 5G connectivity provides the necessary infrastructure for real-time AI processing and immediate response to chatter detection. The system achieves network round-trip latency (50–100 ms) and application round-trip latency (around 150 ms), ensuring CNC operators receive timely commands to continue or halt operations. By automating machine monitoring, the solution frees skilled workers to focus on higher-priority tasks, simplifying their workflow.

In terms of training and education, the user-friendly dashboards and real-time chatter detection support interactive learning and a deeper understanding of CNC machining dynamics, though this value is more difficult to quantify using standard KPIs. Feedback from the trial event—attended mostly by researchers and PhD students—was positive, highlighting the relevance, clarity, and usefulness of the demonstrations. CNC operators also confirmed the system's practical utility, rating the AI assistant as highly effective in suppressing chatter and expressing confidence in deploying the system, noting a smooth and valuable user experience.

5.9 AdaptoFlow

The AdaptoFlow framework was developed to enhance the performance, scalability, and energy efficiency of real-time video analytics use cases in 5G-enabled edge computing environments. It was integrated and validated within the Romanian TrialsNet testbed through a series of technical deployments, experiments, and field trials.

Table 76. AdaptoFlow: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The AdaptoFlow use case support UC1 and UC4 deployed in Iasi. These use cases rely on IP camera streams transmitted over the 5G network provided by ORO to an edge server hosted at TUIASI. The incoming video frames are processed by a deep learning inference pipeline based on the NVIDIA DeepStream and Savant frameworks, using YOLOv8 model variants for object detection and analysis.</p> <p>AdaptoFlow enhances the performance and efficiency of these use cases by introducing two core services: Adaptive Stream Inference (ASI) and Model Swapping (MS). The ASI service utilizes probabilistic estimators to identify and skip non-critical video frames during periods of low activity. This dynamic adjustment reduces both GPU load and network traffic, while maintaining the necessary quality of service.</p> <p>The MS service complements ASI by selecting the most energy-efficient YOLOv8 variant for each frame batch. This decision is based on real-time data from system monitoring probes, which provide metrics on resource usage and power consumption.</p> <p>The complete system is deployed as a set of containerized applications compatible with various hardware platforms, including NVIDIA Jetson Orin, x86-based systems, and ARM-based GPU devices. A unified monitoring stack collects detailed performance metrics, such as inference latency, device utilization, and model output.</p> <p>All collected data is visualized through a user-defined dashboard, which presents real-time information on object detection results, system performance, and energy usage. This provides operators with an intuitive interface for monitoring and optimizing system behaviour during deployment.</p>

Table 77. AdaptoFlow: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The AdaptoFlow-enabled solution delivers real-time video analytics through a deep learning inference pipeline deployed at the network edge and integrated with 5G connectivity. The system is implemented as a modular Python library that extends the Savant framework, maintaining compatibility with existing application logic and business rules.</p> <p>At its core, the solution utilizes NVIDIA DeepStream as the primary inference engine. Object detection is performed using YOLOv8 model variants, which are converted to ONNX format and optimized with TensorRT to ensure high-performance inference.</p> <p>The pipeline includes two key AdaptoFlow services: ASI and adaptive MS. Both services are fully configurable, allowing users to define parameters such as inference frequency, error tolerance, available model variants, target accuracy, and acceptable latency. The full logic of these services is implemented in Python, ensuring flexibility and ease of integration.</p> <p>For deployment, the entire system is containerized using Docker, supporting a range of hardware platforms including NVIDIA Jetson Orin, x86 servers, and ARM-based GPU devices. To support performance monitoring, a unified observability stack has been implemented. This stack combines Prometheus and NetData with native telemetry interfaces such as NVidia's and Intel RAPL to collect real-time CPU, GPU, and power consumption metrics. On Jetson Orin devices, a custom GPU monitoring probe has been integrated to capture detailed utilization and frequency data.</p> <p>Inference results are disseminated in real time using Kafka, while camera streams are delivered over a VPN-secured 5G connection provided by Orange, enabling robust and secure video transmission in field trials.</p> <p>Finally, a Grafana dashboard aggregates and visualizes time-series data, providing users with real-time insights into detection outcomes, system resource usage, and energy consumption.</p>

Table 78. AdaptoFlow: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The AdaptoFlow field trial was conducted over a five-day period from January 27 to January 31, 2025, in Iași, Romania. Its primary objective was to evaluate the performance improvements and operational benefits introduced by the AdaptoFlow framework when integrated into the deep learning model serving pipeline of the Romanian use cases within the TrialsNet project. The experiments were carried out at the 5G laboratory of the TUIASI, which also serves as the control hub for these use cases.</p> <p>The testbed consisted of a GPU-enabled edge server connected to a private 5G network operated by ORO. This infrastructure allowed high-definition video streams from eight IP cameras installed across the city—specifically at the Podu Ros intersection—to be transmitted in real time to the edge processing unit. To ensure data privacy, no video content was stored during the sessions. Instead, the research team accessed the setup through a secure VPN connection provided by ORO and TUIASI, enabling live data processing throughout the field trial.</p> <p>During the trial, three core experiments were conducted to assess different aspects of AdaptoFlow’s performance. The first experiment focused on comparing the baseline use case implementation with an enhanced version incorporating AdaptoFlow’s ASI service. This comparison aimed to identify potential gains in inference efficiency and system resource optimization. The second experiment evaluated the benefits of integrating the adaptive MS feature, analysing its impact relative to the original pipeline. The third experiment extended the analysis further by trialing the system’s scalability, introducing additional camera feeds to observe how the deep learning serving pipeline and 5G network handled increased loads under real-time conditions.</p> <p>Across the five days, the trial achieved significant operational scale, delivering a total of eleven full experimental sessions, each lasting between one to one and a half hours. In total, more than fourteen hours of experimentation were completed, resulting in a large volume of timestamped data, detailed performance measurements, and multiple KPI validation scenarios.</p> <p>In addition to the core technical assessments, two experiments conducted on the third and fourth days were specifically allocated to use case operators. These sessions allowed them to configure and operate AdaptoFlow with varying parameter settings, offering valuable insights into the system’s usability, flexibility, and learning curve from an end-user perspective. To conclude the trial, a live demonstration and technical presentation were organized at the TUIASI lab, giving other project partners an opportunity to observe AdaptoFlow in action and discuss its applicability in real-world smart city scenarios.</p>

Table 79. AdaptoFlow: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The purpose of the KPIs validation was to assess the impact of integrating AdaptoFlow into the video streaming deep learning pipeline used by the Romanian use cases. The results showed significant improvements in system performance and resource efficiency.</p> <p>Specifically, by using AdaptoFlow, application latency was reduced by more than 51%, network traffic by over 71%, computational overhead by 43%, and energy consumption during inference by more than 78%. These improvements came at the cost of a moderate drop in classification accuracy—around 7% for ASI and 12% for adaptive MS.</p> <p>The experiments also demonstrated that with AdaptoFlow in place, the number of 5G video streaming cameras in use could be doubled without overloading the local edge server. The system was able to handle the increased data traffic efficiently, whereas the baseline use case struggled with fewer input streams. This proves that AdaptoFlow can improve scalability by optimizing the use of computing and network resources.</p> <p>Furthermore, network performance KPIs such as uplink throughput remained stable, averaging above 4.6 Mbps per device even when all eight video streams were active. This level of performance was only possible</p>

due to the algorithmic optimizations introduced by AdaptoFlow, as the standard setup could not maintain similar throughput levels under the same conditions.

In conclusion, while current 5G edge systems already provide strong capabilities, the field trial results highlight the need for continued improvements in energy efficiency and resource management. Solutions like AdaptoFlow can offer a path forward by enabling smarter, AI-based control over workloads, which will be essential in supporting the demands of next-generation networks beyond 5G.

Table 80. AdaptoFlow: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>The AdaptoFlow framework was validated against the TrialsNet value model, showing strong alignment across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Validation took place during a five-day field trial in Iasi, Romania, and three demo sessions in Nicosia, Cyprus, involving 22 experts from organizations such as TUIASI, ORO, Ceranext, CYENS, and KIOS CoE.</p> <p>Field trial measurements confirmed significant improvements: energy consumption was reduced by 53–96%, latency by 51–83%, and resource usage improved by up to 66%. Stakeholder feedback supported these results: 68% positively rated cost reduction, 72% confirmed increased scalability, and 63% recognized performance speed improvements. Socio-environmental responsibility received the highest approval at 86%, while overall effectiveness scored 59%, still showing value in hardware optimization.</p>

5.10 AI4RTC

This section presents the AI4RTC use case, which focuses on the deployment and evaluation of the Charging Network Analytics Platform designed to optimize power load balancing across EV charging stations.

Table 81. AI4RTC: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>This use case focuses on trialing a new management system, called the Charging Network Analytics Platform, designed to balance power loads across EV Charging Stations. The goal is to prevent power peaks that could disrupt the operation of local charging infrastructure or affect the stability of the electrical grid.</p> <p>As part of the TrialsNet project, the platform has been deployed over a 5G-SA network to enable real-time data exchange and rapid response to power fluctuations. Specifically, the connectivity of five EV Loader Charging Network stations was upgraded to 5G-SA using the Cosmote 5G infrastructure. This upgrade allows the system to react to power changes within milliseconds, a capability made possible by the low latency characteristics of 5G-SA networks.</p> <p>The platform is supported by AI-based forecasting tools, which predict potential power peaks in advance and take corrective actions to mitigate them. By combining fast, reliable 5G communication with intelligent analytics, the solution ensures stable and efficient charging operations. This results in consistent station performance, prevents overloads, and maintains high customer satisfaction.</p>

Table 82. AI4RTC: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The latest models of User Equipment were used to ensure high-performance 5G-SA connectivity between the Charging Stations and the Management Platform. The Charging Network Analytics Platform was developed using advanced open-source software components, enabling robust operation and powerful visualization capabilities. These components were deployed as Docker containers on a Google Cloud Virtual Machine, providing a scalable architecture for the solution.</p>

Additionally, a new AI model was developed based on the fusion of two deep learning techniques: Transformer Attention Layers (TAA) and Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) Layers. The model was trained both before and during the trial, achieving a high level of performance by the project's conclusion.

Table 83. AI4RTC: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The AI4RTC trial took place at five EV charging station sites across Athens, Greece. These locations included the Parity Platform Office in Maroussi, Four Seasons Astir Palace Hotel in Vouliagmeni, Serafeio Athletic Complex in Athens, Alfa Techniki in Alimos, and Ayens Cars in Glyfada. During the project, a total of 10 EV charging outlets were upgraded and monitored. The pilot served about 200 unique users, including hotel guests, fleet drivers, corporate employees, and visitors to public facilities. Users interacted with the charging infrastructure naturally during their daily routines, without any additional recruitment.</p> <p>The trial spanned from June 2024, starting with a baseline connectivity assessment, and continued into early 2025, focusing on ongoing AI data integration and analysis. Existing Wi-Fi and 3G connections were upgraded to 5G, with Ethernet cables installed at each charger to ensure stable connections. Dedicated 5G routers (ZTE MC801A, RUTX50) were installed at all sites to provide ultra-low latency communication.</p> <p>System performance was benchmarked before and after the upgrade using server logs, Wireshark captures, and telemetry analytics. Data collected through EV Loader's platform was made available via APIs, allowing integration with LocalAI predictive tools. The trial confirmed improvements in responsiveness, throughput, and service reliability under real-world conditions. Facility managers actively monitored the chargers and provided both qualitative and quantitative feedback. Performance KPIs showed no significant service interruptions following the network upgrades.</p> <p>A targeted survey of 10 facility managers reported high satisfaction with system responsiveness and reliability. Technical monitoring through Wireshark and server IoT logs supported these findings by demonstrating enhanced network performance.</p>

Table 84. AI4RTC: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The AI4RTC trial confirmed that all KPIs were successfully met following the upgrade to 5G connectivity. DL throughput per device increased significantly, rising from around 3–5 Mbps before the upgrade to 20–35 Mbps afterward. Similarly, uplink throughput improved from approximately 1–2 Mbps to 10–20 Mbps, as measured using Wireshark.</p> <p>Total system round-trip latency dropped substantially, decreasing from a range of 400–3000 milliseconds before the upgrade to just 50–70 milliseconds afterward, based on EV Loader server logs. Network RTT, measured through Wireshark packet captures, also improved, falling from 80–250 milliseconds down to 18–25 milliseconds. This reduction ensured quick command acknowledgment.</p> <p>Service reliability, defined by sessions operating under 100 milliseconds latency, increased from about 65% to 97% after the connectivity improvements. The trial demonstrated the ability to perform real-time load control across more than 500 session measurements without compromising electrical performance. Minor issues appeared only under very high loads, where server-side processing caused small, non-critical delays.</p>

Table 85. AI4RTC: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>Surveys of facility managers showed a clear improvement in system responsiveness, with an average rating of 4.6 out of 5 after the upgrade. Load management activation thresholds increased from a baseline of 80%</p>

to between 90% and 95%, approaching the target of 95%. Managers noted that the system could now safely use a much larger portion of the available electrical capacity without risking overload.

The success rate of load management operations was as expected, with zero incidents reported at 9 out of 10 surveyed sites. System performance consistently exceeded the goal of 99.8% operational integrity. Trust in the system's reliability was strong, reflected in an average trustworthiness score of 4.8 out of 5 from facility managers. Surveys also showed a significant increase in confidence in the system's ability to autonomously manage electrical loads.

Facility managers highlighted the elimination of activation delays that had previously occurred due to network instability. By ensuring reliable 5G connectivity, the system greatly reduced the risk of overloads caused by late execution of load control commands.

5.11 Cities w/o Barriers

This section presents an overview of the Cities Without Barriers project, which aims to enhance urban accessibility for individuals with mobility challenges through advanced technology integration. The project leverages a network of 5G-connected mobile devices and AI-driven analytics to identify architectural barriers and provide real-time accessibility information.

Table 86. Cities w/o Barriers: Use Case description.

Use Case description
<p>The Cities Without Barriers project aims to improve urban accessibility, especially for individuals with mobility challenges. The system uses a system of mobile devices equipped with advanced sensors, including smartphones and specialized edge-processing modules, all connected via 5G networks. These devices collect detailed data on the urban environment, focusing on architectural barriers such as uneven surfaces, poorly designed stairs, and narrow pathways.</p> <p>Data is initially processed locally on the edge devices to increase efficiency, then sent to a centralized cloud infrastructure. There, AI algorithms perform advanced analysis, including semantic segmentation and obstacle detection. The system produces dynamic, detailed accessibility maps that provide real-time information on the accessibility of urban spaces, including accessibility scores.</p> <p>These maps are valuable tools for city planners and public authorities working to create more inclusive cities. Additionally, the system offers real-time navigation assistance to individuals with mobility limitations, helping them move through urban areas more effectively.</p>

Table 87. Cities w/o Barriers: Application and technologies.

Developed application and technologies
<p>The project focused on developing an accessible and reliable application. A major part of the effort involved designing an accessible GUI and integrating AI algorithms, specifically Deep Neural Networks (DNN), to perform semantic analysis on video and 3D data for identifying architectural barriers. Edge AI optimization was applied to pre-process data locally, reducing latency and network load. This was supported by a cloud infrastructure connected via a commercial 5G network.</p> <p>The system architecture was structured in layers for data collection, processing, and user interaction. It included two main modules: a mapping application for operators to gather data on pedestrian routes, and a navigation application that provides processed accessibility information as an aid for users with mobility challenges.</p> <p>The development aimed to create a scalable application that delivers real-time accessibility information, covering the entire process from data collection by operators in the field to navigation support for end users.</p>

Table 88. Cities w/o Barriers: Trial activity.

Trial activity
<p>The trial was conducted in two phases involving the release of two applications. The first phase, the “mapping” phase, focused on data collection by operators in Turin, with the goal of covering at least 500 km of pedestrian pathways. The second phase, the “navigation” phase, targeted end-user engagement. The large-scale trial lasted 10 months, during which the mapping phase achieved a total of 514.9 km of data collected, while the navigation phase concentrated on user interaction.</p> <p>The mapping trial took place in Turin from July 2024 to March 2025 and encountered challenges such as adverse weather conditions and operator engagement issues. These risks were managed through careful assessment to avoid impacts on schedule and costs. The navigation trial ran mainly from November 2024 to April 2025.</p> <p>The trial began with an initial setup involving internal operators and experts to evaluate the application’s capabilities and data transfer between mapping devices—smartphones and custom edge-processing units—and the cloud infrastructure, all connected via Turin’s 5G network. Following this, the data gathering phase deployed mapping devices to capture RGB imagery and 3D spatial data. Initial data processing occurred locally on the edge devices before transmission to the cloud for further analysis.</p>

Table 89. Cities w/o Barriers: Outcomes of the KPIs validation.

Outcomes of the KPIs validation
<p>The Cities Without Barriers trial produced several important findings related to network performance. The 5G network generally met the predefined performance objectives. Latency on the 5G network was stable and consistently within target ranges. Although uplink performance showed some variability, it still met the average KPIs. Downlink performance was stable and remained mostly within the targeted parameters.</p> <p>KPIs for Edge and Cloud computing capabilities also demonstrated stable infrastructure performance, with all results remaining within acceptable limits and no issues reported.</p> <p>However, the trial identified that stability problems with the mapping application were mainly caused by transitions between 5G and 4G networks. Most connections during the trial operated on NSA 5G architecture, unlike laboratory tests where SA architecture was more common. This highlighted the need to improve 5G coverage to reduce dependence on 4G fall-back connections and enhance overall system stability.</p>

Table 90. Cities w/o Barriers: Outcomes of the KVI validation.

Outcomes of the KVI validation
<p>The measurements of KVIs demonstrated that the Cities Without Barriers project met its targets in all evaluated areas. For social utility, 95.5% of end-users found the application useful for enhancing urban accessibility, while 71.4% of field operators considered the collected data sufficiently detailed. Regarding usability, 65.1% of users rated the app as intuitive, giving it 4 or 5 out of 5, and 36.4% reported regular use. For community engagement, all field operators expressed willingness to continue mapping activities, and 81.8% of navigators confirmed the app helped them find accessible routes. Under scalability, 93.9% of users indicated they would use the service in other cities if data quality remained high. Qualitative feedback pointed to the need for interface improvements, real-time updates, and user-generated content features. Overall, the results confirm strong user satisfaction, active engagement, and clear potential for broader deployment.</p>

5.12 Added value brought by the sub-projects

This section provides the additional values and benefits brought by the sub-project to the original use cases from the ITSS domain, extending their scope and applicability. It also covers considerations on 6G requirements for these sub-projects.

The **Connected Rails** sub-project brought valuable contributions to the initial use cases of WP3 by advancing key aspects of positioning accuracy, real-time communication, and network performance within complex operational environments. Its focus on enhancing tramway operations through integrated high-precision onboard positioning (SYS-NGAP) and 5G signal monitoring (SYS-SDR) demonstrated the practical benefits and challenges of deploying 5G-enabled autonomous systems in real urban settings, as shown on Florence's tram system. The highly accurate positioning capabilities developed by Connected Rails helped inform and support similar localization needs in other use cases, such as autonomous vehicle navigation in UC3 (Autonomous APRON) and mobile tracking in UC4 (traffic monitoring). Furthermore, Connected Rails validated the feasibility of integrating 5G communication in daily transportation services without disruption, reinforcing the sub-project's objective to enable robust, real-time services over 5G networks. Although the trials revealed areas where network continuity needs improvement, the findings contributed to refining network configurations and multi-link strategies also applied in other use cases, enhancing overall system resilience and performance. In summary, Connected Rails delivered practical demonstrations and valuable data that could support the development and deployment of advanced positioning and communication solutions across the broader project.

The **5GS3** sub-project significantly contributed to the initial WP3 use cases by advancing surveillance, autonomous operations, and real-time response capabilities in critical infrastructure environments. By deploying AI-powered autonomous robotic platforms over 5G/B5G networks—particularly demonstrated through live trials at AIA—5GS3 validated the integration of advanced analytics, remote control, and smooth autonomous navigation within demanding operational contexts. The robust communication and low-latency performance achieved by 5GS3 is in line with the other use cases that rely on real-time data exchange and precise control, such as UC3's autonomous baggage handling and UC4's traffic monitoring systems. Its focus on reliable object detection and anomaly response could help refine AI analytics models and system responsiveness, boosting confidence in automation's role across different sectors. Additionally, the centralized dashboard concept introduced by 5GS3 enhanced situational awareness and operational control, which aligned with monitoring and management tools used in other use cases. Overall, 5GS3 provided practical demonstrations and validated technologies that strengthened the initial use cases' objectives of enhancing safety, automation, and operational efficiency through 5G-enabled autonomous systems.

The **Skylink Vision** sub-project brought value to the initial use cases by validating the effectiveness of UAV-based real-time surveillance supported by AI and 5G connectivity. Its focus on aerial video acquisition and ground-based processing addressed key challenges in public safety, traffic monitoring, and emergency response scenarios, which are central elements across several of the use cases. By offloading intensive analytics to ground systems via stable 5G uplinks, Skylink Vision demonstrated how to overcome onboard UAV processing limitations—an insight directly useful to use cases such as UC3 (autonomous ground logistics) and UC4 (traffic analytics). Its ability to maintain video quality and ensure reliable object tracking could support the goal of enhancing situational awareness in dynamic environments, which aligns with UC5's emergency response focus. Overall, Skylink Vision helped bridge the gap between airborne sensing and actionable data, offering complementary capabilities to the ground-based automation and monitoring solutions demonstrated in the other use cases.

The **CITY4ALL** sub-project enriched the initial use cases by introducing a novel educational and awareness dimension through immersive technologies. By leveraging VR, AI, and 5G, CITY4ALL addressed social inclusion, complementing the technical focus of the other use cases with a human-centric perspective. Through the development and deployment of a VR game simulating various disabilities, CITY4ALL provided an impactful tool to raise awareness about accessibility challenges. This contribution aligns especially well with use cases like UC2 and UC4, where user interaction and social acceptance of technology are key to broader adoption. The integration of a cloud-rendered version using 5G further demonstrated the role of high-performance networks in delivering enhanced immersive experiences, reinforcing the need for robust connectivity infrastructure. The project's success in engaging students and improving understanding of inclusivity supports the broader societal goals embedded in the overall initiative. CITY4ALL showed that digital tools can foster empathy and inclusion, adding meaningful depth to the technological advances measured across the other use cases.

The **AI-PREMSET** sub-project brought important value to the initial use cases by addressing critical needs in reliable, real-time communication for emergency and public safety scenarios. By combining AI with 3GPP-compliant MCX over 5G networks, it demonstrated how intelligent adaptation can maintain service quality in dynamic or constrained conditions. The project's live trial in Romania provided valuable insights for use cases

like UC5, which focuses on emergency response, as well as UC1 and UC4, where dependable group communications are essential. AI-PREMSET showed how real-time monitoring and adjustment can reduce communication disruptions, ensuring that teams remain connected during high-stress operations. The integration of AI for service management complements the data analytics and automation strategies used across other use cases, adding a layer of resilience and situational awareness. Positive user feedback confirmed its practical value for enhancing coordination and safety, making AI-PREMSET a strong example of how AI and 5G can jointly support next-generation mission-critical services.

The **MILESTONE** sub-project added strong practical value to the initial use cases by focusing on real-time worker safety monitoring in public infrastructure environments. Through the use of 5G connectivity, AI-based computer vision, and automated alerts, MILESTONE aligned well with use cases concerned with smart infrastructure, operational safety, and automation. Its ability to detect issues such as missing PPE or unauthorized access through edge-based video streams and cloud analytics is directly relevant to use cases like UC2 and UC3, where situational awareness and personnel safety are crucial. The seamless integration of 5G-enabled video monitoring and real-time AI processing demonstrated the scalability of such solutions for wider public environments. MILESTONE showed how digital safety tools can enhance supervision without requiring constant manual oversight, offering a solid foundation for safe and smart management of connected public spaces.

The **ATOS** sub-project added critical contributions to UC2 and UC5 by demonstrating real-world remote vehicle control over a B5G network. Its trials showed that teleoperation is feasible under live network conditions, aligning with goals related to logistics automation and intelligent mobility. By integrating dynamic network management and energy monitoring, the sub-project provided insights relevant to service orchestration and resource efficiency, supporting wider adoption in future mobility use cases. This directly supports emergency and logistics-related mobility scenarios requiring remote operation capabilities in constrained or hazardous environments.

The sub-project **i-CNC** contributed to UC3 and UC4 through its AI-enhanced industrial automation use case. The integration of low-latency 5G with AI detection for milling operations helped validate how smart manufacturing processes can improve operational efficiency, reduce material waste, and assist human operators in real time. Its centralized monitoring and IIoT-based architecture illustrated the benefits of next-generation connectivity in critical production environments. The use of real-time alerts and predictive capabilities provides direct value to industrial safety and productivity objectives, especially in scenarios where time-sensitive intervention is needed.

The **AdaptoFlow** sub-project aligned with UC1 and UC4 by advancing real-time video analytics for city-level surveillance and edge computing. Its demonstration in a live urban setting showed how edge-based AI processing can reduce latency and load while scaling video streams across multiple cameras. This reinforces the role of energy-efficient, scalable edge analytics for smart city and public safety use cases relying on dense 5G infrastructure. Its capacity to support multi-stream analytics without network overload is crucial for city-wide monitoring systems that operate under variable traffic and crowd conditions.

The sub-project **AI4RTC** could support UC4 by addressing the energy dimension of urban infrastructure—specifically EV charging. Its real-time load balancing platform, based on 5G SA and AI forecasting, enhanced energy efficiency and infrastructure protection. The solution's responsiveness and reliability validated how AI and 5G can support critical infrastructure monitoring, improving operational resilience and sustainability in public systems. This contributes to grid-friendly deployment of EV networks in congested urban areas, where stability and responsiveness are vital.

The sub-project **Cities w/o Barriers** can bring additional values to UC1 and UC5 by promoting digital inclusion through AI and mobile sensing. By detecting and mapping urban accessibility barriers in real time, the project tackled a key societal need—urban mobility for all. It demonstrated how 5G and AI can work together to improve navigational safety and accessibility, supporting inclusive smart city developments and future applications in urban planning and navigation tools. This directly supports participatory urban development by empowering municipalities to base accessibility improvements on live, data-driven insights.

For the considerations on 6G requirements for sub-projects, based on the trials and evaluations, several performance and functional requirements towards 6G were identified, ensuring scalability, reliability, and efficiency

for future deployments in the ITSS domain. These are summarized hereafter, following on the categorization that has been provided for the project's core use cases in Section 4.

Performance Requirements

- **Throughput (Uplink/Downlink):** Current 5G deployments achieved sufficient throughput for video, positioning, and automation tasks. However, large-scale real-time monitoring (e.g., multiple UAV streams, VR rendering, worker safety video analytics) will require more than 1 Gbps sustained uplink and high-capacity downlink capabilities per cell in 6G. This is essential for scenarios involving simultaneous high-resolution video streams, AI-driven analytics, and real-time feedback loops.
- **Latency:** 5G SA has enabled low latency, but massive and real implementations for safety-critical use cases such as remote control (ATOS), mission-critical communication (AI-PREMSET), and real-time anomaly detection (MILESTONE, Skylink Vision) will demand less than 10 ms latency. 6G must reduce E2E delay further to enable instantaneous decision-making in emergency or autonomous operations.
- **Reliability:** Mission-critical scenarios require extreme robustness. 6G should ensure 99.9999% service availability with self-healing mechanisms to maintain uninterrupted operation in safety, transport, and emergency response contexts.

Network Functionalities

- **Dynamic Resource Allocation and Slicing:** Sub-projects such as AI-PREMSET and Connected Rails highlighted the need for flexible allocation of resources under varying loads. 6G must provide granular, AI-driven network slicing to dynamically prioritize services like URLLC for emergency operations, eMBB for immersive VR/AR, and mMTC for dense IoT deployments.
- **Edge-Cloud Integration:** Several trials (CITY4ALL, Skylink Vision, MILESTONE) relied on offloading compute-heavy tasks. 6G must deliver pervasive and hierarchical edge computing, with resources distributed at pole/street-level nodes, ensuring minimal backhaul latency and optimized energy use.

Infrastructure Deployment Aspects

- **Coverage:** Sub-projects operating in both dense urban (CITY4ALL, Connected Rails) and wide-area (Skylink Vision, AI-PREMSET) settings underline the need for ubiquitous 6G coverage across heterogeneous environments, from crowded city centers to rural regions.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Projects like AI4RTC and AdaptoFlow stressed the importance of sustainable operations. 6G must incorporate energy-aware networking and AI models to optimize resource use and reduce operational costs.

Other Aspects

- **Security and Privacy:** Sensitive applications (public safety, worker monitoring, accessibility mapping) require end-to-end encrypted communication, privacy-preserving AI, and robust authentication mechanisms.
- **AI Model Accuracy and Trustworthiness:** AI systems (MILESTONE, 5GS3, Cities without Barriers) depend on reliable model performance in diverse real-world conditions. 6G should support continuous federated learning and trustworthy AI frameworks for model validation and resilience against adversarial threats.
- **Societal and Inclusivity Considerations:** CITY4ALL and Cities without Barriers demonstrate the need for human-centric 6G design, ensuring inclusivity, accessibility, and digital trust in smart infrastructure.

As final observation, the collective insights from the sub-projects show that while 5G has enabled initial demonstrations of AI-driven automation, surveillance, mission-critical communications, and immersive technologies, 6G must evolve to provide higher capacity, ultra-reliability, pervasive edge intelligence, and secure orchestration. Meeting these requirements will ensure that advanced ITSS use cases can be scaled commercially, delivering transformative benefits for mobility, safety, inclusion, and sustainability.

6 Conclusions

This document, D3.3, serves as the concluding public deliverable of WP3. It provides an in-depth analysis of the fully implemented ITSS domain use cases and trials, covering both the core use cases and the ones added from the Open Call process. It provides a comprehensive overview of the implemented application designs, infrastructure components, functionalities, and measured KPIs and KVIIs during the trials for each use case.

The main conclusions and recommendations for further development, commercialization, and technology evolution toward 6G, based on the completed use cases, are summarized below.

Use Case 1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” (Madrid): The trial at Movistar Arena demonstrated that 5G-enabled devices, including SPOT, SummitXL, and Temi robots, can be remotely controlled with end-to-end latencies below 12 ms, meeting operational requirements for real-time teleoperation. Throughput performance for individual devices was adequate, although downlink aggregate throughput (148 Mbps vs. 200 Mbps target) revealed potential bottlenecks for larger-scale deployment. LiDAR connectivity and limited millimetric-band coverage were identified as constraints for extending coverage to wider areas. Network reliability was maintained throughout the trial, but cybersecurity, fallback mechanisms, and scalability considerations remain essential for commercial deployment. Key takeaways for future 6G deployments include ensuring sub-10 ms latency for responsive robotic control, increasing uplink capacity for multiple high-resolution sensors, and integrating distributed edge computing to reduce processing delays. AI accuracy and device interoperability should also be addressed, while enhanced security, privacy protection, and extensive real-environment measurements are necessary to support large-scale commercial adoption.

Use Case 1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” (Iași): This trial confirmed the benefits of transitioning from 5G NSA to SA architecture with a dedicated URLLC slice. Downlink throughput reached 512 Mbps and uplink 58.6 Mbps, meeting targets, while application-level throughput ranged from 13.6 Mbps for a single camera to 62.7 Mbps for 13 cameras at 2592x1944@25FPS. E2E latency was 10 ms, with round-trip latency including processing between 148–248 ms, supporting near real-time crowd monitoring and AI-based anomaly detection. Trials highlighted that video processing latency depends heavily on server capabilities, indicating the need for distributed edge computing to minimize delays for large-scale deployments.

For 6G, the key requirements include massive uplink capacity (over 10 Gbps per site for 100+ covered cameras), ultra-low latency for instantaneous anomaly detection, and intelligent edge/cloud computing to handle high-resolution video streams. Advanced AI-driven network orchestration and resource management, along with security and privacy-by-design, should ensure scalability, reliability, and public acceptance.

Use Case 2 “Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management” (Athens): The trials at AIA and Technopolis demonstrated that 5G-enabled AMRs, drones, and fixed cameras can perform remote infrastructure inspections with real-time AI analytics. Key performance metrics included uplink throughput of ≥ 30 Mbps, round-trip latency under 50 ms, and RTT jitter below 10 ms. Network functionalities such as dynamic bandwidth allocation, computational load distribution across robot, edge, and cloud, and fallback mechanisms were critical to maintain real-time teleoperation and video analytics. Advanced network slicing enabled concurrent traffic for control, video, and analytics, ensuring consistent operation under high-throughput conditions. Infrastructure deployment emphasized reliable coverage, hybrid edge-cloud processing, and modular, interoperable components. Security, data privacy, and AI model accuracy were validated, while sustainability benefits were observed via reduced physical site visits. For future 6G deployment, ultra-reliable communication, enhanced AI integration, and distributed edge intelligence will be necessary to scale operations, optimize latency, and support automated monitoring across multiple urban locations.

Use Case 3 “Autonomous APRON” (Athens): The trial demonstrated that autonomous baggage transport using the WINGSChariot AGV platform can be effectively managed over a 5G network, meeting key KPIs for UL throughput (~5 Mbps per AGV), DL throughput (~2 Mbps per AGV), round-trip latency (20–30 ms), and jitter (≤ 10 ms). The system successfully streamed 360° video and transmitted telemetry for real-time control, while LiDAR-based navigation and obstacle detection supported safe autonomous operation. Performance remained stable under controlled conditions, though latency peaks above 40 ms suggest that multi-AGV deployment could stress the current network. For commercial scaling, 6G is expected to enable higher device density, ultra-low latency, dynamic resource allocation, and edge computing to process real-time video and navigation data locally. Network functionalities such as fault tolerance, slicing, and AI-driven orchestration will be

essential to maintain service consistency and reliability, while seamless interoperability with airport systems and secure data management will support operational expansion.

Use Case 4 “Smart Traffic Management” (Iasi): The trials confirmed that AI-based traffic monitoring over 5G SA can reliably process video feeds from multiple high-resolution cameras, achieving downlink throughput above 500 Mbps, uplink of 63.5 Mbps, and end-to-end latency of 20 ms. Application-layer throughput ranged from 11.3 Mbps for a single camera to 67.6 Mbps for six cameras, with round-trip latency dominated by edge processing (216–616 ms). The system successfully detected traffic flow, pedestrian and vehicle behavior, and triggered alerts for hazardous situations, validating the software architecture and AI inference pipeline under realistic urban conditions. Future 6G deployments should target above 10 Gbps uplink per cell to accommodate city-wide high-resolution streams, sub-millisecond latency for instantaneous traffic adjustments, and distributed edge compute for real-time analytics. AI-driven dynamic orchestration, self-healing, granular network slicing, and embedded security will be critical to ensure scalability, low latency, reliability, and compliance with privacy regulations for broader urban deployment.

Use Case 5 “Control Room in Metaverse” (Turin): This trial enabled 18 agents from different emergency services to collaborate via a metaverse control room, achieving downlink and uplink throughput of ~35 Mbps, round-trip latency of 30 ms, and system availability averaging 86.5%. VR headsets performed well indoors, but tablets outdoors experienced lower availability due to difficulty to use them during the emergency situations. WebRTC peer-to-peer communication-maintained system responsiveness during moderate load, although startup model loading posed high bandwidth demands. The platform successfully supported real-time video feeds, sensor data integration, and operational coordination. Scaling to larger deployments will require 6G features such as high-capacity, low-latency connectivity, AI-assisted network orchestration, and secure data handling to manage multiple VR users and video streams. Edge-to-cloud communication must be robust, and interoperability with emergency services’ legacy systems is essential. Enhanced cybersecurity and AI-based anomaly detection will further support mission-critical applications, while wearable devices could improve hands-free operation and operational efficiency in real emergency scenarios.

In addition to reporting the trial results, D3.3 provides general considerations on the limitations observed in existing 5G networks for massive deployment scenarios and identifies the emerging requirements for 6G networks. These include aspects such as bandwidth scaling, ultra-low latency, distributed edge processing, AI-driven orchestration, and enhanced reliability and security, which are critical for enabling large-scale, mission-critical applications. The deliverable also reflects lessons learned regarding system interoperability, user acceptance, and operational scalability, offering insights for future commercialization and wider adoption of ITSS solutions across urban and industrial environments.

Additionally, to the main use cases presented above, the series of sub-project trials demonstrated how 5G and B5G networks enable a wide range of AI-driven applications across industrial, mobility, public safety, urban accessibility, and smart city scenarios. Each trial evaluated the integration of advanced connectivity, edge computing, and AI analytics in real-world settings, testing network performance, latency, throughput, and system reliability under operational conditions. The conclusions for these trials are presented below.

Connected Rails (Florence): The trial on Florence’s tram line T1 demonstrated that the integration of the SYS-NGAP positioning system with 5G signal collection is feasible in real-world revenue service. The 5G-based positioning showed good accuracy, supporting real-time tram operations, while network throughput and latency confirmed suitability for operational tasks. Coverage and service continuity require improvement, mainly due to antenna placement and link fluctuations, highlighting the need for optimized network configurations. The trials confirmed that real-time tramway monitoring and obstacle detection are achievable with 5G-enabled systems. Future 6G deployments should focus on improving coverage, reliability, and dynamic resource allocation to support large-scale autonomous vehicle navigation and mission-critical transport services. Edge computing integration and AI-driven orchestration will be essential to maintain low latency and continuous operation across urban transportation networks.

5GS3 (Patra): This sub-project at AIA validated autonomous robotic patrols with AI-driven analytics over 5G/B5G networks. Latency was very low, detection accuracy remained high, and service availability was 100%. The system successfully demonstrated anomaly detection, autonomous navigation, and collaborative responses, confirming reliable real-time operation and centralized monitoring. Minor deviations in network throughput did not affect operational performance. Results show that autonomous surveillance can be effectively supported

over 5G, but large-scale deployments will require 6G capabilities such as ultra-low latency, extreme reliability, and AI-driven dynamic resource allocation for mission-critical and immersive applications.

Skylink Vision (Madrid): The sub-project's trial demonstrated reliable UAV-based aerial surveillance with AI-powered vehicle detection and real-time video streaming over 5G. Communication performance was generally strong, and detection precision was very high. Latency was met under optimized network configurations, confirming the feasibility of real-time UAV operations for traffic monitoring and emergency response. The trials highlight the potential of UAV-based monitoring for public safety and situational awareness. For 6G, further reductions in latency, advanced network slicing, and distributed edge processing will enhance responsiveness, reliability, and scalability for multiple simultaneous UAV streams and real-time analytics.

AI-PREMSET (Iasi): The trial validated the integration of AI/ML-driven optimization with 3GPP-compliant MCX services in a realistic emergency-response environment involving 34 participants over hybrid 5G SA/NSA networks. The system met all target KPIs in areas with adequate coverage, with performance improving after optimized group deployment and scaling of microservice components. Coverage remained the most critical factor, with errors mainly observed in low-coverage zones, highlighting the need for future RAN enhancements. These results confirm the robustness of the MCX solution, its ability to adapt dynamically to network conditions, and its potential to enhance communication reliability and efficiency in PPDR scenarios, especially with further improvements in coverage and proactive resource management.

CITY4ALL (Turin): This sub-project successfully implemented immersive VR experiences to promote awareness and inclusion for individuals with disabilities. Trials in school and university environments showed strong engagement and educational value. While commercial 5G networks presented some limitations for latency-sensitive VR, private 5G SA configurations provided sufficient performance for interactive and comfortable experiences. The outcomes demonstrate that immersive educational applications are feasible over 5G, but scaling to larger audiences and higher-quality content will require 6G capabilities. Key requirements include higher throughput, pervasive edge computing for real-time rendering, ultra-low latency, and enhanced network reliability to ensure broad access to inclusive experiences and support societal objectives.

MILESTONE (Athens): The trial in Technopolis (City of Athens) showed that 5G-enabled video monitoring with AI PPE detection effectively improves worker safety. Thirty-two participants were monitored, and the system successfully detected safety violations in real time. Network and AI performance met targets, confirming reliable and responsive operation. The trial highlights the importance of low-latency, high-throughput connectivity and edge-cloud processing for real-time safety monitoring. For 6G, sub-10 ms latency, pervasive coverage, and dynamic edge intelligence will be essential for scalable deployment in public infrastructure environments.

ATOS Driving (Netherlands): The sub-project's trial in the Netherlands validated remote truck operation over a B5G network under realistic conditions. Performance metrics such as latency, throughput, and packet loss supported stable control and responsive feedback for the tele-operator, with service reliability remaining high. The results show that teleoperation depends on low-latency, reliable communications with dynamic resource management. For 6G, further latency reduction, ultra-reliability, and AI-driven network slicing will be key to supporting large-scale, safety-critical remote operations.

i-CNC (Paiania): The trial of this sub-project demonstrated that integrating 5G connectivity with AI detection for milling chatter improves production quality and efficiency. Thirty participants observed real-time alerts, and network and application latencies stayed within acceptable limits. Downtime and material waste were reduced. This case emphasizes the need for low-latency, reliable links in industrial settings. 6G will require more robust industrial NPNs, real-time edge AI, and ultra-reliable low-latency communication for scalable, autonomous manufacturing.

AdaptoFlow (Iasi): The sub-project's trial in Iași showed that AI-based optimization improves multi-camera video analytics over 5G edge servers. Latency, network load, and energy use were significantly reduced, allowing more camera streams without overloading the system. The case underlines the importance of energy-efficient, scalable edge processing. 6G will need pervasive edge-cloud integration, dynamic resource orchestration, and ultra-low latency to manage large-scale urban monitoring effectively.

AI4RTC (Athens): The trial of this sub-project was performed across five EV stations in Athens and demonstrated that 5G-enabled AI analytics can effectively balance power loads and prevent grid disruptions. About

200 users interacted naturally with ten upgraded charging outlets, and real-time monitoring confirmed high responsiveness and reliability. Network upgrades reduced latency to around 50–70 ms and increased uplink/downlink throughput substantially, supporting over 500 charging sessions without major interruptions. These results underline the importance of low-latency, high-throughput connectivity and real-time AI processing for critical infrastructure. For 6G, sub-10 ms latency, ultra-reliable connections, and pervasive edge intelligence will be key to scaling AI-driven energy management in urban EV networks.

Cities w/o Barriers (Turin): The sub-project's trial in Turin validated 5G-enabled devices and AI analytics for mapping and navigating urban accessibility barriers. Operators collected data over 500 km of pedestrian routes, generating dynamic accessibility maps for people with mobility challenges. Network KPIs were generally stable, though 5G–4G transitions occasionally affected system stability. The project highlights the need for robust, low-latency, and high-coverage networks to support continuous urban monitoring. For 6G, enhanced coverage, seamless connectivity, and edge-cloud integration will be essential for scalable, inclusive smart city applications.

In summary, D3.3 marks the full completion of trials for all project and sub-projects use cases, with extensive quantitative and qualitative data collected to evaluate performance against the initially defined objectives. The measured KPIs and KVIIs provide a robust basis for assessing system responsiveness, reliability, and scalability.

The trials collectively demonstrate the maturity of 5G NSA and SA networks and the ability to support critical services with low latency, high reliability, and scalable throughput. At the same time, they reveal the key requirements that future 6G systems will need to address for massive, real-world deployments. These include significantly higher uplink and downlink capacity to accommodate dense device and sensor populations, sub-10 ms end-to-end latency for instantaneous control and analytics, and intelligent edge-cloud distribution for optimized data processing. 6G is also expected to bring native support for AI-driven network orchestration, advanced network slicing, and integrated security-by-design, enabling fully automated, resilient, and privacy-preserving services at city and industry scale. Together, these considerations position the trials as a critical stepping stone toward defining 6G-ready architectures and operational models that will power the next generation of connected, intelligent systems.

These results confirm that the initially defined operational and technical objectives were successfully achieved. The collected KPIs and KVIIs will be further analyzed and consolidated in the final WP6 deliverable D6.3 to provide a comprehensive evaluation of performance, scalability, and user experience. The innovations and lessons learned from the WP3 use cases will also be highlighted and further analyzed in D6.3, which will consolidate these results to provide a comprehensive view of their impact and exploitation potential. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities will continue until the project's end to ensure knowledge sharing, stakeholder engagement, and broad promotion of validated ITSS solutions across urban and industrial environments.

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Annex A - UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Madrid) pre-trial activities

This section presents the results from the pre-trial activities of UC1 in Madrid.

Trial 1.1 - Crowd monitoring through static infrastructure and artificial vision

For the execution of pre-trial tests and the preparation of Trial 1.1, various phases and tests have been carried out since deliverable D3.2 to facilitate assembly, configuration, and measurement collection for KPI evaluation. The detailed measurement results for the most relevant tests are reported in the following.

AI analytics tests (July 2024)

AI algorithms have been tested under laboratory conditions through the repeated execution of tests. An AXIS P14-41-LE camera configured on a local network (see Table 91) has been used for the execution of the test. Several algorithms from two different providers, AITech and iSentry by IntelxVision were tested to the detection of the following security events: detection of trespassing a fictitious line (AITech AIIntrusion, iSentry Tripwire; detection of abandoned objects (AITech AILost, iSentry Left Object); and detection of suspicious behavior (AITech AISecurity Loitering, iSentry Unusual behaviour).

Table 92 and Table 93 demonstrate the results of tests involving the intrusion detection algorithms, in which intrusion in prohibited areas was attempted in different ways to test the detection capabilities of iSentry and AITech.

Table 91. Test Setup description for Trial 1.1 AI Testing.

Test setup parameters	Test setup ID: AILab_Intrusion / AILab_Objects / AILab_Behaviour
Radio access technology	None
Network type	LAN
Standalone / Non-Standalone	N/A
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	N/A
Bandwidth per component carrier	N/A
Sub-carrier spacing	N/A
MIMO	N/A
Duplex mode	N/A
Other parameters	2m high FHD bullet camera, ambience lighting, non-empty environment

Table 92. Test summary for Trial 1.1 Intrusion detection testing.

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Test setup ID	AILab_Intrusion
Facility/Site	Prosegur Lab

Objective	Test performance of AI Algorithms for the detection of line crossing, to be implemented in UC1; collecting the relevant KPIs
Description	Lab test of AITech and iSentry algorithms for intrusion detection, for unidirectional line crossing walking (01, 02 respectively), running (03, 04) and walking slowly (05, 06); bi-directional line crossing walking (07, 08), walking slowly (09, 10), and running (11, 12)
Executed by	Prosegur
Components involved	Camera AXIS P14-41-LE, iSentry Tripwire, AITech AIIntrusion
Targeted KPIs	KPI#10 (Accuracy) KPI#11 (Precision) KPI#12 (Recall) KPI#13 (F1-score)
Measurement tools	Results registered by the AI systems (iSentry, AITech)

Table 93. Test cases results for Trial 1.1. AILab_Intrusion (Intrusion detection testing).

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_01	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_02	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_03	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.80 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 0.80 KPI#13: 0.89	Accuracy and Recall under expected KPI values, F1 score slightly under expected value
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_04	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.70 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 0.70 KPI#13: 0.82	Accuracy and Recall under expected KPI values, F1 score under expected value
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_05	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_06	KPI#10: 0.85	KPI#10: 1.00	Complied

	KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_07	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_08	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_09	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_10	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_11	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.80 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 0.80 KPI#13: 0.89	Accuracy and Recall under expected KPI values, F1 score slightly under expected value
1.1_AILab_Intrusio_12	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.70 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 0.70 KPI#13: 0.82	Accuracy and Recall under expected KPI values, F1 score under expected value

Table 94 and Table 95 display the results of testing the abandoned object algorithms, involving different objects such as backpacks of different colours and a cardboard box, to test the detection capabilities of each algorithm in a diversity of conditions within the lab.

Table 94. Test summary for Trail 1.1 Abandoned Object detection.

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Test setup ID	AILab_Objects
Facility/Site	Prosegur Lab
Objective	Test performance of AI Algorithms for the detection abandoned objects, to be implemented in UC1; collecting the relevant KPIs
Description	Lab test of AITech and iSentry algorithms for abandoned object detection. Tests were

	performed with a dark backpack left in the middle of the floor (01, 02), leaning against another object (03, 04) and a cardboard box in the middle of the room (05, 06) and leaning against other objects (07, 08)
Executed by	Prosegur
Components involved	Camera AXIS P14-41-LE, iSentry Left Object, AITech AILost
Targeted KPIs	KPI#10 (Accuracy) KPI#11 (Precision) KPI#12 (Recall) KPI#13 (F1-score)
Measurement tools	Results registered by the AI systems (iSentry, AITech)

Table 95. Test cases results for Trial 1.1 AILab_Objects.

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_AILab_Objects_01	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.50 KPI#11: 0.50 KPI#12: 0.50 KPI#13: 0.50	Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 all score lower than expected values
1.1_AILab_Objects_02	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Objects_03	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.60 KPI#11: 0.60 KPI#12: 0.60 KPI#13: 0.60	Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 all score lower than expected values
1.1_AILab_Objects_04	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Objects_05	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.40 KPI#11: 0.40 KPI#12: 0.40 KPI#13: 0.40	Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 all score lower than expected values
1.1_AILab_Objects_06	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied

1.1_AILab_Objects_07	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.80 KPI#11: 0.20 KPI#12: 0.80 KPI#13: 0.32	Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 all score lower than expected values
1.1_AILab_Objects_08	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 0.90 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied

Table 96 and Table 97 reports the summary and results of tests performed involving the algorithms for detection of suspicious behaviour, such as loitering, both for iSentry and AITech algorithms.

Table 96. Test summary for Trial 1.1 Suspicious Behaviour detection.

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Test setup ID	AILab_Behaviour
Facility/Site	Prosegur Lab
Objective	Test performance of AI Algorithms for the detection unusual or suspicious behaviour, to be implemented in UC1; collecting the relevant KPIs.
Description	Lab test of AITech (01) and iSentry (02) algorithms for unusual behaviour detection.
Executed by	Prosegur
Components involved	Camera AXIS P14-41-LE, iSentry Unusual Behaviour, AITech AISecurity loitering
Targeted KPIs	KPI#10 (Accuracy) KPI#11 (Precision) KPI#12 (Recall) KPI#13 (F1-score)
Measurement tools	Results registered by the AI systems (iSentry, AITech)

Table 97. Test cases results for Trial 1.1. AILab_Behaviour (Suspicious Behaviour Detection).

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_AILab_Behaviour_01	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied
1.1_AILab_Behaviour_02	KPI#10: 0.85 KPI#11: 0.90 KPI#12: 0.90 KPI#13: 0.90	KPI#10: 1.00 KPI#11: 1.00 KPI#12: 1.00 KPI#13: 1.00	Complied

Intrusion detection algorithms show some variations depending on the walking speed of the subject crossing the invisible line. Abandoned object detection algorithms are both quite susceptible to generate false positives when there is a change in the scenery, for example, changes in the position of furniture. AITech is more likely to generate false positives due to lighting changes or changing furniture, and does not discriminate elements in the image, with the possibility of it sending an abandoned object alert when a person is standing still for some time. iSentry also suffers from false positives due to environmental changes, but it is able to discern different types of objects and advanced rules can be composed so that only certain types of objects generate an alert (e.g. backpacks, suitcases, bags). However, test results show a need to delimit the detection area adequately to avoid false positives.

Complete setup tests on 5Tonic network

With these changes implemented, a final visit was made to Ericsson's facilities to test all equipment using the final configurations prepared for the UC1 trial.

During this test, all devices were tested individually (1.1_5TonicM01) and then a UC simulacrum was performed by connecting and operating all devices together (1.1.5TonicM02). This was done in order to first check the final configuration of each device individually, and then test the capacity of the network to withstand operation of all devices and robotic platforms to be involved in the final trial. Finally, the devices tested included two cameras and one LiDAR (with two different configurations, the configuration used by PROSE, reported as LiDAR, and the configuration recommended by the provider, reported as LiDAR Legacy) for T1.1, and three robots for T1.2. Table 98, Table 99 and Table 100 showcase the details of the first test performed, 5TonicM01, in which each of the involved perimetral security devices (cameras and LiDAR) were connected to the network one by one, KPIs were recorded, and then they were disconnected.

Table 98. Test setup description for Trial 1.1_5TonicM01.

Test setup parameters	Test setup ID: 5TonicM01
Radio access technology	5G NR Standalone
Network type	Non-Public Network
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	20W
Frequency band	n258
Bandwidth per component carrier	8x100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
MIMO	2x2
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 99. Test summary for Trial 1.1_5TonicM01.

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Test setup ID	5TonicM01
Facility/Site	Ericsson's facilities
Objective	Test the current 5G network definitive configuration KPI values to comply with UC1.
Description	Each device (Cameras: 01; LiDAR: 02, LiDAR Legacy: 03) has been connected, tested and disconnected, measuring relevant KPIs individually
Executed by	PROSE and Ericsson

Components involved	Camera AXIS PE-1447-LE, Camera - AXIS Q6135-LE, LiDAR: Ouster OS1, Router Ericsson 6675, Baseband Ericsson 6648, AIR 5322, LPG 1.3, SDX 75 Based Prototype CPE
Targeted KPIs	KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08 (Application round trip latency)
Measurement tools	Grafana showing 5G Network probes

Table 100. Test case results for Trial 1.1_5TonicM01.

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_5TonicM01_01	KPI#04: 20 Mbps KPI#03: 20 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	KPI#04: 50 KPI#03: 50 KPI#08: 12ms	Complied
1.1_5TonicM01_02	KPI#04: 83 Mbps KPI#03: 83 Mbps KPI#08: 10 ms	KPI#04: 100 Mbps KPI#03: 100 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	Complied, but latency is a little above expected
1.1_5TonicM01_03	KPI#04: 83 Mbps KPI#08: 10 ms	KPI#04: 60 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04 and #08 have values a little above expectations. However, KPI#03 could not be measured due to a limitation of the LiDAR's default characteristics.

During these tests the cameras were operated as usual. Network configurations were finalized for both cameras and LiDAR to facilitate implementation of UC1 as well as to facilitate measuring KPIs during the field test.

Furthermore, as part of the Full test in 5Tonic, a use case test has been implemented by connecting and operating all devices together as during the UC1 trial. This test has been used to validate the network definitive network configuration, as well as to compile and analyze the network KPIs relevant to the Use Case.

Table 101, Table 102, Table 103, and Figure 60 showcase the configuration and results of the second test. During this test, all static devices involved in T1.1 were connected to the network one by one, along with the three robotic platforms pertaining to T1.2. All cameras and robots were operated together as should be in the definitive trial, in order to test it in a controlled environment, and relevant measurements on uplink and downlink throughput and latency were taken.

Table 101. Test setup description for Trial 1.1 5TonicM02.

Test setup parameters	Test setup ID: 5TonicM02
Radio access technology	5G NR Standalone
Network type	Non-Public Network
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	20W
Frequency band	n258

Bandwidth per component carrier	8x100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
MIMO	2x2
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 102. Test summary for Trail 1.1 Lab simulation (5TonicM02).

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.1
Test setup ID	5TonicM02
Facility/Site	Ericsson facilities
Objective	Test the current 5G network definitive configuration KPI values to comply with UC1, by simulating the UC1 operation.
Description	During the test all static infrastructure and robotic platforms involved have been connected to the network together, one by one (Cameras: 01, Kiiro: 02; Yellow: 03; Temi: 04; LiDAR: 05) with the definitive configuration in order to measure relevant KPIs.
Executed by	Prosegur and Ericsson
Components involved	RB-SummitXL (Kiiro), Boston Dynamics SPOT (Yellow), Temi (Amarelo), Camera AXIS PE-1447-LE, Camera AXIS Q6135-LE, LiDAR: Ouster OS1, Router Ericsson 6675, Baseband Ericsson 6648, AIR 5322, LPG 1.3, SDX 75 Based Prototype CPE
Targeted KPIs	KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08 (Application round trip latency)
Measurement tools	Grafana showing 5G Network probes

Table 103. Test cases results for Trial 1.1 5TonicM02.

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.1_5TonicM02_01	KPI#04: 20 Mbps KPI#03: 20 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 25 Mbps KPI#03: 25 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	Complied
1.1_5TonicM02_02	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 50 Mbps KPI#03: 50 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	Complied
1.1_5TonicM02_03	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps	KPI#04: 53 Mbps KPI#03: 53 Mbps	Complied

	KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#08: 12 ms	
1.1._5TonicM02_04	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 60 Mbps KPI#03: 60 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	Complied
1.1._5TonicM02_05	KPI#04: 83 Mbps KPI#08: 10ms	KPI#04: 350 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	KPI#04 and #08 complied, but latency is a little above expected. KPI#03 could not be measured due to a limitation of the LiDAR's default characteristics.

The test validated the necessary KPIs, ensuring compliance with the requirements of each device for UC1 implementation. By testing the operation of all devices, it was ensured that the CPEs provided by Ericsson and the 5G network used was able to support simultaneous operation of all devices complying with required KPI values and hence, the availability to support the trial. As can be observed from the KPIs measurements, latency was a little above expected for the LiDAR. Although the sensor was able to function, and as a fixed sensor, it could be acceptable to have 12 ms latency, it is not ideal and would benefit from a potent network able to provide lower latency levels. Particularly, if a moving LiDAR was used (e.g., mounted in one of the robotic platforms) it would be even of a higher importance to obtain lower latency.

Figure 60. Graphic representation of ping for Test 1.1_5TonicM02.

During the 5TonicM01 tests with the LiDAR, it was identified that both the device and the perception software (Gemini) needed to be on the same network, as it was not possible to configure them on separate networks to measure the KPIs. Hence, to address this limitation during the Trial, the traffic generated by the LiDAR (cloud point) was sent from CPE2 to CPE1. During measurement-taking the cloud point was not processed via Gemini, but it made it possible to measure the throughput.

Trial 1.2 - Crowd monitoring through programmed or tele-controlled robots with AI

Several pre-trial tests have been performed in order to prepare for the final implementation of UC1. These have included operational tests with robotic platforms, cameras, LiDAR and AI Algorithms. The AI algorithms have been tested in laboratory and all devices, including robotic platforms 5G connectivity and configurations have been tested in a public 5G network at Prosegur's lab and in private B5G networks at 5Tonic Lab. These tests have ensured connectivity with CPE prototypes. Finally, a full test with the final configuration has been undertaken, involving all devices.

Three different robots were used simultaneously in the trial, so during the pre-trial activities, each of them was tested separately for connectivity and operation. In Table 104, Table 105 and Table 106, the tests involving solely the robotic platforms are showcased and analysed. Throughout these tests, each of the robotic platforms were connected to the network, operated and disconnected individually and in order; in order to measure uplink and downlink throughput and latency for each of them and ensure adequate operation and connectivity to the CPEs.

Table 104. Test setup description for Trial 1.2 5TonicM04.

Test setup parameters	Test setup ID: 5TonicM04
Radio access technology	5G NR Standalone
Network type	Non-Public Network
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Standalone
Cell Power	20W
Frequency band	n258
Bandwidth per component carrier	8x100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
MIMO	2x2
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 105. Test summary for Trial 1.2 5TonicM04.

Test summary	
Trial ID	1.2
Test setup ID	5TonicM04
Facility/Site	Ericsson's facilities
Objective	Test the current 5G network definitive configuration KPI values to comply with UC1, connecting and disconnecting different UGVs. (Yellow: 01; Kiirro (local): 02, Kiirro (cloud): 03; Temi: 04)
Description	During the trial all different robotic platforms involved (Yellow: 01; Kiirro (local): 02, Kiirro (cloud): 03; Amarelo: 04) have been connected, tested and disconnected to the network with the definitive configuration in order to measure relevant KPIs.
Executed by	PROSE and Ericsson
Components involved	RB-SummitXL (Kiirro), Boston Dynamics SPOT (Yellow), Temi (Amarelo), Router Ericsson 6675, Baseband Ericsson 6648, AIR 5322, LPG 1.3, SDX 75 Based Prototype CPE
Targeted KPIs	KPI#03 (Downlink aggregate throughput) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#08 (Application round trip latency)
Measurement tools	Grafana showing 5G Network probes

Table 106. Test cases results for Trial 1.2 5TonicM04.

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.2._5TonicM04_01	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 8 Mbps KPI#03: 8 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	Uplink and downlink throughput generated by the robots is lower than initially expected but the functioning is adequate.
1.2._5TonicM04_02	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 4 Mbps KPI#03: 4 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	Uplink and downlink throughput generated by the robots is lower than initially expected but the functioning is adequate.
1.2._5TonicM04_03	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 7 Mbps KPI#03: 9 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	Uplink and downlink throughput generated by the robots is lower than initially expected but the functioning is adequate.
1.2._5TonicM04_04	KPI#04: 10 Mbps KPI#03: 10 Mbps KPI#08: 12 ms	KPI#04: 6 Mbps KPI#03: 5 Mbps KPI#08: 12ms	Uplink and downlink throughput generated by the robots is lower than initially expected but the functioning is adequate.

The results of each test demonstrated the successful operation of each of the robotic platforms making use of the 5G CPEs. Uplink and downlink generated were lower than initially expected for each of the robotic platforms, and latency was kept in line with the requirement values, meaning the robot's operation could happen with acceptable low latency levels.

Annex B - UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Iasi) trial activities (5G NSA)

This section presents the results from the 5G NSA trial activities of UC1 in Iasi.

Trial 1.4 - Crowd monitoring using cameras

A comprehensive trial was organized in December 2024 in Iași, Romania showcasing the capabilities of advanced 5G-based video analytics for enhancing public safety and situational awareness in crowded urban environments. This trial builds upon infrastructure work completed earlier, with the full deployment of surveillance cameras and 5G routers on lighting poles finalized in October 2023. The setup was implemented in close collaboration between TUIASI and ORO leveraging a commercial 5G NSA network configuration.

The objective of the trial was to evaluate how 5G-NSA technologies can support intelligent crowd monitoring in realistic scenarios. Specifically, the use case aimed to measure 5G KPIS while using the application for scenarios as people counting, movement direction, crowd density, and detection of specific events (e.g., intrusion into restricted areas).

The trials were performed by implementing the trial setup as detailed in Table 107 while the trial summary is presented in Table 108.

Table 107. Trial setup description for Trial 1.4.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field01
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	Non-Standalone
Cell Power	50 dBm (~120 W)
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	64TX 64RX
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 108. Trial summary for Trial 1.4.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	1.4
Trial setup ID	Field02
Facility/Site	Iasi
Objective	Demonstration of the video analytics application capabilities (2nd version) and performance measurements for the novel 5G NSA & SA network setup
Description	The application focuses on several distinct scenarios of practical interest: a) estimation of crowd density in the surveyed area; b) total count of people passing through a specific access facility; c) detecting objects entering within a restricted access area.
Executed by	TUIASI and ORO

Components involved	5G SA network, cameras and 5G routers, edge-compute infrastructure, video analytics application
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#05 (Downlink throughput per device) KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device) KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#09 (Application one-way latency)
Measurement tools	iPerf3, nPerf, Speed Test, ping, Netdata, Jaeger

KPIs

The KPIs measurements were performed in December 2024 to assess the solution's E2E performance, including both the network side and the application side; the average results obtained from these trials are showcased in Table 109.

Table 109. Measured KPIs for Trial 1.4.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.4_Field02_01	KPI#05: 500 Mbps KPI#06: 50 Mbps KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#05: 512 Mbps KPI#06: 58.6 Mbps KPI#09: 25 ms	This trial was performed during the winter holidays fair that was also happening on the Stefan cel Mare boulevard. Downlink and uplink throughput were very above to the target and E2E latency was significantly better.

Measurements from the 5G CPE measurements are presented in Figure 61.

Figure 61. 5G CPE measurements.

Application-level trials were done by capturing and analyzing the video traffic streamed from one or more cameras devices up to the 5G Lab Edge Compute infrastructure. The cameras are mounted on three different poles.

For the UC1 trial in Iași, three distinct configurations were designed to evaluate the capabilities of the crowd detection model under varying conditions and resource constraints. Each measurement incrementally increased complexity, providing valuable insights into the detection performance, scalability, and resource optimization. In particular:

- **Single Camera on Pole 5 (1.4_Field02_02.1):** In the first measurement, the focus was on evaluating the performance of the system with minimal input. A single camera, identified as pole5cam1, was utilized. The configuration involved the P2PNet model, with input and output video streams at 20 frame-per-second. This setup provided a baseline scenario for assessing the model's efficiency in processing video data from a single source.
- **Multi-Camera Setup on Pole 5 (1.4_Field02_02.2):** The second measurement expanded the input data volume by integrating all four cameras mounted on pole 5. The cameras captured video at a resolution of 1080p@20fps, encoded using H265 compression with a compression factor of 20. To balance computational demands and output efficiency, the input video is subsampled with a factor of 0.25 (only 1 frame in 4 is processed by the GPU), and the displayed output video with a factor of 0.1 (1 frame out of 10 is encoded in output monitoring video), since the current GPU setup is not capable of processing more than approximately 30 frames per second at this resolution. This scenario aimed to stress-test the model's capacity to process multiple high-resolution video streams simultaneously.
- **Distributed Camera Network Across Three Poles (1.4_Field02_02.3):** The third measurement involved a more complex scenario, utilizing 12 cameras distributed across three poles (pole3, pole4, and pole5). Similar to the second measurement, video streams were captured at 1080p@20fps, encoded with H265 compression (compression factor of 20) using variable bitrate encoding, and streamed to the processing server. To avoid bottlenecks in video processing on the server, the output video stream was completely disabled (objects are detected in the streams, but no output video is produced for monitoring), and the input streams are subsampled to 0.025. This configuration was designed to evaluate the model's scalability and its ability to handle large-scale, distributed video data in resource-constrained environments.

Note that the throughput value depends on various factors, including the actual movement content in the view. The results are shown in Table 110 below.

Table 110. Application-level measured KPIs for Trial 1.4.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Description	Validation
1.4_Field02_02.1	KPI#01: 7.78 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 1.58 Mbps KPI#08: 198 ms KPI#09: 25 ms	A single camera running (pole5cam1)	Not very busy pedestrian street impacting the volume of image data and KPI#01 measurements results.
1.4_Field02_02.2	KPI#01: 31.12 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 23.4 Mbps KPI#08: 257 ms KPI#09: 25 ms	All 4 cameras at pole 5, resolution 1920x1080, at 20fps	Average activity in all 4 camera views. Still not enough image details with impact on lower KPI#01 measurements results.
1.4_Field02_02.3	KPI#01: 95.15 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 62.7 Mbps KPI#08: 197 ms KPI#09: 25 ms	All 12 cameras at poles #3, #4, #5,	All cameras on the three poles

			resolutions 12x 1920x1080, at 20fps	are streaming simultaneously. Still not enough image details with impact on lower KPI#01 measurements results.
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The measurements results highlight several key observations and recommendations for enhancing the system's performance. One of the primary challenges identified is scalability. As the number of cameras and the resolution of video streams increase, the processing system struggles to meet the required throughput. This potential limitation considering high deployment volumes indicates a need for improvements in video compression techniques, frame rate control, and network bandwidth allocation to handle the growing data load effectively.

Another notable point is the latency validation, i.e., KPI#09, which measures one-way latency, and KPI#08, which measures round-trip latency, including the latency incurred by video processing. Comprehensive latency measurements showcased validation for the measured scenarios and are essential in future evaluations to ensure the system's responsiveness in real-time scenarios, particularly for high-demand applications. A particular point is that the latency introduced by video processing, which is part of the round-trip latency KPI#08, is significant and highly dependent on the user server hardware capabilities, requiring at least 2-3 fps (e.g. approx. 100-150ms) for video decoding and around 50ms for object detection.

Annex C - UC4: Smart Traffic Management trial activities (5G NSA)

This section presents the results from the 5G NSA trial activities of UC4.

Trial 4.1 - Smart Traffic Monitoring and Safety Application

This trial focused on high-resolution traffic monitoring, latency assessment, and detection accuracy for selected traffic patterns. Performance measurements demonstrated compliance with latency and throughput targets for the 5G NSA configuration. Different trials aiming at sensing traffic participants in areas of interest, estimating car flow, and detecting cars in forbidden areas were performed in December 2024 using the trial setup as detailed in Table 111. The summary of the trials is presented in Table 112.

Table 111. Trials setup description for Trial 4.1.

Trial setup parameters	Trial setup ID: Field02
Radio access technology	5G NR
Network type	Public
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	50 dBm (~120 W)
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	64TX 64RX
Duplex mode	TDD

Table 112. Trial summary for Trial 4.1.

Trial summary	
Trial ID	4.1
Trial setup ID	Field01
Facility/Site	Iasi
Objective	Demonstration of the video analytics application capabilities and performance measurements for the existing 5G NSA setup
Description	The application focuses on several distinct scenarios of practical interest: a) estimation of vehicles density in the surveyed area; b) total count of vehicles and people passing through a specific access facility; c) detecting cars entering within a restricted access area.
Executed by	TUIASI and ORO
Components involved	5G NSA network, cameras and 5G router, edge-compute infrastructure, video analytics application
Targeted KPIs	KPI#01 (Downlink throughput per user) KPI#04 (Uplink aggregate throughput) KPI#05 (Downlink throughput per device) KPI#06 (Uplink throughput per device)

	KPI#08 (Application round-trip latency) KPI#09 (Application one-way latency)
Measurement tools	IPerf3, nPerf, Speed Test, ping, Netdata, Jaeger

KPIs

The KPIs network measurements have been performed during December 2024 with the results being depicted in Table 113.

Table 113. Measured KPIs for Trial 4.1.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
4.1_Field02_01	KPI#05: 500 Mbps KPI#06: 50 Mbps KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#05: 467.2 Mbps KPI#06: 47.9 Mbps KPI#09: 49 ms	New external antenna installed attached to the CPE leading to improved throughput and radio signal quality parameters compared to the previous trials reported in D3.2 [1].

Solution installation for the 5G CPE is presented in Figure 62 while measurements from the 5G CPE, on the 5G network, are showcased in Figure 63 and Figure 64.

Figure 62. 5G CPE installation solution.

Figure 63. 5G CPE throughput measurements.

Figure 64. 5G CPE throughput variation statistics.

Application-level trials were done by capturing and analyzing the video traffic streamed from one or more camera devices up to the 5G Lab Edge Compute infrastructure.

For the UC4 trialing scenarios in Iași, two distinct configurations were designed to evaluate the capabilities of the YOLOv7 model under varying conditions and resource constraints. Each trial incrementally increased complexity, providing valuable insights into the model's performance, scalability, and resource optimization. In particular:

- **Single Camera (4.1_Field01_02.1):** In the first trial, a single camera (poduros5) was utilized to monitor the Podu Roș intersection. The system was configured with the YOLOv7X object detection model, a highly accurate and efficient solution for real-time processing. The input video stream is captured at resolution 1280x720@25fps. This configuration provided a focused trial of system performance and detection capabilities for individual camera inputs.
- **All 6 Cameras (4.1_Field01_02.2):** The second trial scaled up the operation to include all six cameras installed at the Podu Roș intersection. This setup also employed the YOLOv7X model, but with adjustments to optimize resource utilization and prevent GPU processing bottlenecks. Thus, on the server, the input streams' FPS were subsampled by a factor of 0.4 (4 frames out of 10 are processed by the GPU), while the output video streams for monitoring were completely disabled, enabling efficient data processing without compromising the ability to extract key insights from the cameras. This configuration allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of the system's ability to handle high-density, multi-camera environments.

These measurements provided critical insights into the system's capacity to process real-time traffic data under varying conditions, forming the basis for further optimizations and implementations in smart traffic monitoring solutions.

Note that the throughput value depends on various factors, including the actual movement content in the view. The results are shown in Table 114.

Table 114. Application-level measured KPIs for Trial 4.1.

Measurements ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Description	Validation
4.1_Field01_02.1	KPI#01: 2.23 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 4.59 Mbps KPI#08: 253 ms KPI#09: 49 ms	A single camera (pole5 cam1), at resolution 1280x720@25fps	Camera captures a busy intersection area. KPIs have been validated.
1.4_Field01_02.2	KPI#01: 13.38 Mbps KPI#08: 500 ms KPI#09: 50 ms	KPI#01: 22.8 Mbps KPI#08: 305 ms KPI#09: 49 ms	All 6 cameras, at resolution 1280x720 and fps: 4x25fps, 1x15fps, 1 x 10fps	High activity in all 6 camera views. KPIs have been validated.

The trial results highlight several key observations and recommendations for enhancing the system's performance:

- **Throughput Performance:** The system demonstrated solid throughput capabilities. In Trial Case 4.1_Field01_02.1, a single camera operating in a busy intersection achieved a throughput of 4.59 Mbps, significantly exceeding the required KPI#01 of 2.23 Mbps. This result confirms the system's ability to effectively support single-camera configurations under high-activity conditions, meaning increased objects movement in the video stream. Similarly, in Trial Case 1.4_Field01_02.2, the system processed data from six cameras, achieving a throughput of 22.8 Mbps, surpassing the required KPI#01 of 13.38 Mbps. This indicates that the system can handle multiple high-resolution streams simultaneously during average activity scenarios.
- **Latency:** One-way latency measurements (KPI#09) have been in line with the requirements but at the limit of the target, highlighting the importance of comprehensive latency evaluations in future trials. Round-trip latency measurements (KPI#08) include the latency incurred by the video processing, which is significant, since it requires at least 2-3 fps (e.g., approximately 150ms) for video decoding, and around 50-100ms for object detection and tracking algorithms.
- **Scalability:** In terms of scalability, the system successfully managed normal resolution video streams for all six cameras without apparent throughput issues. However, output video was disabled during the trials to prevent bottlenecks. This suggests that while the system can handle current configurations, scaling beyond this setup may introduce challenges. These findings underscore the need for optimization of the 5G network as well as the end-user video processing algorithms to accommodate increasing data loads.

Annex D - UC5: Control Room in Metaverse pre-trial activities

This section presents the results from the pre-trial activities of UC5.

Trial 5.1 - Control Room in Metaverse

Preliminary measurement activities were carried out in Crossmedia's laboratory and documented in D3.2 [1]. A field test was carried out on 8/7/2024. This was aimed to check the capacity of the 5G network both in the Talent Garden building and in the spots that were chosen for the game in the Parco del Valentino (see Figure 65). The tests have been carried out with mobile devices.

Figure 65. Images from the field test of UC5 in the Park of Valentino.

The test set up parameters and the test summaries for Trial 5.1 are given in Table 115, Table 116 and Table 117, while the results are provided in Table 118.

Table 115. Test setup description for Trial 5.1.

Test setup parameters	Test setup ID: Field
Radio access technology	5G NR R.15
Network type	Commercial
Standalone / Non-Standalone	NSA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band	n78
Bandwidth per component carrier	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
MIMO	massive MIMO (mMIMO)
Duplex mode	TDD
Device type	Smartphones and Tablets
Device number	6
Device speed	0 km/h
Slice Configuration	None
Background / simulated traffic	commercial

Table 116. Test summary for Trial 5.1 Field_1 and 2.

Test summary	
Trial ID	5.1
Test setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	Parco del Valentino, Latteria Svizzera (1 on 8/7/2024 and 2 on 30/7/2024)
Objective	To check the 5G capacity in the site of the emergency intervention
Description	6 persons, with mobile devices
Executed by	M. Mazzaglia, A. Basso
Components involved	Only mobile devices for this test, namely tablets and smartphones
Targeted KPIs	Aggregate Downlink and Uplink
Measurement tools	Speed-test Ookla

Table 117. Test summary for Trial 5.1 Field_3.

Test summary	
Trial ID	5.1
Test setup ID	Field
Facility/Site	Talent Garden, via Giacosa 36, Turin (3)
Objective	To check the bitrate in the site where the control staff from security agencies will be located.
Description	2 persons, with headsets and one 5G CPE
Executed by	M. Mazzaglia, A. Basso
Components involved	Only mobile devices for this test
Targeted KPIs	Aggregate Downlink and Uplink, System availability
Measurement tools	Speed-test by Ookla

Table 118. Test cases results for Trial 5.1.

Test case ID	Test requirement	Measurement result	Validation
5.1_Field_1	KPI#03: 100 Mbps KPI#04: 100 Mbps	KPI#03: 130 Mbps KPI#04: 47.5 Mbps	KPI#04 requirement not met. Note: measures varied between 40 and 200 Mbps (downlink) and between 25 and 70 Mbps (uplink). Mean values reported though with high error margins. The network capacity was very unstable most probably due to the distance from the nearby radio

			station and the presence of trees and other obstacles.
5.1_Field_2	KPI#03: 100 Mbps KPI#04: 100 Mbps	KPI#03: 312 Mbps KPI#04: 57 Mbps	KPI#04 requirement not met. Note: Average of 14 measurements of the network at site location in park
5.1_Field_3	KPI#03: 100 Mbps KPI#04: 20 Mbps	KPI#03: 135 Mbps KPI#04: 42 Mbps	Ok

The initial speed test in the park raised some concern since both the downlink and uplink bitrate were varying from a few Mbps to 100 Mbps in downlink or to 30 Mbps in uplink. Conversely, the headsets in the talent Garden, that were connected wirelessly to a 5G CPE performed satisfactorily in line with the requirements. It was hence decided to carry out new measurements that took place on 30 July 2024 were satisfactory as is shown by the graph in Figure 66 only for downlink, while the aggregated uplink was below the target.

Figure 66. Bitrate measurements at the site of the trial on 30/7/2024.

Annex E - KVIs assessment questionnaires

UC1: Smart Crowd Monitoring (Madrid)

Table 119 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC1 (Madrid).

Table 119. KVI questionnaire for Trial 1.1 and Trial 1.2.

Trust/Trustworthiness	1	I trust the AI system to notify me when a security event is happening.
	2	I trust the alerts delivered by the AI system related to potential security issues to be accurate.
	3	I can rely on the data provided by cameras and LiDAR to assist me in performing my job more efficiently.
	4	I can rely on the robots to assist me in performing my job more efficiently, either autonomously or by using remote control when/if necessary.
	5	The system is transparent about the information collected from different sources, how it is used, and how alerts are generated.
Resilience	1	I trust the devices (cameras, LiDAR, robots) to perform their tasks reliably, without issues causing interruptions
	2	The system is able to bounce back and work well after any issues occur.
	3	The devices with B5G/6G network connection have helped me identify security events faster and more easily (e.g. by controlling the robots and cameras remotely).
	4	The devices with B5G/6G network connection have facilitated reacting to, or solving security events faster and more easily (e.g. by controlling the robots remotely).
Security	1	I trust the system's communication encryption to maintain all communications and data safe from access by unauthorized people.
	2	I trust the system's security features to protect its data and operations from potential cyber-threats.
	3	I think using robots for security vigilance is safe.
	4	I think using these AI algorithms for security vigilance is safe.
	5	I am confident that the system can prevent hacking or data breaches.
Societal sustainability	1	The combination of cameras, sensors and robots connected via B5G/6G has allowed me to solve security situations without having a physical presence onsite.

	2	The combination of cameras, sensors and robots connected via B5G/6G can help me avoid potentially dangerous situations for me or my colleagues.
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UC1 (Iasi): Smart Crowd Monitoring and UC4: Smart Traffic Management

Table 120 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC1 (Iasi) and UC4.

Table 120. KVI questionnaire for Trial 1.3, Trial 1.4 and Trial 4.1.

KVI	Statement
Trust/Trust-worthiness	I trust the alerts delivered by the application related to the potential risks raised.
Trust/Trust-worthiness	I can rely on the data provided by cameras to assist me in performing my activities more efficiently.
Trust/Trust-worthiness	I can rely on the application to assist me in performing my activities more efficiently.
Trust/Trust-worthiness	The system is transparent about the information collected from different sources, how it is used, and how alerts are generated.
Resilience	The devices utilized in the use case (i.e., cameras) and network work reliably without frequent interruptions.
Resilience	The system quickly bounces back and works well after any issues.
Resilience	The apps and services run smoothly when I need them.
Operational Efficiency	The system handles concurrent live streams from various sources without slowing down.
Resilience	If something goes wrong, the system provides clear updates or fixes the problem quickly.
Security	The system protects the collected data (i.e., analytics, outputs) from being accessed by unauthorized people.
Security	I feel safe from potential cyber threats while using the system.
Security	The system uses security features (like encryption) to protect the collected data.
Security	I am confident that the system can prevent hacking or data breaches.
Societal Sustainability	The cameras connected via B5G/6G have allowed me to detect potential security situations without having a physical presence onsite.
Societal Sustainability	The cameras connected via B5G/6G help me to avoid potentially dangerous situations for me or my colleagues.
Operational Efficiency	The service was effective.

Operational Efficiency	The service was timely.
Trust/Trustworthiness	Operators can easily understand the operations executed by the system and intervene in case of emergency.

UC2: Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management

Table 121 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC2.

Table 121. KVIs questionnaire for Trial 2.1.

KVIs	Questions
Trustworthiness	I trust the AI system to notify me about the public infrastructure condition (i.e., when a defect is detected).
	I trust the warnings and notifications generated by the detection model in the dashboard to be accurate.
	The system is transparent about how it utilizes the collected data from the various sources (i.e., drones, AGVs, cameras).
	I trust the system to function reliably and consistently.
	The system's insights and information in terms of detected damages appear credible and accurate.
	I can rely on the sources (i.e., drones, AGVs, cameras) to provide me with useful information and assistance to help me perform my everyday tasks more efficiently through the dashboard.
Resilience	The devices utilized in the use case (i.e., drones, AGVs, cameras) and network work reliably without frequent interruptions.
	The system quickly bounces back and works well after any issues.
	I trust that the apps and services will run smoothly when I need them.
	The system handles concurrent live streams from various sources without slowing down.
	If something goes wrong, the system provides clear updates or fixes the problem quickly.
Security	The system protects the collected data (i.e., analytics, outputs) from being accessed by unauthorized people.
	I feel safe from potential cyber threats while using the system.
	The system uses security features (like encryption) to protect the collected data.
	I am confident that the system can prevent hacking or data breaches.

UC3: Autonomous APRON

Table 122 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVIs of UC3.

Table 122. KVIs questionnaire for Trial 3.1.

KVIs	Questions
Trustworthiness	I trust the AI system to notify me about the condition of airport operations (i.e., when issues with AGVs or other equipment are detected).
	I trust the warnings and notifications generated by the detection models in the APRON Digital Twin to be accurate.
	The system is transparent about how it utilizes the data collected from various sources (i.e., AGV sensors such as cameras, LiDARs, and GPS).
	I trust the system to function reliably and consistently, including in critical situations requiring remote control of AGVs.
	The system's insights and information regarding airport operations (i.e., detected anomalies or predicted issues) appear credible and accurate.
	I can rely on the integrated system to provide useful information and assistance, helping me perform airport management tasks more efficiently through the APRON Digital Twin dashboard.
Resilience	The devices utilized in the use case (i.e., AGV sensors such as cameras, LiDARs, and GPS and network work reliably without frequent interruptions.
	The system quickly bounces back and works well after any issues.
	I trust that the apps and services will run smoothly when I need them.
	The system handles busy or stressful situations without slowing down.
	If something goes wrong, the system provides clear updates or fixes the problem quickly.
Security	The system protects the collected data (e.g., sensor data, analytics, outputs) from being accessed by unauthorized individuals.
	I feel safe from potential cyber threats while using the system.
	The system uses security features (like encryption) to protect the collected data.
	I am confident that the system can effectively prevent hacking attempts or data breaches, ensuring the security of airport operations.
Operational Efficiency	The system performs tasks (luggage transfer from point A to point B, autonomous navigation) quickly and efficiently.
	The workflow for luggage transfer minimizes unnecessary steps and redundancies.
	Employees can easily understand the operation executed by the system delivered and intervene in case of emergency.
	The system effectively reduces the time required to complete processes.
	The system minimizes errors, improving overall productivity.

UC5: Metaverse Control Room

Table 123 reports the questionnaire used to evaluate the KVI of UC5.

Table 123. KVI questionnaire for Trial 5.1.

KV	Items
Availability	Av1 - It was easy to access the virtual reality experience
	Av2 - It was easy to communicate with the other operators involved *
	Av3 - I could quickly access the information I needed *
Acceptance	Ac1 - It was easy to use the functions of the control room
	Ac2 - We were able to exchange information promptly *
	Ac3 - The information received was adequate to understand the location and characteristics of the emergency *
	Ac4 - The information received was useful to provide an intervention appropriate for the situation *
	Ac5 - The experience in the control room was sufficiently comfortable (without nausea or other side effects)
	Ac6 - The control room in the metaverse is promising as a standard modality of intervention for the future
Governance	Go10 - The organization of the interventions facilitated effective cooperation among different operational units *
	Go11 - The organization of the interventions promoted operational effectiveness *
	Go12 - The possibility of receiving information during the journey to the emergency site facilitated operational effectiveness
Service	Se13 - The control room is useful for improving operator training in emergency management
	Se14 - The control room is useful for enhancing the service provided to citizens during emergencies
Societal sustainability	So15 - The service was effective *
	So16 - The service was timely *
	So17 - The operational units cooperated effectively *

* For these items an additional evaluation on a 3-point Likert scale (1=“less than in standard operating conditions”; 2=“same as in standard operating conditions”; 3=“more than in standard operating conditions”) is required.